

Annex

Final Summary of the
R&D&I Funded Projects

Additively Manufactured Smart Pipe Segments for Advanced Thermal Management in Space and Earth Applications

Enabling Electrical Function Integration via Design for Additive Manufacturing

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Abstract

In the AHEAD project, we developed and tested two variants of multifunctional pipe segments using metal additive manufacturing: one for CO₂ refrigeration systems in high-energy physics experiments, and one for thermal management systems aboard satellites [1,2]. Each prototype features embedded sensors, electrical interfaces, and structural integration, reducing complexity compared to traditional systems. Compared to state-of-the-art solutions, our pipes simplify integration, reduce mass, and enable better monitoring with minimal additional volume or wiring. A key enabler of this approach is a patented concept [3] that allows the simultaneous printing of structural elements and embedded electrical conductors and connectors using Design for Additive Manufacturing (DfAM) principles. This unique integration eliminates the need for separate wiring, unlocking a new class of plug-and-play multifunctional components. Leveraging additive

manufacturing and embedded sensing, our work paves the way for more efficient and robust thermal subsystems in space and earth applications. This article presents the innovations, benchmarks, applications, and commercialization prospects of these technologies.

Keywords: additive manufacturing; embedded sensing; multifunctional components; thermal management; CO₂ refrigeration; design for additive manufacturing (DfAM); smart structures

1 Technology Description and Benchmark

The AHEAD project addressed challenges in thermal management for both space and earth-bound systems. In both use-cases, conventional technologies rely on surface-mounted or externally bonded Commercial Off-The-Shelf (COTS) sensors and heaters, requiring extensive cabling, increasing system mass, and complicating assembly. The developed pipe segments are manufactured using Laser Powder Bed Fusion (LPBF) with embedded features including:

- Built-in electrical connector and wiring (in a feedthrough configuration for the CO₂ refrigeration use-case)
- Internal COTS or external surface-printed temperature sensors interfaced to the 3D printed wires and connectors
- Built-in heater (for satellite use-case only)
- Weldable or Swagelok fluidic interfaces

In the satellite use-case, the pipe segment replaces multiple bonded components with a single plug-and-play device. The new design integrates heater, temperature sensor, connector, and fluidic interfaces in one monolithic part, overcoming the curvature and bonding limitations of Kapton film heaters and thermistors. The built-in components eliminate the need for adhesives and minimize risks related to assembly, handling, and mechanical stresses.

For the CO₂ refrigeration use-case, the innovation lies in embedding COTS sensors inside the pipe wall and enabling wireless data transfer powered by energy harvesters. Compared to existing solutions where sensors are glued externally or wired through bulky feedthroughs, this pipe simplifies integration and reduces the risk of leaks. The benchmark slide contrasts this with the state-of-the-art showing the compactness, integrated design, and wireless capability, enabling in-situ fluid temperature monitoring inside confined detector systems with minimal mass impact.

The pipe prototypes were fabricated using validated LPBF processes with low porosity (0.01-0.02%), satisfying tensile properties (Rp0.2 ~490 MPa), and high burst resistance (up to 1225 bar). Manufacturing also included resin casting for insulation and precise machining. For the CERN pipe, a stop-and-resume LPBF method enabled embedding of components mid-print without compromising structure or weldability. Both use-cases required rigorous CT scanning, cleanliness tests, helium leak checks, and proof pressure validation to qualify for real operational environments.

2 Technology Applications

2.1. Technology Applications tested during the ATTRACT Project

Two families of prototypes were developed and tested:

1. **Satellite thermal management (MPL):** 15 stainless steel pipe segments were produced featuring surface-printed temperature sensors and integrated heaters. They were tested under thermal cycling (-65 to +85°C), vibration, pressure (up to 96 bar), and cleanliness. CT scans confirmed internal structural integrity and resin quality. At system level, integration into a two-phase ammonia MPL loop validated their heating performance and robustness. Heaters achieved 60 W output with fast response times. While heater performance was validated, the printed sensors showed limitations in accuracy and will be replaced by COTS sensors in future designs. The components also passed burst testing (up to 1225 bar), demonstrating high mechanical strength.

FIG. 1. Satellite Thermal Management use-case (MPL).

FIG. 2. MPL use-case [manufacturing sequence and functional part movie](#)

2. **CO₂ refrigeration (CERN detectors):** 15 pipes integrating COTS sensors and wireless communication systems were developed and tested at CERN's CO₂ Research Apparatus (CORA). These pipes demonstrated pressure resistance (up to 125 bar proof test, 1000 bar burst), leak-tightness, and successful operation within a two-phase CO₂ loop. Wireless temperature readings were enabled by thermoelectric generators (TEGs) exploiting existing thermal gradients. Tests confirmed functionality even under low ΔT conditions when voltage regulation was manually adapted. Although some improvements would be required to reach optimum metrological performance, the Power Management Wireless Board (PMWB) proved that reliable Bluetooth-based sensing could operate with harvested power, highlighting potential for autonomous thermal monitoring in space-constrained environments.

FIG. 3. Refrigeration use-case.

FIG. 4. Refrigeration use-case CAD model (note the two COTS sensors integrated inside the pipe segment).

FIG. 5. Refrigeration use-case test results at system level. The dark blue data was acquired with one of the two sensors through a conventional data acquisition module. The light blue data was acquired wirelessly through the standalone system harvesting its energy from the surrounding environment.

2.2. Technology Applications envisioned after the ATTRACT

The technologies developed in AHEAD are being extended to other domains, and confidential collaborations with industrial partners are ongoing:

1. **Smart surgical instruments:** Integration of embedded sensors in surgical tools to assist surgeons during surgery.
2. **Space energy management systems:** Development of battery packs for satellite and launcher applications. The patented manufacturing concept enables elimination of traditional wiring and connector integration, as all electrical conductors and interfaces are directly 3D printed with the structure.
3. **Consumer goods processing:** Multifunctional machine component integrating structural, sensing, and thermal functions to enable processing of sustainable materials with improved efficiency and reliability. The embedded sensing function will enable future implementation of machine learning capabilities.

For the satellite thermal management use-case, an aluminum version is under evaluation to further reduce weight. This version could be used in the next generation MPL systems of Thales. For CERN applications, future work includes adding flow and pressure sensors to meet the requirements of industrial refrigeration applications.

These forward-looking applications aim to bring intelligence and modularity into traditionally passive mechanical components, offering tangible benefits in design flexibility, integration effort, and operational performance.

3 Commercialization

The AHEAD project has already led to tangible commercial and collaborative results. Based on the two core use cases:

1. **Space systems:** The multifunctional pipe segment developed for satellite MPL systems reached a TRL7 according to EU definition. The next step is to reach this TRL according to ECSS, for an aluminum version, and to replace the surface printed temperature sensor with a

space qualified commercial temperature sensor. The schedule for these future development steps will depend on the funding opportunities available at ESA.

2. **Earth-based systems:** The CERN refrigeration use-case development will continue with CSEM and LISI Aerospace Additive Manufacturing, focusing on extended sensing capabilities to meet the requirements of industrial refrigeration companies.
3. These achievements have opened the way to the **three industrial applications** already mentioned in the previous chapter: smart surgical instruments, space battery packs, and industrial subsystems for consumer goods processing. Projects related to these applications are currently ongoing and benefit from funding by ESA and Swiss national funding programs.

By embedding intelligence at the material level, these developments offer new paths toward efficient, sustainable, and scalable products. From space to healthcare to industry, the underlying value lies in the modularity, robustness, and multifunctionality of these 3D-printed components. Industrial traction and early-stage co-developments confirm the relevance and viability of the approach. Further standardization and TRL consolidation are expected to unlock broader deployment opportunities in the next two to five years.

4 Conclusions

The AHEAD project has successfully demonstrated that the patented [3] combination of design and hybrid manufacturing (i.e. AM with conventional injection and machining) enables the creation of compact, multifunctional pipe segments capable of replacing multiple discrete components in demanding thermal environments. This approach allows structural parts to be manufactured together with embedded electrical conductors and connectors, eliminating the need for separate wiring and integration steps. Both CO₂ refrigeration and satellite thermal management applications have validated the concept, with lessons learned guiding future iterations. This multifunctional manufacturing strategy simplifies integration, improves system reliability, and opens new opportunities in modular design. Beyond these initial cases, the technologies have sparked new innovations in medical, energy, and industrial domains, proving the cross-sector value of this approach.

5 Acknowledgements

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The AHEAD project was coordinated by CSEM, which was also responsible for the Design for Additive Manufacturing (DfAM) of both use cases, with input from Thales Alenia Space France, CERN, and LISI Aerospace Additive Manufacturing. CSEM also developed and printed the embedded sensors and handled the processing of insulating resins. LISI Aerospace Additive Manufacturing oversaw the additive manufacturing process, including the development of printing parameters, stop and resume printing and material validation testing. Thales Alenia Space France led the definition of the satellite thermal management (MPL) use case and carried out validation testing. CERN defined the CO₂ refrigeration use case and conducted validation testing, with technical support from NTNU. Inano Energy developed the energy harvesting solution used in the CO₂ use case.

6 References

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Adaptive Metamaterials for Smart Standalone Histopathology with Polarized Light

MetaHiLight

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Abstract

Treatment decisions for many pathological conditions, including inflammatory, degenerative, autoimmune, infectious diseases, and cancer, are largely based on microscopy study of the surgically excised tissue specimens (histology). Classical histology currently suffers from (1) Time-consuming tissue sample preparation. (2) Intra- and interobserver variability of diagnosis. To mitigate these challenges the MetaHiLight project develops a novel digital diagnostic tool for optical histology using polarized light. Scattering of polarized light in tissue offers detailed examination of tissue microarchitecture, and we present images of Degree of Polarization (DoP) from tissue that allow for the classification of different tissue types using Machine Learning (ML) and Deep Learning (DL) algorithms. To this end MetaHiLight develops miniature optical components based on optical metasurfaces for rapid polarization state control and read-out.

Keywords: Histology, Cancer diagnostics, Metasurfaces, piezoelectric MEMS, polarimeter, tunable waveplate.

1 Technology Description and Benchmark

The MetaHiLight project aimed to develop a novel diagnostic tool for optical histology using polarized light. This has relied on the development of several technologies: A component for rapidly switching between polarized light (component 1), a component for reading out polarization states (component 2), development of Machine Learning (ML) / Deep Learning (DL) algorithms, and tissue phantoms. In the following section each of these technology developments are considered, while the application of these technologies to the intended use-case (polarimetric imaging) is discussed in Sec. 2.

Development of component 1: Ultra-fast adaptive metamaterial dynamic waveplate

Based on the results published in¹ we developed a MEMS-OMS (optical metasurface) dynamic waveplate optimized for 640 nm with active feedback electronics for reliable control to compensate for the hysteresis in the piezoelectric membrane used to actuate the MEMS. Figure 1 is an illustration of the type of plasmonic nanostructures used in this work.

Figure 1 Tunable Waveplate. (a) Array of nanobricks suspended over a gold backplane. (b) Relevant parameters of structures. (c) Electrical field norm at resonance at small gaps spacings. (d) Electrical field norm at large separation.

Due to limitations in the available EBL equipment the optical aperture of the metasurface was limited to a diameter of 100 μm , while the available aperture in the MEMS was 3 mm. For most practical applications it would be advantageous to have a larger metasurface diameter, and to match the MEMS aperture to this aperture to minimize the MEMS mass and thereby maximizing

¹ Meng, C., Thrane, P. C. V., Ding, F. & Bozhevolnyi, S. I. Full-range birefringence control with piezoelectric MEMS-based metasurfaces. *Nature Communications* **13**, 2071 (2022)

the speed. The current implementation has a resonance frequency of around 5 kHz, while a smaller mirror with the same electronics should be able to reach 10 kHz. Figure 2 includes an image of the assembled MEMS-OMS together with control electronics supplied by the company Tunable. The existing technology most resembling this device is full-wave liquid crystal variable retarders, for example Thorlabs LCC1423 can at most be operated at around 40 Hz and has an efficiency of around 95% compared to the efficiency of the MEMS-OMS waveplate with an efficiency of around 60% limited by absorption in the gold mirror and metasurface at the design wavelength of 640 nm.

Figure 2 (a) Tunable waveplate component with control electronics. (b) Demonstrated switching between circular polarization states. (c) Demonstrated switching between linear polarization states.

Development of component 2: On-chip metamaterial polarimeter

The goal was to design, fabricate and integrate a metasurface-based component for single-shot polarization resolved imaging. Multifunctional metasurfaces were designed and fabricated using EBL resulting in surfaces that disperse incident radiation into multiple channels, each corresponding to a specific polarization state for a given wavelength (Fig. 3). Differences in intensities between the various channels are used to calculate the Stoke's vectors of the incoming beam (Fig. 3b). The fabricated and tested metasurfaces were integrated into a camera module and calibration approaches were used to compensate for fabrication imperfections, enabling accurate real-time data retrieval as compared to a Thorlabs PAX1000IR1 polarimeter. The results of

this activity are included in a preprint manuscript that is currently undergoing review for publication².

Figure 3 Characterization of the metamaterial polarimeter. (a) Microscope image of metasurface. (b) Single-shot full Stokes measurement from diffraction contrast. (c) SEM image of metasurface structure.

Development of realistic tissue phantoms.

Phantoms serve as calibration objects for performing benchmarking between different setups, measurement methods, and optimization of the hardware/software. A novel approach to fabrication has been created utilizing 3D stereolithographic printing technology. Two types of phantoms corresponding to early-stage breast cancer (ductal carcinoma in situ) and progressed stage (invasive ductal carcinoma) have been proposed. The phantoms mimic the typical histological paraffine-embedded tissue block of fat tissues with the inclusion mimicking the cancerous lesions in terms of scattering and depolarization.

Figure 4 (a) Degree of polarization map from (b) a tissue phantom. (c) Degree of polarization map from (d) a tissue sample.

² Thrane, P. *et al.* Metasurface Polarimeter for Structural Imaging and Tissue Diagnostics. Preprint at <https://doi.org/10.48550/arXiv.2501.05864> (2025).

Development of ML/DL algorithms.

12 Formalin-fixed, paraffin-embedded (FFPE) blocks of human breast tissue obtained from Biobank Borealis (Oulu, Finland) were scanned using a custom-built polarimetric imaging system (Sec. 2).

The obtained set of images has been annotated using the reference to a conventional histopathological analysis performed by a professional pathologist. Thus, more than 15k annotated vectors were obtained from each sample, forming a total dataset of more than 180k.

Support Vector Machine (SVM) and Random Forest (RF) models were employed to analyze the obtained datasets and classify them into two tissue types: adipose and fibrotic. To optimize model performance, we systematically tested various configurations of SVM and RF parameters. For SVM, we evaluated different kernel functions (linear, polynomial, and radial basis function), and regularization control (C) parameter. For RF, we explored different minimum leaf sizes. The optimal parameter combinations were selected based on the minimum mean square error criterion and were used for further model training and validation across different sample sets. To evaluate model performance, we analyzed accuracy, sensitivity, specificity, and loss plots for both training and testing datasets. As expected, increasing the number of training samples improved classification accuracy. Our results indicate that the RF model may provide better accuracy on smaller datasets, finally achieving an accuracy of 96% (specificity 95%), while the SVM model tends to outperform RF as the training dataset size increases, ultimately achieving an accuracy of 97% (specificity 81%). Both models demonstrate good performance, validating their applicability for tissue classification tasks.

2 Technology Applications

2.1. Technology Applications tested during the ATTRACT Project

Optical histology using polarized light. Current imaging technologies provide valuable insights into tissue architecture but often fail to capture the intricate details necessary for early and accurate disease diagnosis. While conventional methods like scalar light imaging offer broad perspectives, they lack the sensitivity to detect subtle microstructural changes crucial for identifying diseases at their nascent stages. In the MetaHiLight project the use of polarized light has been employed to bridge this gap, offering more detailed examinations of tissue microarchitecture. The developed technique relies on polarimetric mapping of ex vivo tissue samples as illustrated in Fig. 5.

A supercontinuum laser as the light source, with specific probing wavelengths selected via an acousto-optic tunable filter.

A wavelength of 640 nm was used for imaging. In the illumination arm, the linearly polarized light was converted into circularly polarized light using a quarter-waveplate and then focused onto the sample.

The remitted light was collected using a 100x objective lens and analyzed with a Stokes polarimeter. Spatial sample scanning was performed with an XY translation stage, covering 8×8 mm area at a resolution of $50 \mu\text{m}$.

Figure 5 (a) Optical setup (AOTF, acousto-optic tunable filter; M, mirror; I, iris; L, lens; OL, objective lens; BS, beamsplitter; H(Q)WP, Half(Quarter)WavePlate;) (b) Incident and collected light. (c) Illustration of light propagation in a tissue-like scattering medium.

An example of the resulting Degree of Polarization (DoP) maps is shown in Fig. 6b below and compared with a conventional tissue image in Fig. 6a. Note that the contrast between various tissue types in the conventional histopathology image (Fig. 6a) is achieved after several time-consuming sample preparation steps: (1) Fixation (formalin, ethanol, picric acid, etc), (2) Dehydration (alcohol solutions in ascending concentrations), (3) Embedding (wax, celloidin), (4) Sectioning (made with a microtome), (5) Staining (hematoxylin, toluidine blue, eosin, acid fuchsin, etc.), and (6) Mounting (Canadian balsam, self-polymerising media). The Classical histology workflow in hospital pathology labs can take from days to even weeks to fully complete, representing critical loss of time for early therapy that may adversely affect the prognosis of recovery. An advantage of using polarized light is that several of the same features are visible from the DoP without the need for all the preparatory steps.

Figure 6. Comparison of the classical histopathology analysis (a) with the obtained degree of polarization (DoP) map (b) and the results of automated segmentation (c). Segmentation results on the Poincaré sphere (d).

The conventional approach for examining histology samples strongly relies on the skills and qualifications of the pathologist performing the examination. Thus, the traditional method suffers from a large degree of known intra- and inter-observer variability. The polarization information acquired from the scattered light provides a means towards digitally classifying tissue. Figure 6d visualizes the polarization information using the Poincaré sphere. This polarization information can be used to classify the different tissue types by use of ML/DL algorithms (Sec 1), as observed in Fig. 6c.

2.2. Technology Applications envisioned after the ATTRACT Project

Optical histology with Vector Vortex Beams (VVBs). Unlike plane waves which have uniform polarization throughout the light beam and planar phase-fronts, VVBs are *structured* light beams possessing spatially inhomogeneous polarization states (such as radial polarization) and specific spatial distribution of the phase of electromagnetic wave which gives rise to Orbital Angular Momentum (OAM). If a light beam contains spiral phase fronts it will carry an OAM mode. In our continued work, we aim to utilize the interaction of VVBs with complex biological tissues to provide more detailed polarization resolved imaging. This is motivated by the fact that OAM/polarization

inhomogeneity is maintained in the face of optical disturbances³ occurring in tissue.

Cutting-edge metasurface techniques for versatile VVB generation and dynamic control: We aim to further develop our MEMS-OMS platform for VVB generation and control. Given the intricate control over all aspects of a light field needed for VVB generation—which traditionally requires multiple optical elements—OMSs are poised to revolutionize this domain. The ability to generate versatile VVBs with varied OAM orders and polarization patterns, using static OMSs, has been proven⁴.

Studies into turbid tissue-like media: We aim to design and develop a Monte Carlo-based toolbox to replicate VVB propagation in tissue-like media, accounting for the fundamental properties of OAM light/VVBs and the actual experimental setup. The developed MC model will simulate the propagation of various types of VVBs with non-planar wave fronts through the tissue-like medium by implementing iterative solutions of the Bethe-Salpeter equation⁵.

Multidimensional pathology. In addition to enhancing the polarization imaging modality developed in the ATTRACT projects smartOpsy (phase 1) and MetaHiLight (phase 2) with Vector Vortex Beams (VVBs) of light, we wish to also add modalities of combined 3D confocal imaging and spectral information. This will be conducted through further development of the versatile MEMS-OMS platform in the EIC Pathfinder Open project OPTIPATH⁶.

Further development and manufacturability of adaptive chip-based nanophotonic components. The MEMS-OMS platform has been demonstrated to TRL 4-5. To raise the TRL level of the components, one important area of development is the introduction of closed loop feedback mechanisms that enable the accurate actuation of the devices. Another important area relates to manufacturability, aiming to further develop the devices with a line of sight

³ I. Nape *et al.*, “Revealing the invariance of vectorial structured light in complex media”, *Nat. Photon.*, 16, 538–546 (2022)

⁴ Y. Bao, *et al.* “A Minimalist Single-Layer Metasurface for Arbitrary and Full Control of Vector Vortex Beams”, *Adv. Mater.* 32, 1905659 (2020).

⁵ I. Lopushenko, *et al.* “Exploring the evolution of circular polarized light backscattered from turbid tissue-like disperse medium utilizing generalized Monte Carlo modeling approach with a combined use of Stokes and Jones-Mueller formalisms”, *J. Biomed. Opt.* 29(5): 052913 (2024)

⁶ EIC OPTIPATH (2025-2028), Grant agreement ID: 101185769

towards mass production. Amongst other activities, this involves integrating OMS into the MEMS-fabrication process steps.

3 Commercialization

During ATTRACT. The technology development of photonic components in MetaHiLight is cost intensive, and our commercialization strategy during the phase 1 and phase 2 projects has been to secure generated IP through patent filings⁷. We have attended scientific and industrial conferences to make known the technology and identify partners.

After ATTRACT: The required value chain for commercialization of both the MetaHiLight system and the breakthrough MEMS-OMS components exists within the European Economic Area EEA. European industrial players such as **Zeiss** will be an ideal partner for the next stages of TRL5 → 7 development and subsequent commercialization of the MetaHiLight tool. The MEMS and silicon production lines at SINTEF and NILT (partner in the continuation project OPTIPATH⁶), respectively, are ideally suited for fabricating the MEMS-OMS components in small production volumes relevant for the scientific and medical community. If larger volumes are required, production can be transferred to larger **European foundries** like **Silex** in Sweden or **ST's Fabs**. SINTEF has a long track record of both production and technology transfer to larger foundries, delivering for instance over **300'000 MEMS altimeters** to the international aviation industry and **50'000 MEMS pressure sensors** for invasive blood pressure monitoring. NILT has over the last years transitioned from being a provider of primarily master-templates for the nanoimprint industry to becoming an **optical solutions company** offering both fabrication and design as a service, with recent strategy on transmissive metasurface optics. Commercialization of the developed MEMS-OMS components are therefore of strategic importance to both SINTEF and NILT.

The partners aim to exploit and disseminate the results, either directly or indirectly, for instance by out-licensing the results. The exploitation plan of the project follows two paths: One for the OPTIPATH system, and the other for the MEMS-OMS components. Apart from the mentioned medical applications, SINTEF is currently exploring adaptations of MEMS-OMS to other applications requiring small, light and inexpensive optics, e.g. within

⁷ US20230072722A1 Optical Metasurfaces, WO2023041916 Polarisation Changing Structures, US20240353319A1 System for Tissue Analysis, and two additional filings that are not yet public.

drones/robots, 3D-imaging (Lidar, structured light, confocal imaging), projection for AR/VR glasses, free-space optical communications, absorption spectroscopy. If several application areas are identified for MEMS-OMS components that can be fabricated together on multipurpose wafers, this provides a pathway to volume production also for niche applications and therefore cost reductions per component.

4 Conclusions

We have presented the key results of the MetaHiLight project which aims to realize a radically new diagnostic modality for stand-alone sensing and quantitative characterization of biological tissues. The targeted system relies on the development of optical metasurface components for the control and read-out of polarization states, and integration into a setup for polarimetric mapping of ex vivo tissue samples. The resulting polarization information allows for classification of tissue using Machine Learning (ML) and Deep Learning (DL) techniques. Support Vector Machine (SVM) and Random Forest (RF) models were employed to analyze the obtained datasets and classify them into two tissue types: adipose and fibrotic. Our results indicate that the RF model may provide better accuracy on smaller datasets, finally achieving an accuracy of 96% (specificity 95%), while the SVM model tends to outperform RF as the training dataset size increases, ultimately achieving an accuracy of 97% (specificity 81%). Both models demonstrate good performance, validating their applicability for tissue classification tasks.

These results represent an important step towards a miniaturized and automated digital histopathology diagnostic tool that can be used in real-time for detection of cancer, Alzheimer and other chronic diseases.

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High Performance, High Resolution Optical Components in Fused Silica

The Glass2Mass project: High Performance, High-Resolution Optical Components in Fused Silica for the Mass Market: Breaking the Cost/Performance Gap in Next-generation Optics

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Abstract

Fused silica glass is the key material for many optics from refractive optical elements (ROEs), to high-precision optical components such as diffusers or diffractive optical elements (DOEs). Glassomer® has invented a groundbreaking technology for shaping fused silica glass based on “pre-glass” resins that are as easy to structure as polymeric resins. After structuring, the pre-glass material can be turned into high-quality fused silica glass in an oven process. The Glassomer® process is well known for structuring glass with 3D printing, casting and molding. However, for next-generation glass optics, the resolution of the final glass parts needs to be high. For ultra-high resolution Two-Photon Grayscale Lithography (2GL) is the method of choice. 2GL is suitable to provide input for various scalable processes. An established methodology for scalable, high-volume and low-price shaping of optical components is replication. Common methods like IM suffer from the need of high-cost molding tools and lack high-resolution. By combining 2GL and replication technology, UV nanoimprint lithography (UV-NIL) is a powerful tool for achieving high throughput at high resolution. In this project, we show the development of novel Glassomer pre-glass resins for direct printing with

2GL and UV-NIL to generate free-standing high-resolution TPL prints as well as wafer-scale optical parts.

Keywords: fused silica optics, Two-Photon Grayscale Lithography, UV-Nanoimprint Lithography UV-NIL

1 Technology Description and Benchmark

The three common techniques for shaping glasses are a) melt processing, a technique which dates back to the fifth millennium BC, b) grinding, a technique which was already used by Galileo to produce lenses for telescopes and c) etching. Of these technologies, etching allows for the smallest features. Etching can be assisted by lasers to increase the speed and requires dangerous chemicals such as hydrofluoric acid. But the method has limited freedom of design [1]. For polymers, a more straightforward shaping technology exists that create very smooth optical surfaces at high resolution and high throughput: UV-NIL. The process uses a liquid photocurable polymeric precursor, which is hardened within a cost-effective molding tool made of polymer. As the process requires very little force, the wear on the tools is minimized, which is why UV-NIL does not require expensive metal molding tools. This makes the process significantly cheaper than other methods such as injection molding at a series size in the range of 10.000 to 100.000 final parts.

The Glassomer® Technology is a novel avenue for high-resolution structuring of fused silica glass based on composites containing glass powder. These materials can be processed like a polymer and are subsequently converted to transparent high purity fused silica using debinding and sintering. 3D printing of fused silica using these materials has opened new possibilities in high-resolution structuring. Firstly, it is possible to directly print glass by high-resolution Two-Photon Grayscale Lithography (2GL) a technology introduced to the markets by Nanscribe, to achieve high-resolution parts on a small scale. Secondly, the combination of the Glassomer technology with UV-NIL promises the fabrication of fused silica components with high resolution and scalability. Here, the step&repeat process (S&R) by the EV-group allows for a particularly efficient and economical UV-NIL process. In the process, a 2GL master structure is printed at high resolution and this master is replicated numerous times onto a wafer using a polymer resin. This results in a repetitive, high-resolution S&R master for UV-NIL. The quick and easy replication on a wafer level has been optimized by EVG to reach a throughput of up to 30 wafers per hour. This would significantly speed up the process of making small optical parts by the proposed Glass2Mass workflow.

The surface roughness is a critical parameter for optical and glass parts. Different grades of optics can be defined based on their surface roughness [3].

Reaching towards 1 nm roughness is crucial for allowing a wide range of technologies, see **TABLE 1**. To reach such roughness values in conventional processes, ultraprecision machining is needed. Alternative scalable methods for optics fabrication are highly sought-after.

The two products developed in this project are firstly, novel 2GL resins for printing fused silica on the Nanoscribe system at resolutions below 5 μm . Secondly, a resin for UV-NIL replication of fused silica wafers was developed to allow for the replication of optical parts with low surface roughness. Next to these products, a workflow was built to achieve the fabrication of optical fused silica parts by the full process of master generation, imprinting with Glassomer® resin, debinding and sintering. For this purpose, a number of glass wafers was produced and analyzed to establish the resolution and roughness of the final glass structures.

2 Technology Applications

The Glass2Mass project established a technology workflow of the following steps: a) printing of a 2GL master by Nanoscribe, b) replication of this master structure in a step&repeat (S&R) process to achieve the final S&R Master for high-throughput formation by EVG, c) imprinting of Glassomer® resin with the S&R master and hardening of the resin by UV-light to achieve the imprinted green part, d) debinding and e) final sintering of the green part to result in the final imprinted glass wafer. The full process is illustrated in **FIG. 1**. The technology can be used to produce numerous high-resolution structures in fused silica glass and has many potential applications in the field of optics.

Next to the full Glass2Mass UV-NIL workflow, an improved formulation for Glassomer® resins for 2GL was developed. Here, high-resolution and serial throughput was achieved on the Nanoscribe Quantum X system, see **FIG. 2**. A resolution of below 5 μm was achieved and opens up new possibilities for the direct printing of photonic components. The unique combination of high-resolution and on-demand fabrication enabled by the 2GL process allows for the generation of parts according to customer specifications on a small and medium scale. Here, project partner OSRAM assisted in the choice of suitable designs for the next generation of optics.

2.1. Technology Applications tested during the ATTRACT Project

In the project, the workflow shown in **FIG. 1** was used to produce a number of optical structures to demonstrate the potential of the imprinting technology.

As an exemplary application, prisms and grating replicated by the Glass2Mass process are shown in **FIG. 3**. The results show that different structures of high complexity can be replicated by the Glass2Mass technology. In precision optics, the surface quality is crucial for the performance of the parts. Therefore, the surface quality was analyzed by measuring the squared mean height, standard deviation of height distribution (S_q) and the arithmetic mean height, (mean difference from mean height S_a) between the Nanoscribe master and the part replicated by EVG with a Glassomer® resin on an exemplary microlens array (MLA). The results show that the master printed by Nanoscribe achieves S_q values of 3 nm - 4 nm and S_a values of 2 nm – 3 nm, see **FIG. 4**. The data also shows that the final glass parts reach the same values with a slightly increased standard deviation but there are no significant differences. This shows the precision of the method and proves its applicability for high-precision replication.

2.2. Technology Applications envisioned after the ATTRACT Project

After the ATTRACT project, the Glass2Mass resins for 2GL and UV-NIL will be commercialized by Glassomer. To fully use the potential of the technology, other markets will be analyzed for the use of novel, miniaturized fused silica components. This includes parts not just for applications in the UV, but also for applications in data communication. The bandwidth limitations of current data communication networks have seen significant media exposure with the advent of the fifth-generation technology standard for broadband cellular networks (colloquially referred to as 5G).

3 Commercialization

The Glass2Mass project aims producing specialized resins for nanoimprint lithography as well as producing final optical parts from fused silica. The commercialization strategy has three aspects: firstly, the generation of a specialized Glassomer® UV-NIL resin for use on the EVG machinery. Secondly, a specialized Glassomer® 2GL-resin with improved resolution for use on the Nanoscribe Quantum X printing system. Thirdly, a workflow and agreement will be put in place to allow for the production of ready-made fused silica parts by nanoimprinting.

For ready-made glass parts, the goal is to enter the optics & photonics market, which is a particularly attractive market as it requires the transparency and stability of fused silica glass for many applications. The optics & photonics

market is projected to grow from 983.51 billion in 2024 and is expected to reach USD 1752 billion by 2033, growing at a compound annual growth rate (CAGR) of ~ 6.7% from 2025 to 2033 (source: No 120139, Optics and Photonics Market Size, Share, Growth, and Industry Analysis, By Type LED and Lasers, Detectors and Sensors & Imaging Devices, businessresearchinsights.com¹) while the submarket of diffractive optics was valued at USD 1.76 billion in 2024, with a projected growth to USD 2.55 billion by 2033 at a CAGR of 3.9% during the forecast period (source: No 111615, Diffractive Optics Market Size, Share, Growth, and Industry Analysis, By Type (Beam Shaping - Top-Hat, Beam Splitting, Beam Foci, businessresearchinsights.com²). DOE offer the possibility for miniaturization of optical systems, as they outperform classical refractive optics but require less space. The demand for DOE is constantly increasing, from endoscopes and other MedTech devices to head-up displays, augmented reality and projection systems.

For the launch of the novel Glassomer® resins for 2GL, the workflows and agreements are in place as the foundation was laid in ATTRACT 1, for resins with lower resolution. Two-Photon Lithography System Market size was valued at USD 62.51 million in 2024 and is projected to reach USD 103.95 million by 2032 growing at a CAGR of 7.54 % from 2026 to 203 (source: 496522 Two-Photon Lithography System Market Size And Forecast, verifiedmarketresearch.com³). The market is very competitive with Nanoscribe being the market leader. For the two-photon lithography producing companies, novel material innovations are key to bringing their systems into the market. With the unique Glassomer® resins the production of highly stable high-resolution parts is possible and this is expected to increase the market potential for the printing systems significantly.

For the launch of the novel Glassomer® resins for nanoimprinting, a launch is planned for 2026. The global nanoimprint lithography system market size was estimated at USD 130.6 million in 2024 and is expected to reach USD 224.3 million by 2030, growing at a CAGR of 9.5% over the forecast period from 2025 to 2030. (source: 6041017 Nanoimprint Lithography Systems Market Size, Share & Trends Analysis Report By Type, By Application, By Region,

¹<https://www.businessresearchinsights.com/market-reports/optics-and-photonics-market-120139> (accessed June 2025)

²<https://www.businessresearchinsights.com/market-reports/diffractive-optics-market-111615> (accessed June 2025)

³<https://www.verifiedmarketresearch.com/product/two-photon-lithography-system-market> (accessed June 2025)

And Segment Forecasts, 2025 – 2030, [researchandmarkets.com](https://www.researchandmarkets.com)⁴) UV-NIL enables more complex and miniaturized in fields such as semiconductors, biotechnology and optics. EV-group is the worldwide leading producer of precision manufacturing on the wafer scale.

The commercialization of the products for the 2GL and NIL markets were the goal of this project. To achieve the commercialization of the resins, material safety data sheets have been acquired for the mixtures and resin and bottle design was finalized. A commercialization campaign was planned at Glassomer for promoting the novel resins by a product brochure, see **FIG. 5**. The product launch is planned for 2026. Next to the resins, the on-demand production of glass parts by the full Glass2Mass project workflow is targeted. In order to also achieve the production of full optical glass parts, the setup of a pilot production line is needed to allow for a full clean room process and a fast conversion of green parts to glass. This will be part of the negotiations between partners and will likely need further external funding. Currently, further demonstrators are produced for presentation to customers and at trade fairs to generate customer interest in the technology. Additionally, as system for cutting of the final wafers into individual optical parts will be tested to allow for individualization of the produced optics.

4 Conclusions

In this project, two commercial products and an effective workflow for the generation of optical structures were established. Firstly, novel Glassomer® resins were developed for high-resolution 2GL and UV-NIL. These resins can be used by the end-user to produce on-demand glass structures and will be commercialized officially in 2026. Secondly, the Glass2Mass workflow was developed: by combining the expertise of Glassomer, Nanoscribe and EVG the replication of complex small structures was achieved in fused silica glass. For this, a 2GL master was printed by Nanoscribe and converted to a high-throughput UV-NIL stamp by EVG. EVG then conducted the replication of Glassomer® resin on a UV-NIL machine. As a result, glass wafers with imprinted microoptical structures were achieved. The versatility of the process was shown by displaying several exemplary structures and measuring the surface roughness of the produced parts. The roughness is in the range of 1-4 nm, which corresponds to the roughness of the used masters. This proves that the method is a) capable of producing a high-quality surface and b) reliably replicates the used master structures. With an increase in master smoothness potentially even higher smoothness can be achieved in the future. The next step would be to build a pilot manufacturing line that allows for the in-house

⁴<https://www.researchandmarkets.com/report/nanoimprint-lithography-system-market> (accessed June 2025)

production of wafers to ensure a fully-closed clean-room process to further improve the process quality.

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- (3) Zhiyu Zhang *et al* 2019 *Int. J. Extrem. Manuf.* **1** 022001

6 Tables and Figures

TABLE 1: root mean square (rms) roughness values for different grades of optical parts. Replicated from [3].

Application	Roughness (rms)	Manufacturing
Eye glasses	10 nm	Hot press / injection
Illumination Optics	2 nm	Grinding + polishing
Projector Optics	1 nm	Precision grinding + polishing
Photo Optics	1 nm	Ultraprecision grinding + polishing
Space optics	0.5 nm	Corrective polishing + supersmooth polishing
DUV projection	0.3 nm	Corrective polishing + supersmooth polishing
EUV projection	0.05 nm	Corrective polishing + supersmooth polishing

FIG. 1 The Glass2Mass workflow. Nanoscribe prints a 2GL master (a), which is replicated by EVG to give the S&R master (b). The master is used for imprinting a Glassomer® resin drop on a carrier wafer (c) to give the final green part (d). The green part is transformed to fused silica to give the final glass wafer (e).

FIG. 2 Development of commercial Glassomer® Resin for Nanoscribe TPL with $< 5 \mu\text{m}$ resolution. a) Glassomer® resin containers, b) high-resolution TPL print green part, c) high-resolution TPL print final glass part, corresponding to green part shown in b. d) high-resolution print with holes of $4.5 \mu\text{m}$ diameter.

FIG. 3 Exemplary final glass structures on a Glassomer wafer created by the Glass2Mass workflow. a) Exemplary Prisms and b) An exemplary grating in fused silica made by imprinting Glassomer® resins by UV-NIL.

FIG. 4 Variation in S_q (squared mean height, standard deviation of height distribution) and S_a (arithmetic mean height, mean difference from mean height) between the Nanoscribe master and the EVG replica in Glassomer®. The data shows that values are comparable between the master and the replication, reaching currently a value of 2 nm - 4 nm. The standard deviation is slightly increased in the final replica. The Glass2Mass process is thus capable of producing high-quality, low-roughness surfaces.

FIG. 5 Commercialization of Glassomer® UV-NIL resins. Developed product flyers for product launch in 2026.

7 Acknowledgements

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Head-worn 3D-Visualation of the Invisible for Surgical Intra-Operative Augmented Reality

H3D- VISIONaIR

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Abstract

Surgeons must identify vital anatomical structures (i.e., nerves) to prevent damage. Bare-eye identification is extremely difficult; therefore, surgeons require high-resolution discrimination of critical tissues. This project offers a disruptive head-worn Augmented Reality (AR) system, equipped with Hyper Spectral Imaging (HIS) and normal cameras. In total, 55 human in vivo hyperspectral datasets were acquired and annotated for presence of adipose and nerve tissues by experts. These 55 hyperspectral images generated 204 wavelengths, which were processed and analyzed to reduce the a subset of distinct wavelengths that most prominently could distinguish between adipose and nerve tissue. The best-performing combination of wavelengths led to the selection of 5 commercially available wavelength filters. These filters were integrated into a Quest Photonic Devices' camera prism and with automatic segmentation protocols enabled the generation of an AR overlay on top of the normal RGB imaging to emphasis the delicate nerve structures. I-Med Technology built a prototype to demonstrate the performance of the RGB cameras and the prism camera in an integrated manner. From this an all-in-

one PC was equipped with newly developed software to run the integrated demonstrator with the envisioned workflow of AR overlays. Proof of concept was provided by preliminary feedback from surgeons, but thorough clinical testing still needs to be done.

Keywords: near eye display; hyperspectral imaging; automated tissue classification; human tissue; surgery; filter design

1 Technology Description and Benchmark

As aimed for within this H3D-VISIONAIR project, we have developed a novel technology to TRL 6 which in potential offers a breakthrough and disruptive head-worn augmented reality (AR) system for surgeons to see beyond normal eyesight. The technology consists of two multi-spectral cameras (combining visual range with NIR visualization), a All in One computer with real-time data processing, and a high-end stereoscopic head mounted display connected to the operating room infrastructure (Fig. 1).

The input for the AR overlay was determined from 55 human in vivo datasets collected at MUMC, NL with a Specim IQ hyperspectral camera. All data were annotated by expert surgeons who classified images for presence of adipose and nerve tissue. The hyperspectral images generated 204 wavelengths from 400-1000 nm. The data were processed following a standard normal variate normalization (Witteveen). Subsequently, the dataset was fed in a Multispectral Classifier and models were generated for automatic segmentation of the adipose and nerve tissues (Fig. 2).

Hardware development consisted of filter design of 5 chosen wavelength bands into the Quest Photonic Devices sensor camera allowing for the combination of these 5 bands in 1 optical path and final integration in the 3D head mounted display 'Digital Surgical Loupe' of i-Med Technology. The off-line models were translated to newly developed software to generate the real-time (60 ms) AR-overlays (green color for nerve) on top of the normal RGB images (Fig.1). The software uses a framegrabber interface to collect hyperspectral images, which are normalized and processed using CUDA backend, with an output that is stored in the same memory as the other cameras. The hardware realization allowed for continued real-time image acquisition, processing and displaying within max. delay of 60ms.

2 Technology Applications

2.1. Technology Applications tested during the ATTRACT Project

Using the Multispectral Classifier Optimization protocol, various models were tested using the split dataset (70% training and 30% validation): Deep Neural Network, and XGBoost with several ways to optimize performance including transfer learning with a pre-trained ResNet model, architecture modification, class weights and the ReduceOnPlateau learning rate optimizer. Eventually, the DNN gave the best performance in classification between nerve, adipose, other tissue (F1 score 0.494, Fig. 2). Compared to the study by Throckmorton et al. (2023), we confirm proper selection of at least two wavelength ranges that play a role in human nerve identification: 452-484 vs 450, and 595-607 vs 591. This is really a good, as Throckmorton et al. (2023) performed contact diffuse reflectance spectroscopy, which is less challenging than our contactless hyperspectral imaging.

The demonstrator was tested on a technical level according to the set performance requirements. More specifically, the images from the different cameras were pixel by pixel aligned and processing speed was measured and confirmed to be 60 ms. Additionally, a demo was given to clinical experts to receive their feedback, which was positive (Fig. 3).

2.2. Technology Applications envisioned after the ATTRACT Project

Before, continuation of hardware miniaturization and embedded software development, a rigorous test should be performed in a simulated setting (e.g. the carpal tunnel syndrome release) with 10 clinicians who can confirm the correctness of the real-time nerve AR overlay and its added value.

3 Commercialization

To assist the commercialization activities, several dissemination activities were performed, such as conference presentations during the Nederlandse Vereniging voor Evolutionaire Chirurgie (NVEC) conference April 11th 2023, Amsterdam, NL (150 participants), European Association for Endoscopic Surgery (EAES) conference, Rome in 2023 and Maastricht in 2024 (2000 participants), and during the on-line conference of Optics and Photonics Technology summit in 2024. The results were hands-on input and sometimes

assessment of end users (e.g. surgeons) throughout the entire project. Parallel to this, we actively joined the ATTRACT Academy (Fig. 4), which resulted in several student teams from Finland, Spain and the Netherlands working on possible additional application domains, and improvement of the head-mount design. This all resulted in established preliminary contacts with potential technology commercialization stakeholders: Olympus, Anaut, Karl Storz, BBraun, Zeiss, Dendrite Imaging, Lumiled GmbH. Some steps towards the market pathway have been initiated, for example identification of potential roadblocks, compilation and classification of regulatory documentation and requirements. After the project, discussions are being continued with Olympus, Karl Storz and BBraun, and with a new contact 3Shape Dental. Finally, a new EU ITEA grant has been submitted and received with the NL consortium consisting of i-Med Technology, Semlab, Amsterdam UMC, Leiden UMC, Maastricht UMC.

4 Conclusions

From the six objectives set for the project, we achieved four fully, which were Recruitment of hyperspectral datasets of annotated human nerve and adipose tissue, Off-line classification model of these tissues, Integrated hardware and a Demonstrator at TRL6. Two objectives were partially met: i.e. Embedded software, and Clinical feasibility, for which we motivated that this was due to the challenges encountered and overcome within the project, of which one was the search for a proper light source that covers the hyperspectral wavelength region. The final results proof the concept of the H3D-VISIONAIR project, which has led to a new grant to continue the development.

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6 Tables and Figures

FIG. 1. Left: Demonstrator of H3D-VISIONAIR. Right: Proof of concept that data acquisition streams work real-time.

FIG. 2. Left: Annotation performed by expert as reference. Middle: Annotation performed by classifier. Right: Confusion matrix of best performing classifier.

FIG. 3. Demonstrating prototype to team.

FIG. 4. Left prototype of improved light sources made by team Finland. Right: team Finland from the Tampere University who participated in ATTRACT Academy.

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Fast and non-invasive metabolic profile through hyperspectral imaging

Prototyping a light-sheet microscope for the robust and non-invasive metabolic profile assessment based on hyperspectral phasor analysis and artificial intelligence

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Abstract

Infertility, now considered a disease by the World Health Organization, affects an estimated 25 million individuals in the European Union. Assisted reproduction techniques (ART) have addressed many infertility issues and an average of 2% of babies in Europe are born each year through ART. However, despite the growing demand for fertility treatments, only one-third of the assisted reproduction cycles lead to a live birth. A crucial step in the treatment is the selection of the most competent embryo to be transferred to the patient to achieve the birth of a healthy full-term baby. However, current technological developments have not improved reproductive outcomes.

The overarching goal of the HYLIGHT project was to develop a clinical tool enabling embryologists to select competent embryos in an unbiased way. For that we aimed to develop a light-sheet system to carry out non-invasive hyperspectral imaging of embryos, design a protocol for safe and robust imaging on the device as well as develop an AI-based software to assess embryo developmental potential based on their metabolic hyperspectral profile. To date we have developed METAPHOR, Metabolic Evaluation through Phasor-based Hyperspectral Imaging and Organelle Recognition. This innovative imaging method combines multiphoton illumination with artificial intelligence to extract metabolic fingerprints and assess mitochondrial distribution within biological samples, all while using 100% label-free autofluorescence (AF) imaging. We have also designed a table-top light-sheet hyperspectral prototype for embryo assessment that incorporates the

METAPHOR technology, which will be commercialized by the start-up recently established.

Keywords: hyperspectral; AI; embryos; metabolic profile; assisted reproduction; light-sheet

1 Technology Description and Benchmark

The METAPHOR pipeline combines hyperspectral imaging with AI analysis techniques to evaluate the metabolic state of embryos and oocytes. Hyperspectral imaging (HS) is an optical technique, which provides full spectral information at every pixel of an image. As numerous metabolites within a living cell are naturally autofluorescent, when imaged through HS, they provide a clear read-out of the metabolic state of the cell. By using a precise light excitation, the concentration of autofluorescent intracellular metabolites can be quantified using HS imaging, encoding rich metabolic information for multiple metabolites (6+) simultaneously in low signal-to-noise ratio (SNR) conditions, allowing minimal photo-toxicity. Employing near infrared light at 780nm excitation wavelength, strategically chosen to minimize photodamage, enables a comprehensive analysis of embryo and oocyte metabolism without damaging the samples.

Then, an Artificial Intelligence-based software has been designed to transform the data and assess embryo and oocyte quality based on their metabolic profile. We have developed our own software tools for the whole pipeline of the HS phasor sample analysis, from the z-stack acquisition to the classification. In particular, we have generated image processing algorithms to detect and segment embryos and oocytes as well as to compute the spectral histogram, phasor-plot and mitochondria spatial features. The integration of phasor analysis enables the identification of subtle metabolic differences that indicate embryo health and potential of implantation. Moreover, by segmenting mitochondrial images, we have discovered that their distribution can be used as a first-in-class non-invasive biomarker of oocyte competence. We realized that FAD signal clustered inside mitochondria showing a characteristic spectrum. By combining two FAD features (confinement and spectrum range) we were able to segment images with the enriched FAD signal coming from the mitochondria. We then used the segmented images to measure three mitochondrial parameters: average intensity, intensity variance and occupancy. Finally, the classifier performance was done with a Support Vector Machine (SVM) model with a lineal kernel. During training, we used an Akaike Information Criteria (AIC) to avoid over-fitting and to make sure that the generated models employed a low number of parameters and input features.

To implement the METAPHOR pipeline and turn our imaging method into a commercially available clinical device and together with M Squared lasers, under an OEM contract agreement, we designed and built a custom-built proof-of-concept (PoC) light-sheet multiphoton microscope to perform hyperspectral imaging on living samples. The first PoC was installed in the IBEC premises in 2023 and has been used to fine tune the parameters that enable the most gentle, non- invasive imaging of live embryos while still producing sufficient autofluorescent signal strength for reliable downstream analysis. The experience in imaging embryos in the PoC device, together with market research and the input of Dexeus Fertility help us define the technical requirements for safe embryo imaging as well as the requirements in terms of desired usability and functionality. Those inputs were combined to finally obtain a prototype suitable for clinical use. Moreover, as engineering work ensured functionality, performance and technical feasibility of the prototype, collaboration with an industrial design company has also contributed to improving usability, aesthetics and user experience. Thus, while the initial PoC device measures 150cmx90cm, the footprint of the prototype only measures 60cmx60cm, a slick tabletop multiphoton light-sheet specially designed for a clinical setting.

Several methods are currently used for embryo selection. Embryo scoring through morphology is still widely used but biased by its subjective nature as it relies on embryologist experience. Morphokinetic analysis of embryo development has been established lately in most IVF clinics as time-lapse incubators are being incorporated at the clinical practice. However, developmental events are still mainly annotated by the embryologist operating the system, thus prone to subjective bias. To date, new AI-guided annotation systems are being developed. However, even if undisturbed embryo culture in time-lapse incubators benefit embryo development, no algorithm has shown significant superiority regarding reproductive outcomes when compared with standard morphological scoring in large RCTs (Kieslinger et al., 2023; Bhide et al., 2024). Also, genetic screening of embryos has been also adopted to select the most suitable embryo. Controversy is still ongoing regarding the efficiency of preimplantation genetic testing for aneuploidies (PGT-A) as recent data show that PGT-A alone does not improve clinical outcomes for the general population and only shows better reproductive outcomes when performed on embryos of women older than 35 years old (Yan et al., 2021). Regarding other hyperspectral technologies in the reproductive medicine field, fluorescent lifetime imaging microscopy (FLIM), requires a long exposure time of the sample to the laser (minutes instead of few seconds of METAPHOR), and it only tracks two main metabolites (NADH and FAD). Thus, it falls short at providing a full metabolic profile, and the long light exposure time makes it unrealistic for clinical uptake. Indeed, initial attempts

in pilot trials failed to predict blastocysts leading to pregnancy (Sakkas et al., 2024). In conclusion, due to speed, light efficiency and metabolic precision, METAPHOR constitutes the ideal candidate to finally bring science-based robust evaluation of embryos to clinical practice.

2 Technology Applications

2.1. Technology Applications tested during the ATTRACT Project

Our first results published in PNAS have shown the robustness of our AI-based software enabling the identification of subtle metabolic differences that power the classifier (Parra et al., 2024). Employing HS data, our AI pipeline demonstrated high accuracy in distinguishing young mouse oocytes from old ones, which exhibited significantly different metabolic profiles, achieving an average AUC of 96.2% in binary classification (Figure 1). Moreover, METAPHOR's capability predicts the potential of oocytes to reach the blastocyst stage, with an average AUC of 82.2%, highlighting its potential in oocyte selection for assisted reproduction. Moreover, our research has shown that simplifying our analysis from over 34 parameters and to just four—3 key metabolites (NADH, FAD, PPIX) and mitochondrial distribution— we not only simplify the analysis but also increase classification accuracy for oocytes from 89.3% to 98.4%. This simplification not only improves precision but also clarifies how the algorithm works, moving beyond the 'black box' perception of AI. Regarding mouse embryos, we assessed the capability of METAPHOR to discriminate between embryos with different metabolic profiles (Figure 2). For this purpose, we cultured control mouse embryos in a standard medium and obtained metabolically altered mouse embryos by culturing them in media depleted of specific nutrients: i) pyruvate and lactate, ii) glucose, iii) pyruvate, lactate and glucose. The rationale was to alter the substrates of glycolysis (glucose) an oxidative phosphorylation (pyruvate and lactate) and therefore imbalance the cellular redox state. Our approach allowed us to obtain morphologically standard blastocysts with altered metabolic profiles. After HS imaging and image analysis, the AI pipeline was capable of correctly classifying embryos with an average AUC of 93,7%. To understand the performance of METAPHOR in comparison to standard evaluation methods, we asked external expert embryologists to assess the same set of embryos using the brightfield images that corresponded to the HS images, being brightfield image morphological analysis the gold-standard in clinical practice for embryo quality assessment. Their classification reached an average AUC of 51%, which is close to random chance. Thus, the AI algorithm outperformed the human graders, offering an additional layer of information for embryo assessment.

Thanks to the collaboration with our partner, Dexeus Fertility, which provided human samples after obtaining the Ethics Committee approval, we started to test our method in human oocytes. Human oocytes at different maturation stages (GV, MI, MII in vivo and in vitro matured) were obtained either fresh or vitrified from patients under informed consent. After imaging, oocytes were fixed and immunostained for mitochondrial marker TOMM20 as a reference. METAPHOR was able to obtain an HS profile of human oocytes by detecting the autofluorescence of several metabolites (Figure 3). Fresh MII oocytes showed a higher HS signal intensity than MI and GV oocytes, suggesting that metabolic activity in the oocyte increases along with maturation. Next the HS signal coming from the mitochondria was segmented and quantified. We detected notable differences on mitochondria distribution, ranging from characteristic clustered distribution and accumulated towards the centre of the GV oocyte, to a more uniform distribution along the cytoplasm in MII oocytes. MI oocytes were in an intermediate state, with smaller clusters throughout the cytoplasm. These distributions were also observed with TOMM20 immunostaining, therefore validating the mitochondrial segmentation. Based on the mitochondrial signal segmented from the HS images, we developed an oocyte maturation index (OMI) that is capable of capturing the maturation state of the oocyte.

A second set of experiments was designed to test the sensitivity of the method using vitrified oocytes. Our results reflected again a distinct maturation index for MI and in vivo matured MII oocytes. Interestingly, in vitro matured MII oocytes showed a distribution of values expanding the MI values in the bottom and in vivo matured MII values at the top, suggesting that METAPHOR is a robust method to grade the maturation state of human oocytes.

Even if this hyperspectral data was obtained on a Zeiss LSM780 confocal microscope and samples were imaged with a two-photon laser with excitation at 780 nm following the METAPHOR pipeline, several tests were also performed using the proof-of-concept device (Figure 4). We acquired multi-spectral autofluorescence images from pure metabolites live mouse embryos using our four-channel prototype. Spectral and phasor measurements were validated against images from the 32-channel confocal microscope images by virtually matching its channels to the prototype's configuration. Figure 4A shows the spectral comparison and phasors of NADH-free, FAD, and Protoporphyrin IX, where the original 32-channel spectra are represented in red and the virtually reduced in blue. Figure 4B presents the same type of analysis for live mouse embryos. Despite using fewer spectral bands, the prototype reliably reproduced the spectral signatures and phasor distributions. Future experiments with human embryos will confirm the prototype's

applicability for future integration into a non-invasive imaging device for fertility clinics.

2.2. Technology Applications envisioned after the ATTRACT Project

After the ATTRACT project, we aim to further develop METAPHOR for the metabolic assessment of human embryo metabolic profile to finalize the development of a medical device for the IVF field. As the main application envisioned for the project, we will continue the work started with mouse embryos and adapt the software for human samples. Ethics approvals have been already obtained, and preliminary experiments are underway.

Regarding other applications of the technology outside the reproductive field, the use of single-cell imaging techniques for metabolic analysis delivers unique insights on the dynamics of individual cells, enhancing our understanding of cellular mechanisms, molecular interactions and metabolic activities. At present, one of the most commonly used tools to measure metabolism in cell culture is the Agilent Seahorse XF platform, which measures the two main metabolic pathways, mitochondrial respiration and glycolysis. Even if the reading is in real time, the platform requires the use of detection reagents and a plate reader, it is not immediate and results are given at the cell population level, not for individual cells if desired. Moreover, additional technologies such as other photometric chemistry assays, mass spectrometry, mass nuclear magnetic resonance (NMR) or Raman spectroscopy are either invasive, slow or logistically challenging to implement in a small laboratory. Thus, supplying the field of biomedical research with a robust, quick and non-invasive tool for metabolic measurements able to provide readings both at the population and individual cell levels would maximize results minimizing effort.

In addition to our extensive work focused on reproductive health, we have applied hyperspectral imaging to other cell systems, successfully distinguishing between healthy and pathological conditions based on their metabolic profiles.

In pancreatic cells, we demonstrated through glucose-response assays that a miRNA knock-out (KO) model—with impaired insulin secretion—exhibited reduced metabolic activity upon exposure to increasing glucose concentrations (Figure 5). Moreover, the metabolic response to 2-deoxyglucose and galactose treatment differed significantly between control and KO cells. Our analysis revealed that the spectral profile of healthy cells was associated with higher activity in the oxidative phosphorylation pathway.

When applying hyperspectral imaging to human retinal pigment epithelial (hRPE) cells derived from retinal organoids, we observed distinct metabolic shifts between healthy and diseased cells. Longitudinal monitoring over two months showed that hRPE cells from retinitis pigmentosa organoids displayed a more glycolytic metabolism, likely due to mitochondrial dysfunction. Throughout this period, we tracked persistent metabolic alterations linked to ongoing cellular reprogramming and epithelial-to-mesenchymal transition.

Overall, our results demonstrate that hyperspectral imaging provides novel insights into the biological functions of individual living cells, allowing for the detection and quantification of their metabolic activity. Thus, the hyperspectral analysis presented here offers a valuable tool for advancing our understanding of metabolism-related disorders and assessing therapeutic efficacy.

3 Commercialization

The pathway to market started by defining that the ensuing project results would be commercialized by an IBEC spin-off. A 3-way shareholders agreement was signed by the leading scientists of the group, IBEC and Scranton Enterprises BV, a Dutch VC that funded the creation of the inventor's group at IBEC in 2028. The ATTRACT funding was crucial to incubate the development of the hyperspectral technology until it was ready to be launched to the market. Lumiris Spectral Solutions SL was established in Barcelona in December 2023. The newly founded company holds the worldwide exclusive license of the assets of the HYLIGHT project and will manufacture and sell the hyperspectral device. In December 2024 Lumiris raised €1,5M in a successful seed round with private investors and a crowdfunding platform to promote R&D, clinical entry and expansion of the technologies. The round was planned as a bridge round to achieve the necessary requirements and cover the continuity of the company's activities until the Series A round closes. Following preliminary contacts with major investors, Lumiris is preparing a Series A by the end of 2026 to ensure the full development of the device.

Regarding the protection of the assets developed during the HYLIGHT project, we envisioned a stratified Intellectual Property Rights (IPR) protection strategy for our technological pipeline, based on patenting our hyperspectral laser-scanning device and protecting the AI algorithm. We started with an initial Freedom-to-Operate analysis, which resulted in a positive outcome. Once received the FTO, a patentability study was commissioned to a specialized patent law firm aimed at evaluating the novelty and inventiveness of our technology and the overall patentability strategy. The PCT application WO 2023/161375, published on 31st August 2023, claims priority from European patent application number PCT/EP2023/054610 filed on 24th February 2022. The applicants are IBEC and Scranton Enterprises and the

inventors comprise the researchers of the laboratory. Classified under IPC code G01N 21/64, the invention entails the device for measuring intrinsic autofluorescence of a biological sample and the method using thereof. Protection of the software is also underway by registering it on a private registry of digital IP, thus generating a copyright. The algorithm will also be protected as a trade secret by maintaining the source code.

To date we are starting the regulatory pathway to obtain the CE mark for medical device by standardizing all our procedures through quality system. To help us navigate and design the regulatory roadmap we are being assisted by a consultancy company expert in regulatory affairs. This company will advise us in designing both the preclinical and clinical studies and ensure compliance with Good Laboratory Practices (GLP) and Good Manufacturing Practices (GMP).

While preparing the regulatory pathway, the manufacturing agreement with M Squared Lasers will be negotiated and signed, as M Squared Lasers is not only the industrial partner needed to build the prototype but to scale up manufacturing of the final device, as they do through OEM for other companies. The prototype device will be built in M Squared Lasers premises, and once ready it will be installed at IBEC premises. Preclinical tests with mouse embryos will be commissioned by an experienced company such Embryotools, which is located in the Scientific Parc in Barcelona. Shortly after, the prototype will be brought to our clinical partner, Dexeus Fertility where the clinical study will be performed. Further interested clinics might join the study. We expect the clinical study to last only 2 years as the primary outcome will be ongoing pregnancy at 6 weeks. Positive results from the clinical trial will allow the completion of the regulatory requirements and the obtention of the CE mark for a clinical device. In parallel, we will also seek FDA approval for commercialization in the US.

Revenue streams will stem from various sources, including direct sales of the device with careful consideration of product margins, recurring income from consumables required for device operation (culture dishes), service contracts and ongoing AI software updates that may be offered through subscription models, thereby creating a diversified and sustainable financial foundation.

In parallel to the development and commercialization of the clinical device for embryo assessment, Lumiris has started an industrial partnership with Cairn, a British designer and manufacturer of scientific instruments, and Toptica, a German high-end laser systems manufacturer to develop a hyperspectral laser scanning microscope for oocyte assessment. Preliminary data in human oocytes have encouraged us to develop a new optical device that could assist in the quality assessment of human oocytes. This instrument will follow a

different commercialization strategy, starting as a Research Use Only (RUO) device. A RUO product, an in vitro diagnostic tool exclusively tailored for laboratory research and not aimed for clinical diagnostic procedures, does not need to fulfil the regulatory pathway of a medical device, only obtain the CE mark for an electrical device (EMC directive) and risk assessment. Thus, once validated, commercialization of the RUO device should reach the market in lesser time, providing early revenues to the company. Several companies have approached us already interested in the technology even as a RUO device. On one hand, technological companies developing automated systems for the embryology lab that involve oocyte quality control are keen to incorporate this technology into their R&D pipeline. On the other hand, pharma companies in the reproductive medicine field developing ovarian stimulation drugs are also interested in the possibility of oocyte quality control in their R&D endeavours to optimize the hormone dose prescribed to patients, to avoid the risk of overstimulation and allow for a more tailored treatment. The RUO device will serve as the Alpha program of the oocyte assessment device meant for fertility clinics. Further development of the RUO after usage testing, and once technical adjustments are made, the device will be ready to enter the regulatory pathway as a medical device for oocyte assessment at the clinic.

Finally, as we are able to adapt and develop this powerful methodology to different living samples in the reproduction field, we foresee future research devoted to other cellular types such as cancerous cells, known to exhibit an aberrant metabolism, opening new lines of innovation and new markets for Lumiris.

4 Conclusions

Although significant progress has been made in advancing sexual and reproductive rights worldwide, infertility remains a consistently overlooked issue, even as an estimated one in six couples is affected worldwide. Shifting gender roles and growing financial instability have contributed to people postponing parenthood, which, in turn, heightens infertility risks for both men and women.

In relatively nascent fields of medicine, innovation tends to often flourish leading to rapid advancements in treatment options. Reproductive medicine exemplified this phenomenon, demonstrating significant progress in both therapeutic approaches and clinical outcomes since the advent of in vitro fertilization in 1978. However, even if innovation once shaped the field incorporating technologies such as intracytoplasmic sperm injection (ICSI), vitrification or PGT, there is no recent breakthrough technology that has shaken the stalemate of positive reproductive outcomes anchored at around 30%.

The ATTRACT program aims to bridge the academic field and industry stakeholders, contributing to the improvement of European competitiveness and transforming high-impact research into market-ready applications. By focusing on the domain of detection and imaging technologies, the program funded breakthrough technology concepts that could develop into commercial applications and new business ventures.

HYLIGHT project started as an innovative data acquisition method combining multiphoton spectroscopy and phasor to unmix spectrally overlapped fluorophores at a low signal-to-noise regime with amenable computational analysis. Being awarded by the ATTRACT project fueled the development of the technology, steadily progressing through TRL1 to TRL6 in only 5 years. Now, with a patent application in place and a recently established company which closed a successful seed investment round, the HYLIGHT project will reach soon the fertility clinics to provide the field with a whole new paradigm of quality assessment.

Thanks to ATTRACT, a pioneering initiative that accelerated the pathway from lab to fab, Lumiris Spectral Solutions is now poised to challenge the current state-of-the-art at the fertility clinic, while aspiring to also impact other medical fields by its robust single-cell non-invasive metabolic profile assessment.

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6 Tables and Figures

Fig. 1. METAPHOR classification of mouse oocytes and mitochondria segmentation. (A) Representative images of mouse oocytes from three metabolic profiles: young, old oocytes and *in vitro* aged oocytes. Left panel, brightfield image; central panel, HS z plane (scale bar=30 μ m); right panel, HS 4D reconstruction (x , y , z , λ). (B) Phasor plot of the corresponding oocyte on the left. (C) Segmentation of mitochondria based on autofluorescence. For each group, the top panels show HS images from different planes. The bottom panels show the mitochondrial-enriched images obtained after applying the segmentation algorithm. Yellow pixels represent mitochondria; cyan represents the cytoplasm.

Fig. 2. METAPHOR classification for mouse embryos. (A) Representative images of blastocysts from each of the four profiles: control; no pyruvate and lactate (No-PL); no glucose (No-G); and no pyruvate, lactate, and glucose (No-PLG). Left panel, brightfield image. Central panel, HS optical z plane (scale bar=30 μ m). Right panel, HS 4D reconstruction (x, y, z, λ). (B) Phasor plots of the corresponding embryos on the left. The positions of pure NADH and FAD are depicted for reference. (C) A scatter plot showing the position of the phasors' center of mass, representing a single experiment (see SI Fig. 4 for additional examples). Each cross represents the phasors' center of mass of a single embryo. (D) Normalized averaged histograms of the embryos in (C). The solid line represents the average histogram, and the shadowed area represents the standard deviation. (E) Histograms of single cells from control embryos, No-PLG embryos, and red cells from No-PLG embryos

Fig. 3. METAPHOR classification for human oocytes. (A) Brightfield and HS images of fresh human oocytes at different maturation stages, mitochondria segmentation from HS images and immunostaining for mitochondrial marker TOMM20. (B) Representation of the average HS profile for each group (mean \pm SD). (C) Representation of the oocyte maturation index (OMI) for each group.

Fig. 4. METAPHOR images at the prototype. Comparative analysis of spectral data and phasor plots from (A) pure metabolites and (B) live mouse embryos, acquired with both the commercial confocal microscope and the prototype. (C) Panels show the 4 channels and 3D merged images captured by the prototype.

Fig. 5. METAPHOR applications in cell culture. (A) HS 4D reconstruction (x, y, z, λ) images of beta cells from wild type samples and miRNA knock-out model exposed to low (2.8 mM) and high (20 mM) glucose concentrations. (B) Mean spectra representation of wild type and knock out beta cells exposed to low glucose (2.8 mM) and high glucose (20 mM) of (A).

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The SNIFFIRDRONE monitoring system

Drone-based air pollution mapping for environmental monitoring and improvement of quality of life

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Abstract

We have developed and validated an advanced drone-based system for environmental monitoring in industrial settings. The system is specifically designed to detect and map atmospheric pollutants and odorous compounds, offering a novel approach to emissions monitoring in facilities such as wastewater treatment and composting plants.

The sensing platform integrates high-precision, laser-based non-dispersive infrared (NDIR) sensors for the selective detection of ammonia (NH_3) and methane (CH_4), along with broad-spectrum chemical sensors for comprehensive environmental characterization. The system enables real-time, three-dimensional spatial mapping of gas concentrations and odour perception levels. Collected data are transmitted to a cloud-based infrastructure and

visualized through custom-developed software, allowing for intuitive and accessible analysis.

Field validation was conducted at four wastewater treatment plants and one composting facility in Spain. These trials demonstrated the system's operational robustness and measurement reliability in real industrial environments, supporting its advancement to Technology Readiness Level 7 (TRL 7). Results indicate strong potential for broader application across diverse industrial sectors.

From a commercialization standpoint, a patent has been granted in selected national phases, and international protection is progressing under the Patent Cooperation Treaty (PCT), with filings in Europe and the United States. Initial discussions with potential end-users are underway, and to facilitate further commercial development, plans are in place to establish a dedicated start-up company.

Keywords: pollution; environmental monitoring; industrial plants; drone; chemical sensors; odour concentration

1 Technology Description and Benchmark

We have developed a drone-based system for monitoring air pollution in industrial environments. The system monitors in a rapid and comprehensive way not only chemical volatiles concentration but the more elusive magnitude of odour concentration. To achieve the high sensitivity and speed of measurement required, a non-dispersive infrared (NDIR) sensing unit for simultaneous detection of NH_3 and CH_4 was designed, developed, and validated using laser-based technology. The sensor achieves a rapid response time of 1 second and a resolution of 1 ppm. Its compact form factor, lightweight structure, and low power consumption render it particularly suitable for integration as the primary sensing component within a drone-based monitoring platform.

An initial prototype employing inter-band cascade light-emitting diodes (LEDs) was deemed unsuitable due to suboptimal beam quality and insufficient optical power, which adversely affected sensor sensitivity. Subsequent implementation of near-infrared (Near-IR) laser sources significantly improved both sensitivity and measurement stability.

To increase the selectivity of the IR sensor, a modular high-speed sensing unit employing commercially available broad-selective chemical sensors was also developed. These sensors were embedded in miniaturized chambers with volumes under 25 mm³, enabling response times on the order of 1 second. Integration with a high-resolution (2 cm) GPS module allows the system to resolve fine-scale spatiotemporal variations in the dispersion patterns of volatile compounds in industrial environments. The broad selectivity of the sensors further facilitates the estimation of odour perception from chemical concentration data.

Together, these advanced sensing units equip the drone-based system with high chemical, spatial, and temporal resolution, enabling the generation of three-dimensional (3D) concentration and odour distribution maps. The monitoring architecture includes a ground-based station that receives real-time data from the airborne sensors and transmits it to a cloud platform. Custom-developed visualization software enables facility operators to view 3D chemical concentration and odour maps in real time on-site.

1.1. Mid Infrared unit

In this project, we design and fabricate PZT piezo MEMS mirrors for high-speed, low-power, and reliable beam steering to develop external cavities for tunable lasers. These microelectromechanical mirrors use lead zirconate titanate (PZT) thin films for precise and efficient actuation.

The mirrors are 1D tilt MEMS devices capable of achieving large tilt angles exceeding $\pm 3^\circ$ optical while maintaining low-voltage operation (25 V) and high mechanical stability. PZT actuators generate stresses that enable controlled mirror tilt with fast response times and high resonance frequencies, making them suitable for dynamic scanning. The compact design supports wafer-level fabrication for scalable production (Peng Cao et al., 2023).

A key development is the integration of an optical position sensor for precise closed-loop control of the mirror angle. The sensor is positioned on the backside of the MEMS mirror and consists of an LED and two photodiodes placed symmetrically around it. As the mirror tilts, the reflected light distribution changes, altering the intensity received by each photodiode. By measuring the difference in signals relative to their sum, the mirror angle is accurately determined. We have developed both the hardware (optical and electronic circuits) and the software for this position sensing system.

This precise feedback improves stability against vibrations and temperature drift, enables accurate beam positioning, and allows programmable scanning patterns with high repeatability.

Together, these PZT piezo MEMS mirrors with large-angle tilt and integrated optical position sensing provide a high-performance, miniaturized beam-

steering solution, meeting the precision, speed, and integration needs of advanced optical systems in tunable laser development (Peng Cao et al., 2024).

A complete process was established for the development of high-performance mid-infrared interband cascade lasers (ICLs) that meet all critical performance criteria. These devices operate at a wavelength of $3.5\ \mu\text{m}$, deliver a maximum output power of 80 mW under continuous-wave operation at room temperature, and exhibit a low threshold current of 180 mA along with a low operating voltage of 2 V.

Furthermore, by integrating the ICL with a MEMS-controlled mirror in an external cavity configuration, a tunable ICL was demonstrated. This system achieved a tuning range of 90 nm, covering wavelengths from 3520 nm to 3610 nm.

1.2. Near Infrared unit

Most commercially available non-dispersive infrared (NDIR) sensors are not optimized for trace gas detection or for integration with mobile platforms such as unmanned aerial vehicles (UAVs). These sensors are typically designed for methane detection in concentration ranges up to 5% by volume (equivalent to 100% of the lower explosive limit), offering resolution on the order of tens of parts per million (ppm). Enhancing sensitivity generally necessitates an extended optical path length, which poses a challenge due to the compact size constraints of UAV payloads. Furthermore, conventional NDIR sensors often exhibit slow response times when operated remotely from the sample source, further diminishing the system's responsiveness.

Two NDIR-based detection techniques were assessed for their suitability in this application. Photoacoustic spectroscopy (PAS) was considered due to its inherently compact architecture; however, it failed to deliver sufficient sensitivity for the target gas concentrations. In contrast, absorption-based NDIR demonstrated significantly higher sensitivity but required a longer optical path length, complicating integration within the spatial limitations imposed by drone platforms.

To reconcile the requirement for an extended optical path with the limited available volume, a Herriott cell was selected. This multi-pass optical configuration enabled a substantially increased path length within a compact form factor, making it compatible with UAV deployment.

A distributed feedback (DFB) interband cascade laser (ICL) centered at $3.3\ \mu\text{m}$ was employed as the light source. This wavelength was chosen to coincide

with strong methane absorption features and the spectral edge of ammonia absorption, allowing concurrent development of systems targeting both gases and compatibility with future tunable laser designs.

The prototype optical bench comprises a 100 mm Herriott cell, four steering mirrors for precise laser alignment into and out of the cell, and a compact detector aligned with the laser output. Gas samples are collected through a 10-meter-long intake tube suspended beneath the drone. Although this configuration introduces a time delay in detection due to gas transport lag, the system compensates for this effect via timestamp synchronization with positional telemetry data.

Initial testing demonstrated that the absorption-based configuration using a Herriott cell achieved the required sensitivity while remaining within the drone's payload limitations. Methane was detected at concentrations as low as 50 ppb, and ammonia at approximately 1 ppm. The optical alignment using steering mirrors reliably guided the laser beam through the multi-pass cell and onto the detector, maintaining high signal integrity despite the system's compact design. The delayed sampling introduced by the trailing intake tube resulted in an average time lag, which was effectively corrected by applying a calibrated temporal offset during post-processing.

1.3. Machine Learning-Based Odour Prediction Models

Our prediction models for odour evaluation utilize advanced machine learning algorithms to estimate human odour perception in accordance with the EN13725 standard. After dedicated sensor signal processing, the prediction framework is built upon Partial Least Squares (PLS) regression models that convert multivariate sensor signals into odour concentration estimates expressed in European odour units (ouE/m³). These models are calibrated using dynamic olfactometry measurements as ground truth, where trained human panels evaluate odour samples according to standardized protocols.

Through nested cross-validation and sequential forward selection techniques, we have optimized sensor configurations to achieve robust performance with reduced complexity. Our optimized models demonstrate multiplicative root mean square errors of approximately 1.8-2.1 factors, with 95% limits of agreement ranging from 0.25× to 3.91×. Notably, a three-sensor configuration (NH₃, TGS2602, TGS2611) achieves superior performance compared to the full 21-sensor array, with correlation coefficients reaching 0.89 (Alessandro Benegiamo et al., 2024).

For spatial odour distribution mapping in 3D (Fig. 1), we employ Kriging approximation techniques to interpolate odour concentration predictions

across surveyed areas. The drone-mounted system collects geolocalized measurements over the wastewater treatment plant at different heights. The Kriging odour mapping methodology utilizes an empirical estimation of spherical semivariance to model spatial correlation patterns. This approach enables the estimation of both odour concentration and its associated variance, providing uncertainty quantification for the spatial predictions. To facilitate data visualization and analysis, we have developed a graphical user interface based on R-Shiny that supports comprehensive data exploration across different wastewater treatment plants. The interface enables visualization of 3D odour concentration maps, allowing researchers to examine spatial patterns and identify emission hotspots. Additionally, the system provides capabilities for visualizing raw sensor signals across drone flight trajectories, enabling quality control and detailed analysis of sensor responses.

This integrated approach enables real-time generation of continuous odour concentration maps that reveal emission hotspots and facilitate source identification in wastewater treatment facilities.

1.4. Drone-based system

The complete pollution monitoring system (Fig. 2) is composed by the gas specific NDIR unit, a general-purpose gas sensing unit, and an air sampler on board in the drone. Additionally, a high-resolution GPS sensor provides the position of the measuring point with 2 cm resolution. The drone communicates with a ground station via radio communication (LoRA) that receives all measurement in real time and store them locally and resubmits them to a server for immediate access to the data.

The general-purpose chemical sensor unit has been developed with a modular design that contains 11 commercial sensors in four different chambers. The sensors include 8 Metal Oxide sensors, 2 electrochemical, and 1 photo-ionizer detector. The fluidic delivery system features small and individual sensor chambers (0.6 cm³ to 4 cm³) to reduce response time (Alonso-Valdesueiro et al., 2024; Abdelwahhab Bouras et al., 2023).

1.5. Benchmarking

Table 1 compares the advanced features of the IR chemical sensing unit and the drone-based system with those of the current state of the art. The developed infrared (IR) sensing unit offers simultaneous detection of ammonia (NH₃) and methane (CH₄), a combination not previously available in a single commercial unit. It delivers a rapid acquisition rate of 1 s per measurement, representing a

significant improvement over conventional devices (≈ 30 s). The resolution is enhanced to 1 ppm compared with the typical range of 10–100 ppm. The system is optimized for low-power operation, consuming the equivalent of a 1 Ah battery capacity versus more than 6 Ah in comparable systems, and its weight is reduced to 3 kg compared to larger weights of more than 5 kg.

For the integrated drone-based platform, the measurement rate remains at 1 s per sample, enabling dense spatial mapping with a 1 m grid resolution compared with more than 5 m for state-of-the-art systems. The platform uniquely supports odour mapping, with estimates expressed in odour units, and calibration transfer across four wastewater treatment plants (WWTPs) — capabilities that have not been previously demonstrated in airborne monitoring solutions.

2 Technology Applications

The main technology application that has been tested in this project was pollution and odour monitoring in wastewater treatment plants. The modular architecture of the sensor units and flexibility of the sensor technology makes possible to easily adapt the monitoring system to be deployed in additional industrial plants.

2.1. Technology Applications tested during the ATTRACT Project

Prior to field deployment, the system was tested under controlled environments to validate its high performance. The NDIR sensor unit and the broad selective chemical sensor unit went through laboratory tests where they were exposed to known concentrations of target gases.

The infrared (IR) sensing unit was characterized under controlled environmental conditions, including regulated temperature and relative humidity. Calibration and response tests were conducted using methane (CH_4) at concentrations of 5 ppm, 25 ppm, and 50 ppm, as well as ammonia (NH_3) at 200 ppm. The specificity of the multi-gas unit was tested exposing it to the two target gases CH_4 , NH_3 and two other gases CO_2 , H_2S frequently found in wastewater treatment plants. The results show that the IR unit can detect a low concentration of CH_4 of 1 ppm and it does not significantly respond to gases other than CH_4 and NH_3 (Fig. 3). This demonstrates the high sensitivity and selectivity of the IR unit.

The broad-selective chemical sensing unit was evaluated in a speed response test and in a wind tunnel to simulate turbulent flow conditions. The head space of ethanol of 1 l volume chamber was flown into the sensor system. The response time of the chemical sensors was evaluated taking as a reference the response of the photo-ionization detector. The experiments showed that a rapid response of the chemical sensors with a delay of 3s (Fig. 4). To validate the performance in more realistic conditions, the system was tested in a wind tunnel. Ammonia (NH₃) at a concentration of 100 ppm was introduced at one end of the tunnel into the airflow. A fan was operated in cycles of 100 seconds on and 40 seconds off to generate dynamic gas plumes for response analysis. The results obtained showed that the chemical sensors were able to follow the plume generated in the wind tunnel (Alonso-Valdesueiro et al., 2024).

After the laboratory experiments of the sensing units, the complete drone-based system was brought to a Drone Lab to perform experiments in flying conditions. The drone lab is a safe flying area measuring 80 × 40 × 15 meters. Controlled releases of NH₃ were carried out at ground level to assess the drone's ability to detect and localize emissions under realistic conditions. The results showed the good overall performance of the drone-based system to detect released chemical volatiles.

The main application targeted during this project, was pollution and odour monitoring in wastewater treatment plants (WWTPs) (Gutierrez-Galvez et al.). The system was validated through field deployments at four WWTPs located in Spain: Molina de Segura (Murcia), Torredembarra (Tarragona), and Pinedo 1 and 2 (Valencia). A total of 18 two-day measurement campaigns were conducted, during which sensor data were collected across the full extent of each facility. In parallel, 128 dynamic olfactometric analyses were performed to establish correlations between sensor outputs and odour perception. This comprehensive dataset enabled the development and transferability of concentration–odour models across different sites, thereby facilitating more efficient model calibration for future applications. Figure

To assess the broader applicability of the system beyond WWTPs, it was deployed at a composting facility in Torrelles de Llobregat (Barcelona). Two measurement campaigns were conducted, resulting in the generation of both concentration and odour distribution maps. Furthermore, the system has been

deployed in a pork meat processing facility in Girona to evaluate its performance in a different industrial context.

2.2. Technology Applications envisioned after the ATTRACT Project

The potential technology applications include the use of the IR system individually or the complete drone-based system. Having proven that a high sensitivity sensor can be built in a compact size, the basic design can be fitted with different laser wavelengths & pathlengths to target other trace level harmful gasses. Including some which have low absorption to making them impractical to measure with conventional NDIR sensors.

The versatility and scalability of this system enable a broad range of future technology applications, including:

- Agriculture: Monitoring storage environments for produce, optimizing waste treatment processes, and ensuring compliance with environmental regulations.
- Environmental Pollution Monitoring: Deployment in fixed stations or mobile units for real-time, city-wide air quality and pollutant mapping.
- Waste Management: Detection and analysis of landfill gas emissions to support regulatory compliance and improve operational efficiency.
- Healthcare: Measurement of exhaled breath markers such as ketones for metabolic monitoring and diagnostic support.
- Sports Science: Tracking metabolic indicators for performance optimization and health assessment.

The sensor system can be adapted to detect the following gases with high specificity and sensitivity: Ammonia (NH₃), Carbon Monoxide (CO), Nitrogen Oxides (NO_x), Hydrogen Sulphide (H₂S), Volatile Organic Compounds (VOCs).

3 Commercialization

As part of the commercialization actions carried out, a patent was granted in national phases, with ongoing processes in Europe and the United States.

Direct engagement has been initiated with potential customers. To advance commercialization beyond the project, we plan to establish and launch a dedicated start-up company.

3.1. Commercialization actions during the ATTRACT Project

Collaborative efforts have started with a commercial partner to co-develop high-resolution gas sensors specifically designed for environmental monitoring in agricultural settings. The partner company, Gas Sensing Solutions (GSS), has advanced its technological capabilities to support applications requiring trace-level gas detection with enhanced measurement precision.

To protect intellectual property of the drone-based system, a patent application (PCT/ES2022/070265) has been approved in several national phases. The international patent process remains active under the Patent Cooperation Treaty (PCT), with targeted jurisdictions including Europe and the United States. The patent protects the general architecture of the drone-based monitoring system and the procedure to predict the expected odour concentration from the chemical sensor readings using machine learning models.

As part of dissemination activities, a technical workshop focused on drone-based environmental monitoring was organized. The event attracted 70 participants—40 attending in person and 30 joining remotely—and included representatives from seven leading companies in the field: ELLONA, COMMON INVENT, BETTAIR CITIES, KUNAK, AEROMON, OLFASCAN, and INTA. The primary aim was to introduce the SNIFFIRDRONE system, solicit expert feedback, and explore opportunities for collaboration. We received very positive feedback from the companies present in the workshop resulting in two individual interviews with ELLONA, AEROMON. They expressed their interest in commercializing surveys of the monitoring system as part of the activity of their companies. This led to posterior negotiations with ELLONA.

Negotiations are currently in progress with ELLONA, a company specializing in odour monitoring technologies for industrial applications. ELLONA has demonstrated significant interest in integrating drone-based environmental sensing capabilities into its solutions for wastewater treatment facilities, building on its expertise in odour management systems.

Initial engagement with potential end users has begun, involving discussions with entities that have expressed interest in the technology. These include the

ETRA Business Group, Canal de Isabel II (a Madrid-based water management company), the NEOM City Innovation Center (which is planning the installation of 13 wastewater treatment plants), and NewFields Companies, LLC (an environmental consulting firm). The NEOM City Innovation requested us to be part of their technology providers. After going through the required process, we are now listed as technology providers to collaborate in the development and posterior management of the NEOM city.

3.2. Commercialization actions after the ATTRACT Project

Regarding the commercialization of the IR unit as an independent static monitoring system, Gas Sensing Solutions (GSS) has identified the healthcare sector as a key market for high-resolution gas measurement technologies that eliminate the cross-sensitivity issues commonly associated with electrochemical sensors. This enables improved monitoring of anaesthetic gases.

To support product development and market expansion, GSS has appointed a marketing intern to investigate opportunities for broadening the range of detectable gases, with a focus on high-value applications. The integration of lower-cost interband cascade lasers (ICLs) with compact optical designs now allows GSS to offer analytical-grade gas sensing instrumentation. GSS remains committed to the continued development and enhancement of this sensing platform.

As for the commercialization of the complete drone-based system, the initial market analysis has identified industrial facilities as the primary target sector, with a particular focus on wastewater and waste treatment plant operators, composting and food processing facilities, and agricultural applications related to sludge disposal and the monitoring of plant-protection product residues.

The preliminary business plan centers on the development of a drone-based service for the monitoring of environmental pollution. This service aims to provide real-time, spatially resolved data to support compliance, environmental management, and risk assessment.

To support the launch and scaling of the service, a mixed funding strategy is being pursued. This includes capital investment from an established industrial partner with an interest in commercializing the technology, as well as the application for public grants such as those offered under the Producte program.

In parallel, steps are being taken to formally establish a startup company. This includes the identification of a scientist with entrepreneurial ambition to lead

the venture, and the formation of a multidisciplinary team to support product development, business operations, and market engagement.

4 Conclusions

The development and validation of a drone-based air pollution monitoring system represent a significant advancement in environmental sensing technology. By integrating compact, high-resolution NDIR and broadly selective chemical sensors, the system achieves simultaneous detection of key pollutants such as methane (CH_4) and ammonia (NH_3), alongside estimation of odour concentration. Crucially, the system combines real-time sensing capabilities with geospatial data acquisition, enabling three-dimensional mapping of pollutant and odour dispersion patterns.

The replacement of inter-band cascade LEDs with near-IR lasers, in conjunction with a Herriott multi-pass optical cell, markedly improved sensitivity and selectivity within a compact footprint compatible with UAV deployment. The system demonstrated detection thresholds down to 50 ppb for CH_4 and 1 ppm for NH_3 , while the time-delay introduced by the sampling tube was effectively corrected using synchronized telemetry data. Laboratory and wind tunnel testing confirmed the system's responsiveness and robustness under turbulent flow conditions, validating its operational readiness for complex real-world environments.

Complementing the hardware, machine learning models were developed to translate chemical sensor outputs into odour concentration estimates aligned with EN13725 standards. These models, trained using dynamic olfactometry data, showed strong predictive accuracy and generalizability across multiple wastewater treatment plants (WWTPs). Kriging-based interpolation further enabled the creation of high-resolution 3D odour maps, enhancing the system's value for emission source localization and environmental risk assessment.

Field deployment across four WWTPs and two additional industrial sites (a composting facility and a meat processing plant) confirmed the system's adaptability and efficacy in diverse operational scenarios. Its modular design facilitates expansion to new chemical targets and environments.

In conclusion, the SNIFFIRDRONE system establishes a novel framework for airborne, high-resolution pollution and odour monitoring. Its fusion of laser-based spectroscopy, machine learning, and UAV mobility constitutes a scalable and highly sensitive solution with demonstrated industrial relevance. Future applications are envisioned in agriculture, waste management,

healthcare, and environmental compliance, underscoring the system's broad technological impact.

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6 Tables and Figures

Concentration map

Odour map

FIG. 1. Concentration and odour map of two wastewater treatment plants

Drone-based odour and pollution monitoring system

● **Near IR sensing unit**
(NH₃, CH₄)

● **Chemical sensors array unit**
(and air sampler)

Base Station
(on the ground)

FIG. 2. Drone-based pollution monitoring system parts

TABLE 1: Benchmarking

Unit	Feature	Performance	Comparison with state of the art
IR unit	Multi gas	NH3, CH4	No combination of these two gases available on a single unit
	Fast	1s per measurement	30 s
	Resolution	1 ppm	10 - 100 ppms
	Low power consumption	1Ah - Battery powered	> 6Ah
	Low weight	3 Kg	> 5 Kg
	Drone system		
	Fast response	1s per measurement	> 10 s
	Dense mapping	1 m grid	> 5 m
	Odour mapping	Estimated Odour units	Not done before
	Calibration transfer	4 WWTP	Not done before

FIG. 3. High specificity of the IR sensing unit

FIG. 4. Fast response of 3s of the chemical sensors

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Ultralow-power, non-volatile, random-access memory arrays for datacenters and space applications

ULTRARAM™

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Abstract

The memory market is the largest in the semiconductor chip sector and is projected to be worth in excess of USD 230 billion in 2029. It is dominated (>95%) by dynamic random-access memory (DRAM) and flash. DRAM, which is the main (working) memory in everything from smartwatches, mobile devices and personal computers through to datacenters and other computing services is fast and has essentially unlimited program/erase cycling endurance. However, not only is it volatile, meaning that data is lost when power is removed, even when powered DRAM cells require refreshing tens of times per second, which is inefficient. In contrast, flash is non-volatile, but requires up to 20 V to program and erase, making it intrinsically slow with an endurance that is limited to just a few thousand program/erase cycles. This project was focused on ULTRARAM™, a highly disruptive compound-semiconductor version of flash that exploits quantum-mechanical resonant tunnelling to deliver an intrinsically-fast, non-volatile memory with high endurance and ultralow switching energy.

Keywords: memory; compound semiconductors; resonant tunnelling.

1 Technology Description and Benchmark

Fig. 1 shows a schematic diagram of a floating-gate (FG) metal-oxide-semiconductor field-effect transistor (MOSFET), which is the core device underpinning the data-storage flash technology used, *e.g.*, in universal serial bus (USB) drives, smart devices and solid-state drives. In flash, the storage of charge in the electrically isolated FG affects the conductivity of the underlying channel between source (S) and drain (D). When the FG is charged, a larger (positive) voltage needs to be applied to the control gate (CG) to attract a layer

FIG. 1. Schematic diagram of a floating gate (FG) metal-oxide-semiconductor field-effect transistor (MOSFET). Charge stored in the FG increases the control gate (CG) threshold voltage required to induce a conductive channel between source (S) and drain (D). In ULTRARAM™, the barrier between channel and FG is a triple-barrier resonant-tunnelling (TBRT) structure, rather than a dielectric.

of conducting electrons that will allow current to flow from S to D than if the FG is discharged. Hence, application of a voltage between the upper (FG charged) and lower (FG discharged) threshold voltages along with detection of current flow can ascertain if the FG is occupied, a logical '0', or unoccupied, a logical '1'. Charging or discharging the FG requires the application of a large voltage, up to 20 V, to the CG to overcome the insulating barrier between the FG and the channel.¹ While flash is non-volatile and the occupancy of the FG (logical state) can be read many times without affecting it, an advantageous property called 'non-destructive read', the large voltage needed to charge and discharge the FG makes flash intrinsically slow to program and erase and is damaging, such that at individual cell level its endurance is only a few thousand program-erase cycles.²

ULTRARAM™ is also an FG memory, a compound-semiconductor version of flash in which the insulating barrier between the FG and channel is replaced by a triple-barrier resonant-tunnelling (TBRT) structure consisting of alternating ultrathin layers of aluminium antimonide (AlSb), acting as barriers, and indium arsenide (InAs), acting as quantum wells (QWs) with just one or two quantized levels (Fig. 2). In the absence of any applied bias to the CG, the TBRT very effectively blocks the passage of electrons, but with a CG bias of

¹ The insulating barrier between the FG and the CG is much thicker, such that current (charge) does not flow from one to the other.

² On a large scale, *e.g.*, in a solid-state drive (SSD), this is mitigated by sheer capacity and management techniques such as ensuring cells across the SSD are used uniformly.

just ~ 2.5 V electrons can rapidly tunnel through the TBRT via the quantized levels in the InAs QWs of the TBRT [Hayne]. This eliminates flash's deficiencies, resulting in memory that [Hodgson]: is non-volatile, with storage times of at least 1,000 years; is high endurance with degradation-free operation for at least 10^7 program erase cycles; has non-destructive read; has a switching energy that is 100 and 1,000 times lower than DRAM and flash per unit area respectively; is intrinsically fast, with ns-switching speeds predicted [Lane].

In this ATTRACT 2 project

the main focus of the work was scaling the technology, *i.e.*, scaling the sizes

of devices down and scaling up from single devices to small arrays. By far the most challenging aspect of this was moving away from wet chemical etching during device processing used previously [Hodgson] to 'dry' processing. Wet chemical etching has the considerable advantage that it can be highly material selective, allowing precise etching of the thin layers in ULTRARAM™, but it is unsuitable for sub- μm devices as it is isotropic, such that it can damage or even completely destroy sub- μm features as a result of undesirable lateral as well as

FIG. 2. Left: Transmission electron microscope (TEM) image showing the different semiconductor layers of a typical ULTRARAM™ device (details vary). Right: atomic-resolution image of the TBRT, the thinnest layer of which is just two lattice constants (1.2 nm).

FIG. 3. Experimental (top) and simulated (bottom) reflectance curve at 365 nm (1 of 3 wavelengths available) for etching of an ULTRARAM™ device. The horizontal axis for the experimental curve is time, whereas it is etch depth for the simulation. The curves do not align due to different etch rates in different layers. The channel etch, characterized by a linear increase in reflectance, is deliberately slow, taking almost 100 seconds, and allowing 1-nm etching accuracy.

the required vertical etching. Instead, dry etching using ion bombardment is used which is a combination of mechanical and chemical etching, and can result in (almost) vertical etching, but at the cost of the loss of selectivity. This makes dry etching of the ultrathin layers in ULTRARAM™ very challenging, in particular, etching to the ~10-nm InAs channel to allow deposition of source and drain contact. At least some over- etching is inevitable, causing undesirable parasitic resistance in the portion of the channel between the gate stack and the source and drain contacts. This parasitic resistance dampens the total change in source-drain current as a result of the presence or absence of charge in the floating gate, and increases the fraction of leakage current, *i.e.*, current that flows from source to drain without passing under the gate stack. Via the exploitation of state-of-the-art end-point technology using multi-wavelength reflectometry in a collaboration with LayTec GmbH (Berlin) we are now able to etch the channel with an accuracy of about 1 nm (Fig. 3). In the best case the 0/1 memory window contrast exceeds what was achieved for wet-etched devices by a factor of 60 (Fig. 4).

FIG. 4. Best-case program (0) and erase (1) currents for a recent, dry-etched, device (main figure) and a previous wet-etched device [Hodgson] (inset). The memory window in the recent device is 1.25 mA, whereas is the wet-etched device it stabilizes at 0.02 mA, which is 60 times smaller.

2 Technology Applications

As a candidate ‘universal’ memory, with the characteristics of non-volatility, speed, endurance and low-energy switching, ULTRARAM™ could have the potential to be deployed at any point in the memory hierarchy and in any application. Indeed, its speed and, in particular, its high endurance, compared to flash has led to the suggestion that it be used in solid-state drives at the bottom of the memory hierarchy, as a competitor to flash, whilst others have proposed that it could compete with static random-access memory (SRAM) which is situated close to the processor, due to SRAM’s volatility and relatively high cost, *i.e.*, at the top of the memory hierarchy. However, it would be extremely difficult to compete with flash’s main attribute, its low cost, and direct integration of ULTRARAM™ onto a state-of-the-art processor chip is fraught with challenges. Hence, the most logical aspiration is for ULTRARAM™ to compete with (or complement) DRAM, at least for some applications. It is expected to match DRAM in terms of speed, but has the additional advantages of being non-volatile and refresh-free with ultra-low

switching energy. Furthermore, DRAM is implemented as packaged chips, reducing integration issues.

2.1. Space

A key target beachhead market is the space sector, where ULTRARAM™'s non-volatility and energy efficiency are attractive as they deliver robustness against data loss in the absence of power, whether intended or not, and allow for reduced battery or solar panel sizes, saving on launch costs. Another feature of space is that it is very cold, just a few K. On the other hand, in direct sunlight objects can heat up significantly,

as the lack of atmosphere means that there is no convective cooling. The ability to cope with a very wide range of temperatures is thus a key attribute in space. Experiments undertaken during the project indicate that ULTRARAM™ can operate over an extraordinary temperature range. Fig. 5 shows current-voltage (IV) characteristics for the readout channel of an ULTRARAM™ device at cryogenic temperatures. It can be seen that even at the very lowest temperature of 1.28 K the channel remains conductive. This is because ULTRARAM™ does not suffer from carrier freeze-out, the process in which, at low temperatures, semiconductor dopants have insufficient thermal energy to release the electrons (or holes) required for operation. Indeed, quite exceptionally, ULTRARAM™ does not have any (intentional) dopants, as it relies on the physics of band alignment to provide charge carriers, namely the type-III heterojunction band alignment of GaSb and InAs. The conduction band of InAs is below the valence band of GaSb, such that electrons flow from the valence band of GaSb to the conduction band of InAs, even at 0 K. All conventional electronics, including digital electronic components and devices, relies on doping of semiconductor materials, so this property of ULTRARAM™ is unprecedented. Resonant-tunnelling-based program and erase are expected to fully operate at temperatures down to 0 K.

On the other hand, we have also tested several (dry-teched) ULTRARAM™ devices at temperatures up to 100°C, an example of which is shown in Fig. 6. It can be seen that there is no evidence of the decay of the logical states for the

FIG. 5. The readout channel in ULTRARAM™ remains conductive at cryogenic temperatures.

duration of the experiment. Indeed, the data is improved compared to the inset of Fig. 4 in two ways. Firstly, there is no initial decay of the current before reaching a stable value. We attribute this initial decay in the

FIG. 6. Retention of program (write) and erase states at 100°C for an hour.

data of the inset of Fig. 4 to charge traps in the AlSb barriers of the TBRT. At room temperature the traps take an observable time to release the trapped charge into the FG or channel, but 100°C is hot enough that this process is almost instantaneous. This implies that the local potential well associated with these traps is about room temperature (26 meV) in depth. Secondly, it can be seen that the size of the memory window is larger than for the data in the inset of Fig. 4. In fact, at room temperature the memory window for this device was smaller than for the data in the inset of Fig. 4, but, unexpectedly, it increased with increasing temperature. We attributed this temperature-driven improvement to increased thermal occupation of the over-etched channel regions by carriers, reducing the parasitic resistance and thus improving the memory window. This explanation is consistent with the premise that poor 0/1 contrast is a readout issue, *e.g.*, due to leakage currents, and thus further improvements should be possible.

2.2. Datacenters

The long-term aspiration is the use of ULTRARAM™ in high-volume applications, such as datacenters, where it would directly compete with DRAM, offering similar performance in terms of speed and program/erase endurance, but without the need for refresh. Refresh contributes to 20% of DRAM power consumption, and degrades system performance by 30% [Bhati], which also costs energy, such that a reasonable estimate for whole system energy cost of refresh is 30%. According to the International Energy Agency (IEA), datacenter electricity consumption in 2024 was 415 TWh, equivalent to 200 million tonnes of CO₂, using a global average of 481 g of CO₂ per kWh. Moreover, datacenter electricity use is rapidly increasing; the IEA predicts it more than doubling to 945 TWh by 2030 [IEA]. A 30% reduction on this would save 284 TWh or 139 million tonnes of CO₂ per year.

3 Commercialization

In the project proposal the formulation of a roadmap was foreseen to plan future commercialization events after the end of ATTRACT. In reality this was far exceeded, with the incorporation of Quinas Technology Limited, a spinout of Lancaster University, on 18th February 2023, with James Ashforth-Pook, an executive with more than 35 years of experience in the semiconductor industry at the helm as Chief Executive Officer. Since its incorporation Quinas has gone from strength to strength (Fig. 7). A little under six months after Quinas was awarded ‘Most Innovative Startup’ at the Flash Memory Summit in Silicon Valley, the world’s largest memory event. This was rapidly followed by an (Electronics Weekly) Electra Awards Reader’s Choice Award for Research Group of the Year (formally awarded to Lancaster University) in the same year. In 2024, Quinas was the only European Company to win the first round of the IC Taiwan Grand Challenge, and in July of 2025 Quinas became the (joint) first UK company to win a World Intellectual Property Organisation (WIPO) Global Award. The latter award testifies to Quinas’ approach to intellectual property. ULTRARAM™ is currently protected by five granted and eight pending patents in four families, covering US, Europe (UK), Republic of Korea, Japan and China, *i.e.*, most of the world’s leading centers of semiconductor production. Taiwan is not on the list as it is not party to the WIPO Patent Cooperation Treaty, but it is the intention to submit to Taiwan in a separate (parallel) action in future. The UK is not currently a major center for semiconductor chip manufacture. Indeed no memory chips are manufactured in the UK and the UK currently has no stake in the memory market. However, if ULTRARAM™ was to go into production, this would change, as we shall now go on to explain.

FIG. 7. National and international awards. Top to bottom: Flash Memory Summit (2023), Electra Awards (2023), IC Taiwan Grand Challenge (2024) and WIPO Global Awards (2025).

FIG. 8. Unprocessed ULTRARAM™ wafers. The 3" wafer was grown at Lancaster by MBE and the 6" wafer was grown by MOCVD at IQE.

The first stage of the production of any compound semiconductor device or chip is the epitaxial growth of the different semiconductor layers. Multiple layers, even hundreds, can be grown in a single technological process on several wafers in parallel at relatively low-cost, *i.e.*, using equipment with orders of magnitude lower capex than in a chip processing 'fab'. This is very different from Si-based digital electronics, where all the complexity, starting from a bare wafer, is introduced in the fab. ULTRARAM™ chips will require processing in a fab, subsequent to the epitaxial growth, but this will be relatively simple, with many times fewer processing steps, only requiring etching and metal and dielectric deposition. One might therefore expect that the cost per wafer of ULTRARAM™ production could be lower than for Si.³ Prior to ATTRACT, all ULTRARAM™ epitaxy had been undertaken using molecular beam epitaxy (MBE), which is widely considered to primarily be a research technique, on 2" or 3" wafers. During ATTRACT, and funded separately by Innovate UK in a collaborative project with Quinas, Lancaster University and Cardiff University, world-leading semiconductor epitaxy foundry and ATTRACT Phase 1 partner, IQE, developed, for the first time, ULTRARAM™ epitaxy on 6" wafers using metal-organic chemical deposition (MOCVD) (Fig. 8), which is the preferred method for industrial compound semiconductor epitaxy. Quinas and Lancaster will continue to work with IQE to develop the industrial process further, with the goal of establishing the capability of production-quality growth on multiple 8" wafers in parallel. After epitaxial growth wafers will need to be processed to form integrated circuits. While scaling down of devices and scaling up of array sizes is still under development, as described above, we are already in discussions with potential partners who could do this for production prototype development, pre-production and pilot and volume production. As compound semiconductor epitaxy is not currently available on wafers with diameters beyond 8" (200 mm), it is envisaged that this will be in partnership with older, lower-cost ('legacy') fabs with minimum feature sizes (gate stack dimension) of ~100 nm,

³ While the cost per wafer may be lower, in the first instance the feature size (node) will be relatively large so the bit density will be lower, and the cost per bit higher. Cost per wafer will also strongly depend on overall volume, with costs decreasing substantially as volume increases.

thus also reducing the extent to which devices need to be scaled down prior to production. Devices of this size are still expected to have 0/1 switching energies that are many times smaller than DRAM or flash and orders of magnitude lower than emerging memories, and should be more radiation tolerant than smaller devices, which fits with targeting space as a beachhead market.

4 Conclusions

ULTRARAM™ is a novel computer memory technology with a remarkable set of properties. In common with conventional memories, *i.e.*, SRAM, DRAM and flash, it is a charge-based memory. Indeed, it can be considered as a compound (III-V) semiconductor version of flash in which the dielectric between the floating gate and the readout channel is replaced by a triple-barrier resonant-tunnelling (TBRT) structure. This eliminates flash's deficiencies, resulting in a non-volatile memory with intrinsically fast program and erase, high endurance and ultralow switching energy. The ability to allow robustly-stored data to be easily changed is the key technical attribute of so-called 'universal' memory that could be used anywhere in the memory hierarchy and in any application. However, due to the challenge of co-integrating III-V semiconductors with Si and the low-cost per bit of flash, the objective is to compete with or complement DRAM, as a fast, but non-volatile and refresh-free memory. In the project, substantial progress was made in device processing, with the challenging development of a dry-etch process suitable for scaling achieved, and the fabrication of multiple 16-bit arrays. In some cases, the 0/1 contrast was significantly improved compared to the previous wet-etching process, but further work is needed to reduce parasitic resistances and leakage currents and improve yield. Two potential applications were highlighted in the proposal. Space applications was selected as a beachhead market for which ULTRARAM™'s non-volatility and energy efficiency are key. During the project, ULTRARAM™'s unprecedented range of operating temperature, from 1 K to 100°C, was demonstrated, highly advantageous for space applications. In the long-term, the aspiration is use of ULTRARAM™ in datacenters, where its efficiency could reduce CO₂ emissions by up to 140 million tonnes per year. Commercialization activities far exceeded what was foreseen in the proposal, with the incorporation of Lancaster spinout Quinas Technology Limited, and the receipt of multiple international awards, including the startup winner in the ICT category of the WIPO Global Awards (2025). In a separately-funded project, the first steps were taken towards mass manufacture with the development of ULTRARAM™ epitaxy in an industrial process on 6" wafers by world-leading epi-foundry IQE.

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VISIR2

Novel visible-infrared imaging system in two dimensional arrays

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Abstract

The VISIR2 project focused on the industrialization of EYE4NIR's dual-band photodetectors towards the fabrication of a VGA image sensor. This document reports about the development activities, highlighting the technical results obtained during the project and demonstrating the feasibility of the proposed approach. Despite multiple technical issues involving the fabrication of the Ge-on-Si devices together with the CMOS circuitry, a final demonstrator has been obtained, and its performance have been assessed. Finally, we discuss three different technology applications, demonstrating the industrial and commercial potentialities of the proposed sensing and imaging system.

Keywords: ge-on-si; swir; visible; imaging; CMOS

1 Technology Description and Benchmark

The project focuses on the industrialization of EYE4NIR's dual-band detection technology, which is based on a Ge-on-Si pixel architecture with a back-to-back configuration. This innovative design enables selective detection of both visible (VIS) and short-wave infrared (SWIR) light within a single pixel

structure. The industrialization efforts carried out within the VISIR2 framework have been made possible thanks to the advanced fabrication capabilities of the SiGe–BiCMOS pilot line at IHP, alongside the specialized expertise in read-out integrated circuit (ROIC) design provided by IMASENIC. The development process followed a structured, step-wise approach, starting from pixel-level optimization and progressing to the successful integration of a multi-pixel chip with the ROIC, marking a significant milestone towards the commercialization of this dual-band imaging technology. The final goal of manufacturing a full imager with VGA resolution has not been achieved due to difficulties in fabricating the ROIC and the Ge-on-Si photodiodes layer within a single fabrication run.

1.1 Single-pixel devices development

The first phase involved the fabrication of single-pixel devices leveraging standard microelectronic manufacturing processes. IHP developed an epitaxial growth protocol suitable for the realization of Ge-on-Si vertically illuminated detectors [1]. The original pixel structure, initially developed in academic laboratories, was completely re-designed to ensure compatibility with CMOS process constraints. Such single-pixel devices were successfully fabricated, and their electro-optical performance were thoroughly characterized, demonstrating the desired functionality. A scanning electron microscopy (SEM) image of one of the single-pixel devices is shown in figure 1(a). The spectral responsivity shown in figure 1(b) exhibit the expected behavior, showing a clear switch between VIS and SWIR components.

FIG. 1: SEM picture of a single-pixel (a). Spectral responsivity (b)

1.2 Electronic Design

In order to achieve both goals of optimizing the pixel design and building an imager, we adopted the strategy of building a so called parametric test sensor. This is a sensor which looks like a full imager, with the complete readout chain and control blocks, but where, instead of having a focal plane composed of a single pixel type, the pixel arrays is divided into sub-arrays, where each sub-array has a single type of pixel. In this way, it is possible to test several pixel types within a full imager, thus achieving both goals of designing a full imager and optimizing the pixel.

The floorplan of the parametric test sensor we developed is shown in the figure 2.

FIG. 2:Chip floor-plan

1.3 Fabrication of the ROIC and the multi-pixel chip.

After the strategic decision of proceed for a non-monolithic integration, the CMOS-ROIC and the Ge-on-Si photodiodes were fabricated on separate fabrication runs. Specifically, the CMOS lot required 370 process steps and have shown in-spec functionalities after testing. The CMOS-only chips were also used to capture some images in the VIS range to test the ROIC functionality.

Figure 3: Exemplary image captured under visible light on the CMOS-only chip. The different pixel designs are responsible for the different performances of different cells.

The Ge-on-Si photodiodes fabrication run has been performed on a 12 wafers lot, with several splits made for the development of the dual-band photodiodes. Cross sectional images of the Ge-on-Si photodiodes at different stages of the device development are shown in fig 4a and 4b.

FIG. 4: Ge-on-Si photodiodes SEM images taken at different processing steps

1.4 Device integration

A CMOS-ROIC and a Ge-on-Si photodiode chips were then hybrid assembled, by gluing one chip on the other and wire bonding the photodiodes with the readout electronics (see fig. 5a and 5b). Two Printed Circuit Boards have been designed for the test system. The Chip-on-Board to which the assembly is bonded, and the Interface Board that interfaces between the sensor and the PC.

FIG 5: Pictures of the PCB board (a) with the CMOS-ROIC and Ge-on-Si photodiodes assembly on top (b)

We then tested the Ge-on-Si photodiodes response as a function of the integration time, with light on and off, recording a clear signal indicating that the hybrid assembly worked properly (see fig. 6a and 6b). The Ge photodiode unfortunately features rather high dark current levels, which have hindered any attempt to increase the integration time. Further optimization steps will be required after the end of the project to reduce the dark current and to integrate more pixels.

FIG. 6: Bright - Dark signal as a function of the integration time in the VIS (a) and in the SWIR(b)

2 Technology Applications

SWIR imaging technology can be exploited in several different fields of application; in this project, we envisioned different experiments to showcase the potentialities of the devices and technologies developed in VISIR2. More specifically, we identified three different applications that can greatly benefit from SWIR sensing and imaging, namely (1) waste material recognition and management for efficient recycling, (2) early fire detection in both indoor and outdoor conditions, and (3) improved vision for autonomous driving and in-cabin monitoring. Given the fabrication issues we faced and the difficulties in obtaining a complete VGA imager based on the double-diode structure demonstrated in the first phase of the ATTRACT project, we decided to showcase the technology applications either by using single-pixel devices (waste management and fire identification) or by exploiting a commercial SWIR camera. This strategy was pursued with the explicit aim of demonstrating the manifold functionalities of a SWIR sensing and imaging system and the advantages offered by the dual-band sensing of the double-diode devices.

2.1. Technology Applications tested during the ATTRACT Project

2.1.1 *Waste management and plastic recognition*

Efficient waste recycling is pivotal to reduce the ecological impact of human activities. Today, waste classification relies on costly apparatuses that are only available in large-scale waste management plants. Bringing the waste classification closer to the citizens would allow for a more efficient management of the waste cycle, contributing to the general pollution reduction. Several waste materials (i.e., plastics, aluminum, paper) show specific reflectance signatures in the SWIR range, thus allowing for classification based on simple reflectance measurements [2,3]. The classical approach to classification requires the employment of multispectral imaging systems, relying on optical filters or dispersive optics. The spectral tunability of the dual-band Ge-on-Si pixel developed in the VISIR project allows for the qualitative evaluation of the spectral reflectivity of a waste sample without the need for any specific optics, thus enabling facile waste recognition. Fig. 3 shows the measurement set-up we used for this demonstration. A single-pixel, dual-band device was enclosed in a 3D-printed plastic container with a frontal

aperture for illumination. The pixel was pointed towards a black box, containing different samples in the form of pellets (4 different plastics, aluminum from a soda can, glass, and paper). The samples were illuminated by means of a halogen lamp and the reflected radiation was collected by the single pixel. The pixel was biased with a varying voltage in the -0.5 V - -0.25 V range with a 10 mV step, thus switching its sensitivity from the visible to the SWIR range. The photogenerated current was amplified by means of an external trans-impedance amplifier and it was detected by a lock-in amplifier.

FIG. 7: Schematic representation of the measurement set-up

Each one of the tested materials was analyzed for 350 times over different days and without any specific control on the environmental conditions (i.e., ambient illumination, temperature, humidity). The experimental data were divided in a training and a test data-set (80%/20% of the total data) and used to train a standard machine learning algorithm for classification (Support Vector Machine algorithm). A five-fold cross validation was employed to prevent over-fitting. Fig. 4 shows the confusion matrix obtained at the end of the training process, demonstrating an overall classification accuracy of 95%.

True class	AB400L	Aluminium	Glass	PET	PP_Transparent	PP_White	Paper
AB400L	282					4	14
Aluminium		286	1	10	1		2
Glass		3	296	1			
PET		7		272	1	1	19
PP_Transparent					288	11	1
PP_White	2				4	294	
Paper	13			9			278

FIG. 8: Confusion matrix of the training data-set. Final classification accuracy is 95%

Similar accuracies (i.e., 94%) were obtained even when increasing the voltage step of the bias sweep applied to the single pixel device up to 100mV, thus allowing for fast material recognition. Finally, the pre-trained system was employed for the classification of real waste material (e.g., plastic bottles, soda cans, glass bottles) demonstrating an overall accuracy close to 80%. A re-training of the system including data obtained from real waste samples instead of pellets would allow for a further increase in accuracy.

2.1.2 Fire detection system

Early fire detection is pivotal in many different scenarios, ranging from safety in industrial plants to woods monitoring and fire prevention in rural settings [4]. Fire detection is typically achieved with three different approaches [5]. For indoor applications, fire detectors are typically based on small ionization chambers, capable of detecting the very small particles in the smoke. In this case, the fire is not detected directly, but it is the smoke that triggers the alarm. For outdoor applications, where interference from the sun is critical, optical systems are employed. Such systems are composed of multiple detectors (2 to

4) operating in the UV and mid-infrared. The operating wavelengths are selected based on the need to reduce the effect of the interference from sunlight and on the typical light emission of flames. Finally, recent fire detection systems often employ visible cameras and image recognition algorithms to identify flames in complex outdoor settings. All these approaches show some limitations, either in terms of flexibility (smoke detectors can only work indoors), cost (multi-wavelength detectors are expensive and they must be equipped with fragile and costly mid-IR optics), or effectiveness (imaging systems working in the visible wavelength range are effective only when large flames are already visible in the image). The dual-band device developed in the VISIR project is a valid alternative for early fire detection, thanks to its voltage-dependent spectral sensitivity allowing for a qualitative evaluation of the emission spectrum of a light source.

To demonstrate the feasibility of the Ge-on-Si dual-band detector for early fire detection, we used a testing approach similar to the one previously described for waste recognition. In this case, the single pixel device was facing a white screen with a small paraffin candle in front of it. The screen could be illuminated by different interfering light sources, in order to simulate the effect of optical interferences coming from ambient illumination. An LED lamp and a fluorescent lamp were employed to simulate the typical illumination for indoor activities, while a 2800K halogen lamp was employed as an interfering light source with an emission spectrum similar to that of the sun in a typical sunny day and to simulate outdoor operation of the system. The single pixel could be moved closer or further away from the reflective screen in a 16cm – 160cm range, thus changing the total amount of light emitted from the candle reaching the detector. At the same time, the interfering light sources were moved, and their intensity was modulated in order to change the overall signal-to-noise ratio. The SNR was changed between 14.5dB and 7.4dB. These values were chosen according to the standard certification guidelines typically considered for commercial fire detectors (EN54-10 European directive). Experimental data were obtained over 30 days of measurements in order to maximize the capability of the system to operate with changing environmental conditions. Fig. 5 shows the confusion matrix obtained after training the system with 1600 different measurements. Each measurement could be obtained with the candle lit or not and with or without interfering light sources. The final classification accuracy was 99.4%, thus demonstrating the capability

of the system to effectively recognize a small flame even when strong interferences were present.

FIG. 9: Confusion matrix of the training data-set. Final classification accuracy is 99.4%

In order to estimate the capability of the system to generalize when exposed to illumination conditions not included in the training data set, we tested the pre-trained system over a wide SNR range, obtaining a 70% accuracy for flame identification down to a 0dB SNR.

2.1.3 Autonomous driving and in-cabin monitoring

Compared to conventional RGB imaging, SWIR technology provides advantages in environments with degraded visibility. First, SWIR wavelengths are less affected by scattering phenomena than visible light. In conditions such as smoke or fog, where fine particles scatter shorter wavelengths more

effectively, SWIR light maintains a more direct propagation path, enabling clearer imaging through such obscurants. Second, certain atmospheric absorption windows exist within the SWIR spectrum, wavelength bands where solar radiation is significantly attenuated due to absorption by water vapor and other atmospheric gases. These low-radiance bands reduce the background solar illumination, effectively enhancing image contrast and helping to avoid saturation, especially in outdoor daylight conditions. Lastly, SWIR has the ability to reveal chemical and material differences due to the distinct spectral signatures of various substances in this range.

This research line was chosen because it enables the integration of two critical sensing capabilities into a single camera system: anti-fog vision support and early detection of flammable substances. This dual functionality is particularly relevant in light of upcoming automotive safety regulations, which are expected to place greater emphasis on vehicle behavior immediately after an accident.

The first setup, the one simulating the smoky conditions, consists of Alvium 1800 U-130 VSWIR camera, the Edmund VIS-SWIR Fixed Focal Length Lense of 12mm, bandpass filters in the SWIR band (a. 1100-2300nm, b. 1290-1310nm, c. 1440-1460nm, d. 1540-1560nm), a smoker and a transparent chamber. The Alvium 1800 U-130 VSWIR includes the Sony IMX990 sensor, and in InGaAs sensor type with a $5\mu\text{m}$ pitch, a resolution of 1296 (H) x 1032 (V). The images obtained with the SWIR camera, equipped with the 1100-2300nm filter, were compared to a standard RGB camera to assess the advantages of SWIR vision in low-visibility conditions. Fig. 6 shows the images obtained with the two cameras when the transparent chamber was filled with different amounts of smoke. From a straightforward comparison between the different images, it is clear how the SWIR camera allows for better identification of the object inside the glass box, even in very low visibility

conditions. Moreover, the SWIR camera can clearly identify the hot burning chamber of the smoker, thus allowing for a facile identification of hot bodies.

FIG 10: Low-visibility images obtained with a RGB camera (left) and a SWIR camera (right)

The second test was conducted to evaluate the capability of a SWIR camera to identify flammable substances inside the vehicle for in-cabin monitoring applications. This test involves permeating a standard car floor mat with two different liquids, engine oil and water, in order to evaluate the SWIR camera's capability to differentiate between them. The liquids were applied separately in controlled amounts. The goal was to determine which wavelength ranges offered the highest contrast between the materials, based on their differing absorption and reflectance behaviors.

Fig. 7 showcase the same scene captured with the SWIR camera using a selection of optical bandpass filters and with an RGB camera. For each filter tested, two images are presented side by side: one taken with a shorter exposure time (displayed on the left), and another with a longer exposure time (on the right). This dual-exposure approach was employed to explore how variations in exposure impact the contrast and visibility of the liquid stains. High-exposure images often reveal greater contrast between the liquids and the mat surface, which may enhance the ability to differentiate them depending on the image analysis or classification method employed.

FIG. 11: Car mat impregnated with engine oil (left stain) and water (right stain). Images are obtained in the visible (a), and in the SWIR with different filters: (b,c) 1100-2300nm, (d,e) 1290-1310nm, (f,g) 1540-1560nm. Images in the left column are obtained with a shorter exposure time.

It is important to note that while the optimal exposure setting may vary depending on the specific algorithm or detection system used, this test clearly demonstrates a key advantage of SWIR imaging: the ability to reveal the presence and distribution of impregnated liquids that are virtually invisible in

the visible spectrum. Regardless of the filter or exposure used, the SWIR system consistently provides discernible contrast between the oil and water stains, underscoring its potential utility for in-vehicle hazard detection and material classification applications.

Finally, we evaluated the effectiveness of SWIR imaging in monitoring the eye region, even when the subject is wearing sunglasses, a scenario highly relevant for in-cabin driver monitoring systems, particularly under varying lighting conditions.

To achieve this, we created a broad and varied dataset comprising multiple individuals wearing a range of sunglasses with different lens materials, coatings, and levels of opacity. Several bandpass filters within the SWIR spectrum were used in the experiments to identify which spectral regions offered the best performance in penetrating sunglass lenses while preserving the visibility of eye features. This extensive database allowed for a robust comparative evaluation across diverse real-world conditions.

The SWIR system consistently demonstrated strong performance, successfully revealing eye details through many types of sunglasses, results that are often unattainable with standard RGB cameras.

Fig. 8 presents one representative example from this dataset. While only two images, it serves to illustrate the system's potential in handling this specific use case.

FIG. 12: Man wearing sunglasses observed with the SWIR camera equipped with the 1540-1560nm filter

2.2. Technology Applications envisioned after the ATTRACT Project

After ATTRACT, EYE4NIR will continue to pursue technological applications in the domains of industrial automation, automotive and possibly consumer electronics.

3 Commercialization

Thanks to the work we've carried out over the past months, we have successfully built a strong network of partnerships and industrial relationships that are now opening up important strategic opportunities. Our commitment to developing advanced sensor technologies has enabled us to engage directly with companies and consortia operating in high-potential application areas from smart textiles to agriculture, logistics, and advanced manufacturing. and other sectors where our solution can deliver clear value. These engagements go beyond exploratory conversations. We are already working with potential industrial clients on proof-of-concept (PoC) projects and field testing, applying our sensor technology directly in real-world production environments. This approach not only allows us to validate and optimize our technology in relevant contexts, but also helps tailor our solutions to meet real industry needs, accelerating adoption and impact.

A key milestone toward commercialization is the tape-out of our chip at a commercial, large-volumes, foundry. This step represents the transition from research and development to industrial production and confirms that our technology is mature and ready to scale. With this tape-out we should overcome the limitations encountered within VISIR2 demonstrating our ability to deliver tangible, manufacturable solutions. In parallel, we are actively pursuing two patent applications that cover important innovations in how our sensor technology is applied. These filings aim to protect the uniqueness of our approach and strengthen our competitive edge in the market. Intellectual property plays a strategic role in our roadmap, not only to safeguard our developments but also to create valuable assets for future growth and potential partnerships. On the business development front, we are currently preparing for a Series A funding round. This round will support us in scaling our activities, including team expansion, production ramp-up, and further market deployment. We are seeking to bring on board strategic and financial investors who share our vision and who can actively support our growth at this pivotal stage. The focus of this round is not just scaling manufacturing but also accelerating market access and expanding internationally, particularly in sectors where we've already validated interest.

Importantly, we are proud to share that we have EYE4NIR has been selected for funding from the EIC Accelerator. This prestigious European funding program for high-impact deep tech startups has not only provided us with non-dilutive financial support, but also validated our business case at the highest level. Being selected by the EIC Accelerator has given us access to a strong network of experts, coaches, and potential partners, reinforcing our positioning as a high-potential European deep tech company. The EIC support has also helped us strengthen our strategy, sharpen our commercialization roadmap, and prepare for international market entry. With both grant and equity components, this funding gives us the flexibility to execute our vision while maintaining a solid financial foundation.

4 Conclusions

In conclusion, within the VISIR2 project, the consortium has taken significant steps toward the industrialization of the technology. Despite some technological challenges that have hindered the fabrication of a complete imager, several important use cases have been successfully demonstrated, particularly in plastic sorting, flame detection, and automotive applications. The results achieved during the project have enabled EYE4NIR to make key advances toward commercialization, including its selection by the EIC Accelerator programme.

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MEGAMORPH

Market-Entry of Graphene-based large-Area MOdulators with a Radical Production of Holographic displays

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Abstract

The MEGAMORPH project introduced GMOD[®] technology, an energy-efficient, reflective/holographic pixel platform using 16 µm graphene micro-membranes over 500 nm cavities. A 1000×1000-pixel prototype was demonstrated using CVD graphene, nanoimprint lithography and custom backplane electronics. This article presents a complete electro-mechanical, optical and dynamic model of the system, showing >60% reflectivity contrast at ~30 V per pixel and MHz-speed potential. Seven patents were filed and Dragon Elements SLU was launched for commercialization. These results

underpin GMOD[®]'s future application in AR/VR, automotive HUDs and sustainable displays developed within ATTRACT Phase 2.

Keywords: GMOD[®]; reflective display; microdisplay; CVD graphene; MEMS; MOEMS; electrostatic actuation; nanoimprint lithography; holography; commercialization.

1 Technology description and benchmark

Graphene, a monolayer of sp²-carbon atoms, combines exceptional mechanical strength, optical transparency and electrical conductivity, making it ideal for microscale devices. In GMOD[®], graphene membranes act as micro-opto-electro-mechanical system (MOEMS) pixels, suspended over a spacer, forming a Fabry-Perot cavity with an electrode at its bottom (Cartamil-Bueno et al., 2016) (Cartamil-Bueno et al., 2017). Applying voltage deflects the membrane, tuning the interference boundary condition and modulating the pixel reflectance in a continuous spectrum of wavelengths, that is, the pixel functions as a tunable color filter (Cartamil-Bueno et al., 2018). This concept echoes the interferometric modulation of Qualcomm's Mirasol[®] (IMOD) displays (Wikipedia, 2024) but crucially uses chemically-vapor-deposited (CVD) graphene instead of silicon. Graphene allows ultra-thin, compliant membranes for low-voltage operation, higher pixel densities and better contrast, making GMOD[®] a disruptive technology in the IMOD category.

TABLE 1: Pixel and material parameters.

Parameter	Symbol	Value	Source
Pixel side length	L	16 μm	This work
Cavity gap	g_0	500 nm	This work
Graphene thickness	t	0.335 nm	(Lee et al., 2008)
Young's modulus	E	~ 1 TPa	(López-Polín et al., 2015)
Poisson's ratio	ν	0.16-0.22	(López-Polín et al., 2015)
2D elastic modulus	E_2D	~ 340 N/m	(Lee et al., 2008)
Areal mass density	ρ_2D	0.77 mg/m ²	(Graphenea, n.d.)
Pre-tension	T_0	0.2 N/m	Fabrication parameter
Vacuum permittivity	ϵ_0	8.85×10^{-12} F/m	Physical constant

1.1 Electro-mechanical model

The mechanical response of the GMOD[®] pixel is governed by the equilibrium between the downward restoring pressure p_m of the suspended graphene membrane and the upward electrostatic pressure p_e . These two pressures are modeled as follows (Lee et al., 2008) (López-Polín et al., 2015):

$$p_m(z) = k_3 z^3 + k_1 z \quad (1)$$

$$p_e(V, z) = \frac{\epsilon_0}{2} \left(\frac{V}{g_0 - z} \right)^2 \quad (2)$$

where $k_1 = \frac{c_2 T_0}{L^2}$ is the linear stiffness from the intrinsic bending of the membrane, $k_3 = \frac{c_1 E t}{1-\nu^2} \frac{1}{L^3}$ is the cubic stiffness (dominant at large deflections), T_0 is the linear tension from pre-stress in the graphene; $c_1 = 3.393$, $c_2 = 0.8 + 0.062\nu$ are constants for square geometries of the pixels; V is the applied bias voltage; and z is the vertical deflection of the graphene at the center of the pixel.

Solving the nonlinear equilibrium condition $p_e(V, z) = p_m(z)$ by numerical modeling yields a monotonic increase of deflection with voltage. In the small deflection regime, the deflection approximately follows: $z \propto V^{2/3}$. This scaling is consistent with known behavior for electrostatically actuated membranes in the pre-pull-in regime.

For the GMOD[®] pixel geometry (16 μm side, 500 nm gap, ~ 0.2 N/m pre-tension), the maximum central deflection at 30 V is approximately 120 nm, or 24% of the cavity gap. This deflection remains below the typical pull-in threshold ($\sim 1/3$ of the gap), supporting stable and reversible operation.

FIG. 1. Modeled deflection vs voltage.

1.2 Optical interference model

The reflectivity of each GMOD[®] pixel arises from interferometric modulation between the suspended graphene membrane and the underlying reflective electrode. As the membrane deflects electrostatically, it alters the cavity depth, producing a wavelength-dependent phase shift that affects the constructive or destructive interference of reflected light (Nair et al., 2008). This behavior is modeled as:

$$R(z) = R_0 + \Delta R \cos\left(\frac{4\pi n(g_0 - z)}{\lambda}\right) \quad (3)$$

where λ is the wavelength of the incident light. Using this corrected formulation, the phase shift at 550 nm for a deflection z of 120 nm is $\varphi = 4\pi/\lambda (g_0 - z) \approx 8.68$ rad.

Such a phase shift allows the membrane to modulate light intensity significantly, enabling high optical contrast. Maximum contrast occurs when $g_0 - z \approx \lambda/4n$. For green light (550 nm), the ideal cavity depth for peak constructive interference is ~ 138 nm. The 120 nm deflection thus brings the device close to this optimal point, delivering $>60\%$ reflectivity contrast in the prototype, as confirmed by simulation and measurement.

FIG. 2. Modeled reflectivity vs deflection at RGB wavelengths (450, 550 and 650 nm).

1.3 Dynamic response

The mechanical resonance frequency of the suspended graphene membrane determines the speed and refresh potential of GMOD® pixels (Cartamil-Bueno et al., 2018). The fundamental resonance is approximated by:

$$f_0 \approx \frac{1}{2L} \sqrt{\frac{T_0}{\rho_{2D}}}$$

(4)

For a 16 μm pixel with a pre-tension of 0.2 N/m and areal mass density of 0.77 mg/m², the resonance frequency is approximately 1.1 MHz. Such high resonance supports low-latency pixel modulation and video-capable refresh rates, while also enabling future integration into dynamic holographic applications where high-frequency actuation is required.

1.4 Fabrication and integration

The GMOD[®] display was fabricated using a multi-step process combining large-area material deposition, nanoimprint lithography (NIL), and thin-film transistor (TFT) integration. The key steps include:

- CVD graphene: supplied by Graphenea, delivered large-area monolayers with 97% transparency and sheet resistance $\sim 125 \Omega/\text{sq}$.
- NIL: Morphotonics used roll-to-plate NIL to pattern micro-cavities and spacers across glass substrates.
- Assembly: suspended graphene membranes were transferred to pre-patterned substrates and electrically connected to TFT backplanes designed by SCALE Nanotech.

The integration flow was optimized to maintain membrane cleanliness, achieve uniform pixel gap formation and ensure compatibility with flexible printed circuits and driver electronics.

Post-assembly, the arrays were encapsulated for stability and mounted into functional evaluation kits used in performance demonstrations.

1.5 Benchmarking

GMOD[®] displays were benchmarked against existing reflective and emissive display technologies in terms of static power consumption, contrast, daylight visibility and scalability. The comparative analysis highlights GMOD[®]'s distinctive advantages in ambient-light operation and energy efficiency.

TABLE 2: Comparison between GMOD[®] and other technologies.

Feature	LCD/OLED	LCoS/DLP	GMOD [®]
Power (static)	High	Medium	$<10 \mu\text{W}/\text{pixel}$
Contrast (visible)	High	High	$\sim 60\text{--}70\%$
Outdoor visibility	Poor	Limited	Excellent
Scalability	Established	Moderate	High potential

Compared to LCD and OLED, GMOD[®] avoids the need for backlighting or active emission, enabling power usage orders of magnitude lower during static image display. In contrast to LCoS and DLP, GMOD[®] offers a thinner form factor, better sunlight readability and greater mechanical resilience due to the flexibility of graphene membranes.

The fabrication approach based on NIL and CVD graphene supports roll-to-plate production, enabling large-area deployment with lower equipment costs and fewer thermal constraints than traditional MEMS display technologies.

1.6 System performance

The final GMOD[®] demonstrator achieved a resolution of 1000×1000 pixels, stable operation below 60 V, and contrast >60% at 30 V. Key performance parameters measured in the prototypes include:

- Operating voltage: ≤60 V
- Central deflection: ~120 nm at 30 V
- Static power consumption: <10 μW/pixel
- Mechanical resonance: ~1 MHz
- Refresh capability: kHz range (currently limited by driver electronics)

Collectively, these figures confirm that GMOD[®] pixels meet the mechanical, electrical and optical benchmarks required for integration into modern reflective microdisplay platforms. Target applications include near-eye AR/VR modules, automotive head-up displays (HUDs) and reconfigurable low-power signage in outdoor environments.

2 Technology Applications

GMOD[®] technology developed under the MEGAMORPH project opens new possibilities for energy-efficient, sunlight-readable and scalable displays. Its ability to modulate light through graphene membranes, with minimal power and high mechanical reliability, creates advantages for several industry sectors seeking improvements over OLED, MicroLED and LCoS technologies. This section outlines both the applications tested during the ATTRACT Phase 2 project and those envisioned for commercialization and future development.

2.1. Technology Applications tested during the ATTRACT Project

During the ATTRACT Phase 2 project, the consortium produced and tested GMOD[®] evaluation kits comprising 1000×1000-pixel arrays integrated with CVD graphene, nanoimprint lithography-patterned cavities and custom driving electronics. These kits were evaluated internally and shown to several potential industrial users and stakeholders in demonstration events. The systems successfully displayed gray-scale pixels under ambient lighting, with measured reflectivity contrast exceeding 60% at 30 V and stable mechanical behavior up to 60 V. The evaluation kits demonstrated core performance attributes including good visibility in direct sunlight, robust response to electrical actuation, and pixel-to-pixel uniformity across large display areas.

The demonstrations raised interest of representatives of the AR/VR hardware integrators and defense sector. These discussions confirmed a clear demand for low-power, high-contrast microdisplay technologies that do not rely on emissive light generation or backlighting. Participants identified the potential of GMOD[®] to outperform emissive solutions in outdoor settings, particularly for head-mounted displays and integrated dashboard HUDs. Feedback also highlighted technical challenges that remain, particularly in driving larger arrays at video frame rates and integrating the membrane-based display stack with standard backplane electronics.

Importantly, the evaluations revealed a strong fit between GMOD[®] and the growing demand for ultra-low power, context-specific visualization. In scenarios requiring intermittent updates, such as drone-mounted tactical readouts or passive alert displays, GMOD[®] offers exceptionally low power consumption due to its capacitive actuation and absence of continuous current draw. Although the membrane does not exhibit true bistability like E-Ink, static images can be maintained with minimal holding power or periodic refresh, making it highly suitable for power-constrained applications. Furthermore, the technology operates reliably across the temperature ranges typical for automotive and wearable environments.

2.2. Technology Applications envisioned after the ATTRACT Project

Looking beyond the ATTRACT demonstration phase, GMOD[®] and LATIDO[®] technologies are being developed for use in commercial products in multiple

sectors. These are positioned for adoption across a range of high-growth display segments (Market Research Future, 2023) (Statista, 2023) (IDTechEx, 2023) (Grand View Research, 2023) (Yole Développement, 2023) (Research and Markets, 2023):

- AR/VR microdisplays: forecasted to grow from USD 1.8 billion in 2023 to USD 8.2 billion by 2028 (35.6% CAGR). GMOD[®]'s sunlight readability, low power draw and compact footprint make it ideal for AR glasses and compact headsets.
- Automotive HUDs: projected to reach USD 12.8 billion by 2032 (CAGR ~15.7%). GMOD[®] can enable durable, high-contrast HUDs operable in full daylight and resistant to heat buildup.
- Smart wearables and LATIDO[®] capsules: the market for near-eye wearable displays is estimated to grow to USD 10.4 billion by 2033. GMOD[®] paired with LATIDO[®] offers a unique integration of acoustic and optical modulation, enabling dual-functionality in helmet visors and tactical eyewear.
- Reflective outdoor signage: reflective digital displays are expected to rise from USD 2.1 billion to 3.5 billion by 2032. GMOD[®] enables energy-efficient signage readable under sunlight without backlighting.
- Defense and aerospace: ruggedized GMOD[®] displays are suited for UAV command interfaces, soldier-mounted AR systems and multispectral instrumentation requiring radiation tolerance and minimal power consumption.

In AR/VR systems, GMOD[®] is highly suited to compact microdisplays that must be bright, energy-efficient and readable across lighting conditions. Current OLED and MicroLED technologies suffer from poor outdoor visibility and relatively high-power consumption, especially when brightness is increased. GMOD[®] pixels do not emit light, but instead reflect and modulate ambient light, enabling strong performance in outdoor scenarios such as industrial augmented reality, sports coaching glasses or defense helmet systems. In wearable devices powered by small batteries, even a 30-50% reduction in display power draw can translate to significant improvements in device runtime.

In the automotive sector, head-up displays are expected to become standard in many mid- and high-tier vehicles within the next decade. Current HUD technologies are mostly based on LCoS and DLP projection systems, which require complex optics and struggle with thermal dissipation under dashboard exposure. GMOD[®] pixels can be placed into transparent substrates and provide direct reflective projection without requiring heat-producing light sources. In HUDs, high-contrast readability in sunlight is critical for safety. GMOD[®] can provide this natively through optical interference without increasing energy use. In addition, the thinness and light weight of the membranes support integration into curved windshields or helmet visors.

In signage and electronic paper displays, GMOD[®] offers a route toward ultra-low power digital signs that function without backlight, ideal for daylight or solar-exposed environments. Reflective signage is currently used in traffic systems, public transit and outdoor advertising. By switching from printed or passive materials to GMOD[®] pixels, dynamic content could be presented with negligible power draw, yet remain visible in full sun. In urban infrastructure, this could support real-time reconfigurable signage with solar operation and minimal maintenance.

A unique extension of the core display platform is the LATIDO[®] pixel, developed to integrate both optical and acoustic modulation in the same membrane. This enables new applications in wearable devices and immersive interfaces. For example, a firefighter helmet visor equipped with LATIDO[®] pixels could simultaneously display critical icons and emit localized audio alerts through the same membrane structure. This integration reduces component count, simplifies design and improves robustness in field conditions.

In defense and aerospace, GMOD[®] could support rugged and radiation-tolerant displays for head-mounted targeting systems, unmanned aerial vehicle controls and field-deployable sensor interfaces. The reflective nature of the display minimizes thermal signature and power consumption, two major requirements in operational environments. Because the display consumes little power, it is well suited to scenarios involving monitoring and alert-based visualization.

The range of these envisioned applications reflects both the modularity and the versatility of the GMOD[®] platform. From passive static displays to dynamic

audiovisual systems, its core physical principle (graphene membrane modulation) remains unchanged, providing a consistent technology base that can be adapted for very different product needs.

3 Commercialization

As the MEGAMORPH project advanced GMOD[®] technology from TRL 3 to TRL 7-8, commercialization activities were embedded from the beginning. Unlike many early-stage deep tech projects, the MEGAMORPH consortium not only focused on demonstrating technical feasibility but also initiated concrete steps to bring the technology closer to market. This included securing intellectual property rights, developing early-stage product concepts and launching a dedicated spin-off company, Dragon Elements SLU. The following sections describe the commercialization milestones achieved during the ATTRACT Phase 2 project and the roadmap for scaling beyond the project's duration.

3.1 Commercialization during the ATTRACT Project

During the course of the ATTRACT Phase 2 project, the consortium developed a GMOD[®] evaluation kit to demonstrate the capabilities of the technology in a real-world context. This kit contained 1000×1000-pixel arrays mounted on glass substrate, patterned using nanoimprint lithography and covered with suspended CVD graphene membranes. The backplane and control electronics were designed to allow actuation of pixel blocks, enabling gray-scale pixel rendering. This kit was shown in private demonstrations to stakeholders in AR/VR, defense and materials industries. The demonstrations generated interest in both the underlying electro-optic performance and the long-term potential of the platform as a scalable low-power reflective display.

Feedback collected from these sessions helped refine the integration and manufacturing roadmap. Stakeholders emphasized the importance of video-rate refresh, improved pixel addressability and compatibility with existing TFT backplane standards. Based on this input, the consortium identified the need for higher-speed drive electronics and better pixel multiplexing. These learnings will be integrated into the design of the next-generation evaluation kits.

A critical commercialization step during the project was the development of a robust intellectual property (IP) strategy. Seven patent families were filed covering the membrane architecture, display actuation method, integration with backplanes and the LATIDO[®] audiovisual pixel concept. The patents are structured to protect the platform at the component, system, and manufacturing levels, offering a solid foundation for future licensing and investment activities.

To bridge the transition from R&D to market engagement, SCALE Nanotech established a new spin-off company: Dragon Elements SLU. Incorporated during the final stages of the MEGAMORPH project, Dragon Elements is the dedicated vehicle to commercialize GMOD[®]-based products. It was founded with the purpose of leveraging part of the results developed during MEGAMORPH while offering a clean IP structure and entrepreneurial governance suited for industrial scale-up and private funding. The company was initially staffed by a core team from SCALE Nanotech, with operational independence and a roadmap aligned with both scientific and commercial goals.

3.2 Commercialization strategy after ATTRACT

Following the completion of the ATTRACT Phase 2 project, Dragon Elements SLU will focus on refining the technology into market-ready products. The first phase involves updating the GMOD[®] evaluation kits with video-capable drivers and smaller pixel pitches, to improve resolution and refresh rate. These kits are intended for delivery to early-access partners in the AR/VR and automotive sectors, enabling them to test integration with optics and driver electronics.

In parallel, the company will scale NIL manufacturing to improve uniformity, yield and throughput. Pilot production is planned to be based on roll-to-plate NIL using the expertise and tooling developed by Morphotonics. The roadmap includes development of flexible or curved substrates, supporting integration into automotive windshields or visor systems.

Commercial engagement will follow a dual path: (1) evaluation kit sales to OEMs and R&D groups; and (2) licensing discussions with display integrators interested in using GMOD[®] as a reflective module within broader systems. Dragon Elements also plans to explore LATIDO[®] as a dual audiovisual module

in defense and wearable applications, where minimizing component count and increasing ruggedness are valued.

To support this plan, Dragon Elements is seeking €3-5 million in seed and early-stage investment. This funding will be used to build product teams, develop pilot lines, complete industrial certifications and secure initial customer deals. The team has submitted applications for EIC Accelerator support and the company is engaging with private venture capital groups focused on sustainable electronics and photonics.

The commercial roadmap includes product refinement (12–24 months), holographic enhancement of GMOD[®] pixels and eventual volume production of custom and modular reflective panels. Market sectors targeted include the AR/VR microdisplay segment (USD 1.8 billion → 8.2 billion by 2028), automotive HUDs (USD 12.8 billion by 2032), and wearable near-eye displays (USD 10.4 billion by 2033).

GMOD[®] is positioned to compete not by replicating OLED or MicroLED capabilities, but by addressing market gaps those technologies leave unfilled, namely in outdoor readability, power efficiency and long-term stability. In AR/VR, GMOD[®] can complement emissive pixels with reflective layers for hybrid visibility. In automotive, it eliminates the thermal and optical inefficiencies of LCoS and DLP HUDs. In signage, it provides a programmable, low-maintenance alternative to backlit LCDs in environments where power or visibility is constrained.

The primary competitive risk comes from continued miniaturization of emissive displays, particularly MicroLEDs. However, their cost, environmental impact and power consumption continue to present challenges that GMOD[®] is well-positioned to overcome. Material supply chain risk, particularly for large-area graphene, is being mitigated through a strong partnership with Graphenea and other suppliers. The modularity of GMOD[®]'s membrane system also allows for future upgrades and new materials as they become available.

From a regulatory and manufacturing standpoint, GMOD[®] avoids some of the hazardous processing steps and rare-earth material dependencies common in emissive display fabrication. Its compatibility with CMOS backplanes and

roll-to-plate manufacturing methods supports scalability and cost competitiveness.

With IP protection in place, a spin-off structured for growth and interest from multiple sectors, GMOD[®] is well positioned to enter early markets within the next 12–24 months

4 Conclusions

GMOD[®] has achieved TRL 7-8 with a fully characterized, programmable and scalable graphene display. MEGAMORPH project has established a solid scientific and technological foundation for GMOD[®], confirming its viability through modeling, fabrication, performance validation and early-stage market outreach. The technology delivers low-power, high-contrast, sunlight-readable displays suited for microdisplay, HUD and signage applications.

Commercialization efforts led to a spin-off company, seven patent filings and pilot customer engagement, laying the groundwork for near-term industrial deployment. GMOD[®] represents a sustainable evolution of IMOD concepts with relevance across multiple strategic markets.

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h-cube

Micromechanical Bolometers arrays for Terahertz hyperspectral imaging

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Abstract

Here we report on the main results we achieved in the h-cube project, a R&D&I project within ATTRACT phase II initiative. Leveraging the potential of thermomechanical bolometers as uncooled THz detectors, we built a commercial system composed of 256 pixels with all-electrical and maximally multiplexed frequency read-out. Validating the technology with different applications in the fields of THz imaging of dry food and hidden art canvas, we further report on advanced capabilities such as performance enhancement by inclusion of nano-carbon and exploitation of mechanical nonlinearities and passive black-body detection in feedback-based readout configurations. We finally verified the potential of the sensor for obtaining hyperspectral information in a compact chip that is producing false-color imaging in the THz range.

Keywords: THz imaging; thermomechanical bolometers; food quality inspection; hyperspectral camera

1 Technology Description and Benchmark

The basic concept behind the core of our technology, the thermomechanical bolometer (TMB) is sketched in Fig. 1. We started with a trampoline resonator consisting of a wide central plate sustained by four tethers directly anchored to the substrate(1). In its fundamental vibration mode the tethers are extended while the plate translates perpendicularly to its plane (see green arrow). When illuminated, if radiation is absorbed it can induce a temperature gradient along the tethers, which causes a frequency shift due to the thermal expansion/relaxation processes, see the colormap in Fig. 1. Finally, an increase in temperature decreases the mechanical frequencies and enables detection.

FIG. 1 Concept of thermomechanical detection

Our resonators were made of silicon nitride, a material well known for its mechanical quality, due to an intrinsic tensile stress which can be tuned when deposited on silicon substrates(2); suspended Si_3N_4 devices are perfectly flat and can be fabricated with extreme aspect ratio, even surpassing what can be done with standard 2D materials(3).

Device fabrication followed standard CMOS procedures and started with a 250 μm Si wafer sandwiched between two 300 nm thick stoichiometric Si_3N_4 device layers. We deposited a metallic layer, via lithography and lift-off, to define an absorber in the membrane center, contacts running through the tethers, bonding pads, and alignment markers. A second aligned lithography was used to define the membrane shape which was then transferred to the Si_3N_4 layer via fluorine-based reactive ion etching. A final wet etch in TMAH or KOH solution releases the trampoline by removing the silicon underneath, more details can be found in ref. (4). A typical fabricated device is shown in the Scanning Electron Microscope (SEM) image in Fig. 2 (a).

In a preliminary work precedent to h-cube we detected the motion of the membrane (driven by a piezoceramic actuator on which the chip was mounted) by shining a near-infrared, weak laser probe on the partially reflecting central pad and setting it up as an external mirror of an interferometer in self-mixing configuration(5).

FIG. 2 (a): SEM of a typical thermomechanical bolometer. Fundamental mode resonance of a device with 1 mm frame measured with optical interferometry (b) and magnetomotive voltage (c).

Using the interferometric read-out for low actuation voltages returns spectra similar to the one shown in Fig. 2 (b). Adding metallic contacts on top of the tethers enabled an all-electrical control of the trampoline vibrations; including a static and planar magnetic field with permanent neodymium magnets we can force oscillations by leveraging the Lorentz force originated by an AC current flowing through the contacts. Conversely, when the metallic contact moved in a static magnetic field, an electromotive voltage was generated whose amplitude was directly proportional to the modification of the concatenated magnetic flux, which in our case depended on the vertical membrane velocity, as very well known in MEMS applications(6). The complementary electrical read-out of the membrane of Fig. 2 is reported in panel (c), under the same driving condition of panel (a). Interestingly, the peak frequency of the mechanical resonance was correctly evaluated, but the overall shape was changed, essentially due to a broad coupling term which gives rise to a Fano lineshape(7). The Fano effect is a further feature of the electrical read-out which will be exploited to further improve the detector sensitivity.

After running some optimization studies(8), we standardized the trampoline geometry which comprised a $300 \times 300 \mu\text{m}$ frame, a central $100 \times 100 \mu\text{m}$ pad and tethers of varying width in a range from 13 to $45 \mu\text{m}$.

A critical parameter of the TMB performance is the absorption layer since it controls the electromagnetic range of operation of the device. In fact, silicon nitride is practically transparent in the whole infrared range, with the exception of a strong absorption peak at about 25 THz due to the Si-N bond stretching mode(9), see Fig. 3 (a). While a broad and strong absorber is desirable, it is important that it does not degrade the resonator mechanical quality: to this end, we considered only ultrathin absorption layers to be embedded within our TMB. In our configuration, the maximum absorption is given by 50 %, as can be expected by simple impedance matching constraints for a single, isolated layer(10); in particular, this condition is fulfilled by a 2D conductor with a sheet resistance of 188 Ω .

FIG. 3 (a): Experimental (markers) and simulated (lines) transmission and reflection spectra of a 300 nm Si₃N₄ membrane. (b): Experimental (markers) and simulated (lines) transmission and reflection spectra of a 300 nm Si₃N₄ membrane covered by a 20 nm thick PyC layer. (c): Comparison of the extracted absorption in the two samples.

We decided to employ carbon-based ultrathin materials, due to their broad absorption band, ease of deposition, compatibility with the process and possibility to control their thickness (and therefore their conductivity) with great precision(11). Our final choice fell into Pyrolytic Carbon (PyC). Pyrolytic carbon thin films present a highly versatile platform for THz photonic

applications due to their ability to be deposited on a wide range of dielectric substrates, including those with complex geometries. This flexibility enables integration into diverse device architectures. One of the key advantages of PyC films is the tunability of their DC and THz-range conductivity, which allows for tailoring their electromagnetic response. Specifically, by optimizing the conductivity relative to the vacuum impedance ($\sim 377 \Omega$), PyC films can achieve strong THz absorption, up to 50%, at targeted frequencies(12).

FIG. 4 (a): multiplexing concept: each membrane is designed to oscillate at different frequencies in such a way to multiplex/demultiplex them using a single electrical contact. (b): microscope image of the final sensor, composed of 16x16 individual pixels. (c): preliminary characterization shows that different resonators in different rows have matching frequencies, enabling time-multiplexing. (d): evolution of final prototypes.

Preliminary characterization has been done by depositing 20 nm of PyC on a silicon nitride square membrane and measuring reflection/transmission in a broad spectral range, employing commercial FTIR and TDS systems. Main

results are shown in Fig. 3, where we see transmission and reflection spectra of a bare Si₃N₄ membrane (panel a), of a PyC-covered Si₃N₄ membrane (panel b) and a comparison of the extracted absorptions (panel c). The presence of the ultrathin PyC layer enhanced the absorption in the whole spectral range, obtaining a strong ~43 % absorption from 0.5 THz to almost 20 THz(13). Another possibility made use of an ultrathin layer of Au as TMB absorber. Even if the theoretical thickness to achieve the sheet resistance value leading to 50% absorption would require a sub-nm film, grain-induced discontinuities strongly suppressed conductance for film thicknesses ranging around 1 - 10 nm, improving the film absorption with respect to what expected from a homogeneous layer.

Optimizing design and fabrication we obtained a best responsivity at 0.14 THz of ~497 kHz/mW and ~73 kHz/mW for the PyC and ultra-thin gold device respectively(14). This suggests an absorption of the ultrathin gold of ~12 %, which, as expected, was strongly enhanced with respect to the 2-3% absorption in a ~35 nanometers thick Cr/Au layer in the previous device generation(5). The best noise-equivalent power (NEP) we obtained was of 30 pW/√Hz for the PyC device with an operating speed exceeding 20 Hz. This very well compares with commercial camera devices which show optimal performances in the mid-infrared spectral region, yet degrading towards the THz and sub-THz range(15,16) and proof-of-concept experiments with thermomechanical bolometers in terms of responsivity in the THz range(17) and NEP in the THz(18) (10 – 20 pW/√Hz) and MIR range(19,20) (3 and 27 pW/√Hz, respectively). Note that all these parameters have been obtained in a laboratory environment employing optical read-out techniques.

2 Technology Applications

2.1. Technology Applications tested during the ATTRACT Project

After a detailed market investigation (see sec. 3) and a fair assessment of our prototype capabilities, we targeted three different applications of our technology:

- **Food inspection:** the fast detector refresh rate combined with the potential for detecting hyperspectral images make our system suitable to be employed in conveyor belts, where food can be inspected non-destructively to assess its quality and ripeness, minimizing waste and granting for more efficient distribution.
- **Hidden art inspection:** leveraging the fact that regular paper is transparent to THz and sub-THz radiation and oil-colors have precise absorption fingerprints(21,22), we could reveal what is hidden behind a painting, including preliminary pencil sketches. Considering that the same canvas is often used several times by painters, we could explore hidden art that has been painted over without destroying precious masterpieces.
- **Health diagnostics:** our technology could represent a huge improvement for portable detectors for preliminary health screening, in particular for skin diseases.

Given the need for a THz markers library for disease recognition (which could be implemented through AI-base methods) and the requirement to pass country-specific, regulatory medical tests, we chose to focus on the first two applications. While reflection-based characterization would be possible with minimal changes in the optical setup, we decided to consider the more straightforward approach of active transmission characterization. A 0.1 THz source and detector were placed facing each other at a few centimeter distance. The object under study was placed in between, on a motorized stage if scanning with single pixels, or static in front of the matrix array. While this configuration constrained the range of objects we could test compared with a more versatile transmission/reflection scheme, it still offered a rich set of application tests. As an example, we focused on dry food, given low absorption in the THz frequency range.

FIG. 5 Single-pixel, THz imaging of a peanut: photograph (a) and resulting absorption at different dynamical ranges (b-c). Note the donut-shape indicating the presence of a kernel. Camera-based, THz imaging of a coffee bean (d-e) and of a coffee bean with tin insertion (f-g). The tin contamination appears as dark spots. Single-pixel, THz imaging of triangle-shaped pencil drawing in a paper suspended over a frame (h-i). The triangle shape is clearly visible as well as a diagonal line indicating paper bending and stress.

A gallery of the most interesting results is reported in Fig. 5. Panels (a) to (c) illustrate the inspection of a peanut using the single pixel, PyC-based sensor. Setting appropriately the measurement dynamic range, we can clearly recognize the peanut outermost silhouette (Fig. 5 (b)) but also its inner content (Fig. 5 (c)). The donut shape in this latter image is indicative of the presence of a good kernel: the central spot of minimal absorption is given by a ball-lens effect of the ellipsoidal (dielectric) kernel. While showing interesting features, the peanut image took a few hours to be recorded, limited by the motor scanning speed. A similar concept measurement can be performed using the matrix array, and requires less than one minute acquisition time. Figure 5 (d)

shows the photograph of a coffee bean, while panel (e) displays its transmission map. Again, the ball-lens effect gives a strong transmission spot in the center of the sensor. As a comparison, we considered a different coffee bean where we inserted some tin, which represents some possible internal contamination and therefore invisible to the naked eye. Figure 5 (f) shows the contaminated bean photograph while panel (g) shows its transmission map. Qualitatively similar to the healthy bean map, a couple of dark spots remarks the presence of tin, which completely stopped THz transmission. Final validation showed the possibility of detecting a pencil-drawn shape. To this end we drew a triangle on regular paper attached to a frame not transparent to THz radiation (cf. Fig. 5 (h)). The transmission map (panel (i)) revealed interesting information: the non-transparent frame looked blue while the regular paper showed the maximum transmission and appeared red. A partial absorption revealed the triangular shape (in green) while an additional diagonal line in yellow indicated a stress line in the paper which was additionally slightly bent by the frame attachment, showing the high sensitivity of our measurement.

2.2. Technology Applications envisioned after the ATTRACT Project

Future applications of our technology spans from our efforts in trying to improve even further the detector performance. In fact, switching from optical to electrical read-out can be advantageous in terms of integration, but could also lead to a degradation of device performance due to the impact of metallic contacts on the mechanical resonator and the larger noise of electrical components with respect to all-optical probes(20). In order to keep our detector NEP well below $100 \text{ pW}/\sqrt{\text{Hz}}$, we developed advanced read-out techniques which, along with the improvement of the absorbing layer, would maintain the necessary high sensitivity standards. These have led to the demonstration of black-body radiation detection in the THz range, opening new scenarios for example resonating with companies deploying THz body scanners for airport security(23) with evident advantages over their current technology based on fast mixers, which cannot operate at frequencies larger than 0.3 THz, neglecting a particularly rich and interesting portion of the THz spectrum.

An innovative detection protocol was based, on device side, by considering an appropriate single frequency transduction. For a weak perturbation, the

detector responsivity R for a single demodulating frequency can be approximated as directly proportional to a chain of derivatives:

$$R \propto \frac{dV}{df_m} \times \frac{df_m}{dL} \times \frac{dL}{d\Delta T} \times \frac{d\Delta T}{dP_a} \quad (1)$$

where V is the read-out electromotive voltage, f_m is the mechanical frequency, L a generalized geometrical length, ΔT the temperature change and P_a the absorbed power. While some terms depend on the chosen material ($d\Delta T/dP_a$ and $dL/d\Delta T$, the latter simply being the thermal expansion coefficient) and other on device geometry (df_m/dL). The first right-hand-side term, dV/df_m , depends only on the resonance spectral shape and the actuation driving frequency, the latter easily controllable in our scheme. In particular, we note that the voltages read-out around the resonances of typical devices had interesting shapes arising from the Fano effect and Duffing nonlinearities. This gives extremely sharp voltage derivatives which in turns enhance the device responsivity, see Eq. (1). Figure 6 (a) reports a typical trampoline mechanical spectrum for different piezoelectric actuator driving voltages. Low drives ($V_{\text{RMS}}=90$ mV) showed an asymmetric peak with the familiar Fano shape, given by the cross-coupling of the sharp TMB resonance with the broad ones coming from the piezoelectric stack. Increasing the drive gave rise to mechanical nonlinearities: for our material the most common one was the Duffing nonlinearity(24), which can be cast in a simple expression for an 1-D oscillator, adding a further term in the recalling force amplitude F :

$$F = -kx - \beta x^3 \quad (2)$$

where k is the spring constant, β the Duffing coefficient and x a generalized displacement. The Duffing term is known to give rise to a rich and complex dynamics including multi-stability, frequency doubling and also chaotic motion. For moderate drives it is known to make a standard Lorentzian peak more asymmetric, pushing it towards lower (softening) or higher (hardening) frequencies, depending on the sign of β , which is mostly determined by the material(25). Our system showed a net hardening effect, as can be seen in Fig. 6 (a). Interestingly, the Duffing-based deformation of our signal dramatically changes the slopes of the resonant curve; as can be seen in Fig. 6 (b), the larger drive reveals a ten-fold increase in the derivative albeit in a very narrow spectral range. This is an effective technique to increase the detector responsivity without improving the Q-factor, which is the standard practices

challenging the state-of-the-art fabrication and operational stability. The drawback of the responsivity enhancement comes with a reduction of the maximum radiation power which can be detected, which is only a weak constraint in the THz range, where researchers routinely operate with extremely low power beams. Our best device with NEP ~ 30 pW/ $\sqrt{\text{Hz}}$ had a maximum detectable power of 100 nW (ref.(14)), which well compares with state-of-the-art commercial sensors(26).

FIG. 6 (a): mechanical spectrum of the PyC TMB at different driving strengths. (b): first derivative of the modulus of the curves in (a), showing a strong peak for the largest drive albeit in a narrow bandwidth.

Operating with a single driving/demodulating frequency it is possible to implement feedback-based protocols to increase the read-out sensitivity of the system. To this end, we implemented Phase-Locked Loop (PLL) measurements, where we set the resonator phase at a certain value which we kept constant by correcting the driving frequency via a Proportional-Integral-Derivative (PID) control(27). Our reconfigurable FPGA allows us to change the measurement scheme without changing the hardware: in particular we can implement 8 multi-tone PLLs simultaneously and small upgrades to the FPGA could upgrade the scheme to 16 tones. The PLL protocol showed good stability and extremely quick locking speeds, limited by the thermal relaxation time of the TMBs (~ 10 - 20 ms, not shown). Using the improved sensitivity of PLL protocol we aimed at detecting passive black body radiation with our sensors. As reported in Fig. 7 (a), placing a hand close to the sensor we saw a net frequency change in a set of 8 neighboring TMBs that we were probing in the matrix array sensor. The response time included an overall warming up of the whole setup given by the broad angular emission of black body radiation from the hand. Interestingly, the phase we set (slightly different in each resonator,

according to their best working point) remained constant, indicating a good stability of the PLL, as shown in Fig. 7 (b). The capability of detecting passive radiation is quite significant, since it enables source-free operation. The particular configuration of our detector bench makes it even more significant, given the special window we employed to illuminate the devices.

FIG. 7 Frequency shift (a) and locked phase (b) for 8 TMBs in the matrix array configuration. Placing a hand in front of the sensor significantly shift the resonances. (c): comparison between COC transmission and normalized black body spectral radiance at 300 K. The inset shows the loglog plot of the transmitted radiance, with the green area indicating the THz range (0.1 - 15) THz and the light blue area the rest of the spectrum.

The material of our chamber window (cyclic olefin copolymer – COC) is in fact transparent in the visible and THz range, whereas it has a strong transmission suppression in the mid-infrared range, where black-body radiation peaks at room temperature. This has been summarized in Fig. 7 (c) where we simultaneously plotted the COC transmission spectrum(28) and the (normalized) spectral black body radiance for a temperature $T=300$ K, according to the well known Planck's law:

$$S(f, T) = \frac{2hf^3}{c^2} \frac{1}{e^{hf/k_B T} - 1} \quad (3)$$

where h is the Planck's constant, c the speed of light, k_B the Boltzmann's constant and f the electromagnetic frequency. The black-body maximum emission is suppressed by the COC window: in a more quantitative assessment, one could evaluate the amount of radiance reaching the TMB in

the THz frequency range (0.1 - 15 THz) and in the rest of the spectrum, including MIR, NIR and visible range (15 - 500 THz). While for the unfiltered case the two spectral regions contributed roughly equally to the total radiance, when the transmission of COC is considered the THz range (green area in the inset of Fig. 7 (c)) weights about 2.7 times more than the rest of the spectrum (light blue area in the inset of Fig. 7 (c)). This suggests a strong impact of the spectral sensitivity of our detector to THz radiation which plays a prominent role in our passive detection experiment. More detailed measurement employing specific band-pass filters will allow to clearly quantify the device performance in detecting passive detection of black-body radiation at THz frequencies.

The demonstration of passive black-body detection unveils interesting scenarios for future THz imaging applications, which won't rely on THz sources, which are often not portable or need to be cooled, making their integration in other systems challenging and making them unsuitable for field operation.

As a further activity, we successfully demonstrated the possibility of "colouring" THz radiation introducing hyperspectral features directly embedded within our imaging system. We do not report here on our results not to disclose important information about the technology.

3 Commercialization

Our commercialization strategy considered several aspects of the complex process of going from Lab to Market. Starting with the identification of the most promising market segments for the application of THz detection technology, we aimed to raise our own entrepreneurial skills by arranging a crash course on market research and application opportunities. For this purpose, at the beginning of the project, we created a "commercialization working group" made of volunteers.. They joined a short, internally run, training program which included masterclasses, experiences shared by young European entrepreneurs who have launched successful technology startups, and hands-on training on specific tasks (market and customer identification, customer benefits, competitive advantage, market size, value chain). In addition, the interaction with the student's projects outside the h-Cube consortium was leverage to further expand our business development option,

by tapping into fresh perspectives and interesting application ideas which were then included in our overall market assessment.

Our preliminary market research activities resulted in a detailed report, in which possible deployment opportunities of THz TMB detectors were screened and scored. Prioritisation criteria included: fit with the attributes of our specific technology implementation, size of the opportunity (mass vs. niche market applications), value chain structure, ease of adoption and market penetration. As described in sec. 2, based on the criteria mentioned, we prioritised 3 applications, namely: **i. Food quality control, ii. Hidden art inspection and iii. Health diagnostics.**

The preliminary commercialization activity was followed up by a more dedicated effort which considered the commercialization process during and after the ATTRACT initiative. We explored routes to market that are internal as well as external to the consortium. The former involved close interactions among our partners Asteria BD, TeraVil and Elettra¹. They identified key steps to facilitate internal commercialisation such as: development of a read-out electronics based on massive multiplexing by Elettra and integration of our sensor in TeraVil's spectroscopic systems.

To explore external commercialisation routes, we began by approaching the major European commercial players in the field of THz-based solutions and application. We then progressed to organising a thematic workshop: **THz detector technology - Thematic Workshop on Research and Applied Frontiers**, at Ca' Foscari University in Venice on February 15th-16th 2024. By inviting both academics and selected industry professionals, we promoted an exchange of scientific and industrial know-how, which allowed us to better understand the state-of-the-art in the field and to map current and emerging technology needs. A particularly fruitful interaction with a world leading supplier of security screening solutions lead us to develop and demonstrate the passive detection capabilities of our sensors. This is an initial but crucial pre-step to future exploitation of our technology through a license or a consultancy-based technology transfer to the identified company and application leader. In order to further promote our technology features and

¹ Elettra participated to h-cube as a public research institution (Elettra Sincrotrone), however it has an active industrial office for the commercialization of detectors and electronic devices which was involved in the future planning of our technology

capabilities we produced a video showcasing the compact size of our THz camera, as well as industry and application-relevant examples of active and passive scans of dry food, concealed objects, hidden art and human body (a hand, in passive mode detection). The video and follow-up conversations are designed to pave the way to an uptake of our technology by external companies.

4 Conclusions

In conclusion, during the project timeline we developed a proof-of-concept device, tested in a laboratory environment, into a pre-market Technology Readiness Level, suitable for operation in a relevant (industrial) environment. Adding all-electrical control to trampoline resonator thermomechanical bolometers, we fabricated a 256 pixel sensor which can be read using an innovative frequency multiplexing scheme. Validating the technology with focused applications, we demonstrate its usefulness for food inspection and hidden art investigation. Leveraging on novel read-out schemes, we demonstrated detection of passive THz radiation, enabling future application in fields such as security and source-less imaging. With the potential of generating hyperspectral images, our technology will follow specific commercialization paths, both considering players internal and external to the consortium, with promising prospects for deployment in the next future.

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POSICS-2: A Wireless Gamma Camera for Intraoperative Radio-Guided Surgery in Breast Cancer

Development and Performance Assessment of a Wireless Gamma Camera Using LG-SiPMs for Accurate and Efficient Surgical Guidance with Tc-99m Radiotracers

POSICS consortium

Abstract

The POSICS-2 camera is a lightweight, handheld gamma imaging device designed for intraoperative use, primarily aimed at enhancing precision in Radio-Guided Surgery procedures, such as Sentinel Lymph Node Biopsy (SLNB), with breast cancer as its primary application. With a total weight of approximately 350 g, the system combines compactness with wireless communication, making it an efficient and ergonomic device to support surgeons' decision-making and seamlessly integrate into surgical workflow. The POSICS-2 camera features two interchangeable tungsten collimators: a Low Energy High Sensitivity (LEHS) and a long Low Energy High Resolution (LEHR) collimator. This dual hardware configuration provides surgeons with the flexibility to prioritize either detection efficiency (lowering detection times) or spatial resolution, based on the requirements of each procedure. At 2 cm distance, the camera achieved spatial resolutions of 4.1 ± 0.1 mm (HS) and 2.4 ± 0.1 mm (HR). Sensitivities at 2 cm were measured at 481 ± 14 cps/MBq for the LEHS collimator and 134 ± 8 cps/MBq for the LEHR configuration. Additionally, the device demonstrated an energy resolution of 20% at 140.5 keV, confirming its suitability for Tc-99m imaging.

Keywords: Gamma camera, Surgical guidance, Sentinel lymph node biopsy, Spatial resolution, Silicon photomultiplier, Intraoperative imaging, High sensitivity.

1 Technology Description and Benchmark

The POSICS camera:

Radio-Guided Surgery (RGS) is a well-established surgical approach, which is performed in oncological procedures such as Sentinel Lymph Node Biopsy (SLNB) and Radio Occult Lesion Localization (ROLL). In these procedures, the injection of a radiotracer, which is absorbed by metabolic hot spots in the body, is used to guide surgeons to the lesion to be resected during surgical procedures. This approach is increasingly adopted in oncologic surgery for breast cancer and melanoma.

RGS typically relies on 1D gamma probes, which offer limited directional information, as these devices are only capable of measuring the decay rate of the radiotracer in the direction they are pointing to. To address this, 2D Intraoperative Gamma Cameras (IGCs) have emerged as a promising alternative, enabling real-time image visualization of the radioactive source, enhanced localization near injection sites, and reduced operating times (Mariani et al., 2011; Paredes et al., 2008; Farnworth et al., 2023; Tsuchimochi and Hatazawa, 2013; Hellingman et al., 2016; Soluri et al., 2006; Marin et al., 2017).

Figure 1: Technical drawing of the first the POSiCS-2 camera module prototype, comprising collimator, scintillator, LG-SiPMs array and back-body (Acerbi et al., 2025).

In this context, we present **POSiCS-2**: a novel, wireless handheld gamma camera tailored for SLNB and ROLL procedures (Della Volpe et al., 2019; Acerbi et al., 2025). The system utilizes a high-density LYSO:Ce scintillator, coupled with position-sensitive Linearly-Graded Silicon Photomultipliers (LG-SiPMs) developed by Fondazione Bruno Kessler (FBK), which enables high spatial resolution with a minimal number of readout channels (Gola et al.,

2013; Acerbi et al., 2023; Acerbi et al., 2024). Designed for compatibility with Tc-99m radiotracers, the camera includes two interchangeable tungsten collimators optimized for either sensitivity or resolution.

Figure 2: Spatial resolution performances of the POSICS camera with the LEHS collimator (left) and the LEHR collimator (right)

The collimators were designed through theoretical calculations improved and validated with Monte Carlo simulations using GATE (Jan et al., 2004). The chosen geometry ensures a septal penetration probability below 5% (Cherry et al., 2003). The LEHR (Low Energy High Resolution) configuration enables precise delineation of lesion margins, while the LEHS (High Sensitivity) version allows for rapid imaging, even at low radiopharmaceutical doses. A custom-built collimator shield surrounds the active region to minimize side-incident gamma rays and improve contrast.

On the detection side, POSICS-2 introduces LG-SiPMs: a new silicon photodetector in which each microcell is connected to a resistive network enabling direct charge-weighted reconstruction of the incident light spot (Acerbi et al., 2024; FBK-LG-SiPM). These 10×10 mm² sensors operate with a microcell pitch of 25 μ m and peak sensitivity near 420 nm, matching the LYSO emission. Using a 3×3 array of LG-SiPMs, the system can reconstruct gamma interaction positions with a resolution of a few hundred microns (Acerbi et al., 2025; Raiola et al., 2025), with only 8 readout channels. This approach allows for compact readout electronics and fully wireless data transmission, enabling real-time imaging with minimal hardware footprint.

The body of the camera's module houses the electronics (needed to read the electrical signals from the light detector), the wireless module sending out the position, timing and energy information of each detected gamma ray, and the rechargeable battery.

Performance testing:

Figure 3: Reconstructed image, after image correction algorithm, of the Cobalt point source with the LEHR collimator. On the left, the image was taken with the source in contact with the camera, while the image on the right was acquired with the source at 3cm.

From a scientific and technological point of view, the camera was benchmarked using a ^{57}Co point source (122 keV) to simulate Tc-99m gamma-rays energy. At 0 cm source-to-detector distance, spatial resolutions of 1.9 ± 0.1 mm (LEHS) and 1.4 ± 0.1 mm (LEHR) were recorded. Resolution degrades with increased distance, but this effect is less pronounced for the LEHR collimator. The degradation of resolution with respect to the distance of the source from the camera is a well-known phenomenon in Gamma cameras and is due to the projective effect of the collimator (Farnworth et al., 2023). The full results of resolution testing are presented in Figure 2.

In terms of sensitivity, a uniform Tc-99m source was used at a 2 cm distance. The LEHS collimator reached 481 ± 14 cps/MBq, while LEHR achieved 134 ± 8 cps/MBq. Those values that are consistent with or superior to existing intraoperative gamma cameras (Tsuchimochi and Hatazawa, 2013; Farnworth et al., 2023).

Figure 4: Recorded energy spectrum of a Tc-99m source by the POSICS-2 camera (LEHS collimator). It is possible to clearly separate the photopeak (140.5 keV energy) from other background sources and scattered gamma rays. Only gamma-rays belonging to the photopeak will be considered for imaging.

The energy resolution at 140.5 keV, assessed through flood-field imaging and pixel-by-pixel calibration, was approximately 20% FWHM for both collimator types, sufficient to discriminate Tc-99m signals from background and scattered events.

Phantom imaging and first tests on mice

Finally, phantom imaging demonstrated the system's clinical utility: a low-activity plastic mouse phantom with adjacent radioactive cavities was successfully imaged. In Figure 5, we present the results of the Mouse Phantom testing. The system demonstrated the capability to resolve small, closely spaced sources with minimal radiotracer activity. As shown in Figure 4, the mouse phantom was scanned in four separate 1-minute acquisitions to

Figure 5: Imaged Mice phantom cavities with the POSICS camera (LEHS collimator). The white lines represent the physical size of the phantom and its cavities.

compensate for the camera's FOV ($\sim 3 \times 3 \text{ cm}^2$). The composite reconstruction enabled clear identification of all regions containing radiotracer, accurately delineating the morphology of the simulated tumor structures

In summary, POSICS-2 combines portability, real-time wireless imaging, high spatial and energy resolution, and modular collimator flexibility into a single, surgeon-friendly tool. The system shows strong promise for improving surgical accuracy, reducing invasiveness, and enabling better patient outcomes through advanced intraoperative guidance.

Several scans were also performed in animal tests, for which a tumor was implanted in a mouse and Tc-99m radiotracer was injected. This test allows us

Figure 6: SPECT scan of a mouse tumor (left) taken during several minutes, compared to the POSICS reconstructed image (right), whose acquisition took only 6.83 second.

to understand the speed of the camera in reconstructing tumors, as well as the possibility of clearly distinguishing the main tumoral structure from background activity. In Figure 6, we display the image of a tumor, acquired with a SPECT scan (tens of minutes) on the left, and the POSICS camera scan of the same object. The camera produced similar results compared to the SPECT scanner, by only imaging the source for less than 7 seconds. In this picture, we can clearly observe the vertical ellipsoidal shape of the tumor, with some background activity coming from the radiotracer absorption from the liver. Regardless of this source of background gamma-rays, it was still possible to distinguish the tumor, and to observe the same shape, as what imaged by a way larger SPECT scanner. This demonstrates the camera sensitivity and precision but also the excellent dynamic range and contrast, which proves the capability to resolve multiple lesions with different activity.

The results of the experimental campaign, regarding both technical performance assessments and imaging in biological tissues, demonstrate that the design objectives have been successfully met. Specifically, the system achieves high spatial resolution (on the order of a few millimeters) and rapid acquisition times, fulfilling the requirements for intraoperative gamma imaging in SLNB procedures for breast cancer and melanoma. Furthermore, the POSICS-2 module was engineered with a compact form factor (approximately 150 mm × 48 mm × 48 mm) and a total weight below 400 g, depending on the selected collimator. These features contribute to the device's ergonomic integration into the surgical workflow, enabling precise real-time localization of radiotracer-labeled structures without disrupting the operative process.

2 Technology Applications

2.1. Technology Applications tested during the ATTRACT Project

During the ATTRACT project, it was possible to test the POSICS technology with respect to its benchmark applications: SLNB procedures. The response of the camera to the flagship radiotracer for those applications (Tc-99m) was assessed, allowing us to determine that the camera can easily differentiate this radiotracer from other gamma-ray sources, with a resolution of 20%. Moreover, it was demonstrated that imaging of those sources with POSICS is possible with a spatial resolution of a few millimeters and with high sensitivity.

The detection of Tc-99m emission was tested both with materials that simulate living tissues (such as PMMA) and with actual organic tissues, showing that

imaging through these materials is possible. Moreover, one of the main challenges to overcome in RGS is the strong background activity from neighboring tissues, as well as the shine-through effect due to the strong gamma-ray emission coming from the injection site. Through mice testing, it was possible to determine that the camera can distinguish the implanted tumor from the background radiation (for instance, in Figure 6, from the uptake of the liver), imaging the target source in a few seconds.

In addition to demonstrating the feasibility of intraoperative imaging, the POSICS-2 system was shown to offer clear advantages over conventional 1D gamma probes. While traditional probes rely on acoustic feedback and require precise manual alignment, POSICS offers real-time 2D visual feedback that is intuitive, easy to use without extensive training, and enhances localization accuracy for surgeons.

Moreover, due to the high sensitivity reached with the LEHS collimator, it will be possible to rely on the POSICS technology to check the remaining cavity after lymph nodes resection for residual activity. These features are all implemented through a wireless approach that was proven to be a reliable way of data transmission, which effectively removes the need for cumbersome cables hanging during surgeries in the operating room. This was possible thanks to the simple readout of LG-SiPMs, which allow position reconstruction reconstruction with sub-millimetric precision with only few readout channels.

The flexibility offered by its interchangeable collimators allows optimization for either high sensitivity or high spatial resolution, depending on clinical needs. The device's ability to clearly resolve small sources even in the presence of strong background emission underscores its potential as a more informative and effective alternative to standard probe-based guidance.

The combined improvements in usability, resolution, and sensitivity indicate that POSICS may not only complement but, in many cases, supersede conventional gamma probes as the primary tool in RGS.

2.2. Technology Applications envisioned after the ATTRACT Project

Due to the high sensitivity and fine spatial resolution achieved, additional clinical applications are envisioned beyond the ATTRACT project. The camera is also suited for the resection of other types of radiolabeled tissues, such as tumoral masses located within the body.

Specifically, the system is well-adapted for procedures like Radio Occult Lesion Localization (ROLL), where the device is used intraoperatively to localize tumors situated deep beneath the skin surface, in a manner analogous to lymph node identification. This capability may enhance the effectiveness of oncological surgery by improving margin definition, thereby enabling smaller incisions, and reducing post-operative complications.

The system was also evaluated for its ability to detect emissions from lutetium-177 (Lu-177), a radiopharmaceutical used in targeted beta-emitter therapy, for example in the treatment of prostate cancer. In addition to its therapeutic beta emissions, Lu-177 emits X-rays and gamma rays, with the most abundant emissions peaking at 113 keV and 208 keV. Without any hardware modifications, POSICS was capable of imaging Lu-177 sources through the detection of X-ray and 113 keV photons. Although the 208 keV emission exceeds the energy range optimized by the current collimator design, a straightforward redesign of this component would enable full compatibility with the isotope.

The integration of such functionality supports the principles of theragnostic medicine: a therapeutic strategy in which the same radiopharmaceutical used for treatment is simultaneously employed for diagnostic imaging. This approach allows real-time monitoring of radiotracer distribution in the body, offering both safety and dosimetry control during therapy (Marin et al., 2017; Ramonaheng et al., 2024). In current clinical practice, this monitoring is typically performed using large, stationary scanners (such as SPECT/CT), which limits flexibility and reduces the number of activity checks that can be realistically carried out during the course of treatment. By contrast, the compact form factor and rapid imaging capabilities of POSICS allow for repeated or even continuous imaging sessions, making it possible to track radiopharmaceutical uptake at multiple time points and in different care settings.

Therefore, the developed technology holds vast clinical potential beyond its primary application in SLNB. **A true breakthrough of POSICS lies in its ability to provide surgeons with real-time visualization of tumor margins during surgery, allowing for more precise resections. This capability can significantly reduce the**

volume of healthy tissue removed, particularly critical in procedures such as prostate or lung surgery, ultimately improving patient outcomes and post-operative quality of life. Furthermore, the opportunity to develop dedicated imaging protocols in close collaboration with surgical teams, such as optimized radiotracer injection timing, activity dosage, and acquisition windows, could enable highly tailored and efficient surgical workflows.

This adaptability is especially relevant for the integration of emerging radionuclides or novel molecular imaging agents into clinical protocols, ensuring that the system remains versatile, future-ready, and aligned with evolving standards in personalized medicine.

The potential of POSICS was recently recognized by the Innovation Technology Board of the University of Geneva, which awarded our project one of its three annual grants of CHF 30,000 to support the path toward commercialization.

3 Commercialization

The POSICS project is now entering a decisive phase, transitioning from a successful technological development effort to the early stages of clinical implementation and market preparation.

Having achieved major milestones in both laboratory and preclinical settings, the project has validated the performance, reliability, and usability of its wireless gamma camera for RGS.

With these accomplishments in place, the focus now shifts to transforming the current prototype into a certified, clinically deployable medical device.

A top priority in the commercialization path is the industrialization of the device. This involves refining the camera design based on direct clinical user feedback, improving ergonomic handling, streamlining the user interface, and ensuring robustness for operating room conditions.

The objective is to finalize a “design freeze” version of the device that complies with regulatory requirements and is ready for scalable manufacturing. All development activities are being aligned with a Quality Management System (QMS) following ISO 13485 standards for medical device design and production.

In parallel, usability studies will be extended in close collaboration with clinical teams—particularly the surgical staff at Geneva University Hospitals (HUG), already deeply involved in the project.

Discussions are ongoing with additional centers in Switzerland, Italy, and France to expand clinical partnerships. These collaborations will help ensure the device is seamlessly integrated into surgical workflows, with insights informing final adjustments to both hardware and software components.

POSICS-2 has already entered its clinical validation phase, beginning with ex-vivo testing of human lymph nodes under controlled conditions.

These initial tests confirmed the system’s ability to accurately detect radiolabeled tissues, demonstrating spatial resolution suitable for intraoperative lymph node identification.

Building on these results, the project is now preparing full in vivo clinical trials, focused initially on SLNB in breast cancer. This clinical indication is highly relevant due to the need for surgical precision and the potential to reduce long-term complications such as lymphedema.

The regulatory pathway includes achieving CE marking under the European Medical Device Regulation (MDR). The technical file will incorporate data from preclinical and clinical studies, verification and validation testing, biocompatibility assessments, software validation, and usability analyses.

In parallel, a roadmap is being prepared for FDA 510(k) or De Novo submissions, supporting potential expansion to the U.S. market based on a harmonized data package.

From the outset, protecting POSICS’ unique innovations has been a strategic priority. A PCT (Patent Cooperation Treaty) application has been filed, securing international rights around key elements of the system: its compact wireless architecture, the integration of LG-SiPM detectors with a pixelated scintillator, the simplified 8-channel readout electronics, and the proprietary software used for real-time image reconstruction.

A freedom-to-operate (FTO) analysis was also conducted, reviewing existing patents in gamma imaging, intraoperative radiation detection, and wireless medical devices.

The findings confirm that POSICS introduces original and independent technical solutions not covered by active third-party patents. The use of commercially available components, such as LG-SiPMs and LYSO scintillators, falls within standard supply agreements.

This favorable FTO position significantly reduces the risk of IP-related barriers during commercialization.

To support clinical deployment and commercial scaling, the POSICS consortium is actively preparing the launch of a dedicated startup company.

This new entity will hold licensing rights to the core technology and will oversee production, regulatory approvals, market entry, and post-market surveillance.

Early-stage planning is already in progress in coordination with academic technology transfer offices and innovation support agencies.

The startup will initially focus on bringing the POSICS gamma camera to European markets, targeting cancer centers specializing in breast surgery and SLNB. It will also form partnerships with surgical training institutions to support adoption and education. Core business functions, including product management, regulatory affairs, and customer support, will be developed internally, while manufacturing may be outsourced to certified ISO 13485-compliant partners to ensure efficiency and scalability.

Commercialization efforts have been significantly strengthened by support from **FONGIT (Fondation Genevoise pour l'Innovation Technologique)**, Switzerland's premier innovation incubator.

FONGIT is providing expert guidance on business planning, startup formation, and intellectual property strategy, while also offering mentoring and access to funding opportunities. Their involvement is helping accelerating the transition from research prototype to market-ready product, positioning POSICS for long-term impact in surgical oncology. To enable large-scale production, the POSICS team will engage manufacturing partners experienced in medical device assembly under ISO 13485 certification.

Production processes will be standardized for core components such as the LG-SiPMs arrays, collimator housing, and electronics boards, ensuring traceability and robust quality control.

A modular production strategy will allow for future product iterations without disrupting the overall manufacturing pipeline.

The supply chain will be structured around long-term agreements for key components and reliable logistics solutions for distribution across Europe and, eventually, globally. Special care will be taken with packaging, sterilization of patient-facing accessories, and transportation protocols specific to radiation-sensitive equipment.

The POSICS system delivers immediate value by enhancing surgical precision and reducing complications linked to current probe-based techniques.

Its visual feedback is expected to shorten procedure times, ease the learning curve for new surgeons, and reduce the risk of overtreatment.

Initial commercialization will target high-volume breast cancer centers in Europe.

Following this, the product has clear expansion potential into other high-need areas such as melanoma, gynecological cancers, and head and neck surgeries, where precise intraoperative imaging remains a challenge.

The POSICS platform is designed with a long-term innovation roadmap.

Current development efforts include 3D image reconstruction and augmented reality (AR) overlays that will allow surgeons to visualize radiolabeled tissues in three dimensions, superimposed on live anatomy.

These advanced capabilities will serve as a key differentiator, especially in competitive surgical imaging markets.

Combined with a strong intellectual property position, validated performance, and strategic regulatory planning, POSICS is well positioned to become a leading solution in intraoperative cancer imaging.

The team continues to pursue follow-up funding through Innosuisse and European EIC innovation programs to support clinical trials, certification, and go-to-market execution.

4 Conclusions)

Despite a modest budget and a small consortium, the POSICS project successfully achieved all its stated goals. The team developed and validated a compact, wireless gamma camera for radio-guided cancer surgery, confirming its performance through extensive laboratory tests and preclinical trials. The project also took its first steps toward clinical application, including ex-vivo testing of human lymph nodes in surgical settings.

These achievements lay a strong foundation for the next phase: redefining cancer surgery through the integration of 3D reconstruction and augmented reality (AR). By enabling surgeons to visualize radiolabeled tissues in real time and in spatial context, the POSICS system has the potential to shift current clinical practice toward more precise and less invasive interventions.

The innovation potential of POSICS has been recognized and supported by key regional platforms. The University of Geneva Innovation Office awarded the project a competitive CHF 30,000 grant to further develop the 3D imaging pipeline. Additionally, the project is receiving mentorship and strategic support from FONGIT (Fondation Genevoise pour l'Innovation Technologique) Switzerland's leading innovation incubator. This support is instrumental in accelerating the transition from prototype to market-ready medical device.

On the intellectual property front, a PCT (Patent Cooperation Treaty) application has been filed, covering the camera's unique design, wireless integration, and image processing methods. A freedom-to-operate analysis has confirmed the project's ability to proceed without infringing existing patents, securing the legal foundation necessary for commercialization.

Together, these results position POSICS as a promising candidate for startup creation and investor engagement. The combination of clinical

relevance, technological innovation, and IP protection provides a strong case for advancing the project toward regulatory approval and commercial launch. POSICS is not just a research success: it is a platform poised to transform how cancer surgeries are guided and performed.

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A Novel Hyperspectral Imaging System for Multiplex Cancer Marker Detection: Design and Clinical Evaluation

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Abstract

A novel system for cancer diagnosis has been developed and demonstrated, enabling pathologist to diagnose cancer using a single slide, thus saving precious tissue, and reducing workload. The system utilizes a Fourier-based hyperspectral imaging system which can visualize up to 15 different fluorescent markers on a single slide. Two retrospective clinical studies have been conducted, focusing on lymphoma and lung cancer, and results show that in both cases the system enabled pathologists to accurately perform diagnosis using a single slide.

Keywords: hyperspectral imaging; multiplex imaging; non-small cell lung cancer; cancer diagnosis; immunofluorescence; Fourier optics; optical system design; tissue biomarkers.

1 Introduction

Accurate cancer diagnosis critically depends on histopathological analysis of biopsy samples to determine malignancy, cancer subtype, stage, and the expression of biomarkers that guide therapeutic decisions. Immunohistochemistry (IHC) remains the gold standard for identifying these biomarkers [1]. However, conventional IHC is inherently limited, as it typically allows only a single biomarker to be visualized per slide. This

constraint requires multiple serial sections—often 5 to 10 slides per case, occasionally processed gradually, which extends processing time, increases tissue consumption and complicates interpretation, collectively resulting in delayed clinical diagnostic decision-making [2].

Multiplex imaging offers a compelling alternative by enabling simultaneous visualization of multiple biomarkers on a single tissue section. Although several multiplexing technologies have been developed and commercialized in recent years [2], their clinical adoption remains limited.

Multiplex imaging can potentially benefit clinical practice in several key ways:

1. **Tissue Preservation:** In many cancers—including lung, brain, and pancreatic tumors—the diagnostic tissue yield is minimal. Competing demands from hematoxylin and eosin (H&E) staining, IHC, qPCR, FISH and next-generation sequencing (NGS) often exceed available tissue. Utilization of Multiplex imaging, instead of usage of several single-plex IHC staining steps requiring multiple sections, could mitigate this issue, enabling complete informed diagnosis also from low-availability tissue samples [3].
2. **Improved Contextual Interpretation:** Traditional IHC assesses different biomarkers on adjacent sections, making it difficult to interpret co-expression patterns and spatial relationships between cell types. In contrast, multiplex imaging allows for single-cell co-localization and spatial mapping of the entire specimen, including the tumor microenvironment—an area increasingly recognized for its prognostic and therapeutic importance [4].
3. **Workflow Efficiency and Diagnostic Timelines:** With multiplex imaging, a single tissue section can provide a comprehensive biomarker panel, potentially reduce lab-workload, and shorten the diagnostic process. This can eliminate the need for iterative rounds of staining and re-evaluation, thus shortening the time to treatment initiation.

Most currently available multiplexing solutions rely on fluorescent labeling (multiplex Immuno-fluorescence, mIF), due to the narrow spectral bandwidth of fluorophores, enabling higher multiplexing compared to chromogenic stains used in IHC. However, conventional fluorescence-based systems typically utilize specific narrow-band excitation and emission filters for each fluorophore, necessitating mechanical switching of filter cubes and resulting in photon (signal) loss, cross-talk between channels and prolonged acquisition

times [5]. To achieve higher multiplexing, many multiplex imaging systems employ cyclic staining—iteratively staining, imaging, and bleaching of a few markers at a time, followed by post-staining computational image alignment step. While these approaches can detect dozens of markers, they are slow, expensive, and not readily compatible with routine clinical workflows [6]. Hence, there is a clear need for a fast, robust, and clinically practical multiplex imaging solution. In this project, we developed a novel hyperspectral imaging system based on a monolithic Sagnac interferometer and Fourier-based spectral reconstruction. Unlike conventional filter-based systems, our method enables full spectral acquisition without mechanical switching or filter wheels. We describe the design and operation of this system, its ability to differentiate a high number of fluorescent markers, and two applications we have studied in a retrospective clinical study. Our results suggest that this new platform can bridge the gap between advanced multiplexing capabilities and practical clinical utility.

2 Technology Description and Benchmark

The multiplex imaging method implemented in this system is based on a fundamentally different optical principle than standard systems, enabling the acquisition of hyperspectral data without the use of optical filters or mechanical switching elements (beyond X-Y sample scanning). This design offers potential advantages over conventional multispectral imaging systems, particularly in terms of mechanical simplicity, acquisition speed, and long-term stability.

A schematic of the optical system is shown in Figure 1a. The core innovation is the integration of a Sagnac interferometer into the detection path. Unlike other interferometers, the Sagnac configuration introduces an angularly-dependent optical delay between the clockwise and counterclockwise propagation paths. For a monochromatic light source, this delay produces a sinusoidal interference pattern as a function of beam angle along one axis. In our design, the interferometer is placed in a collimated (parallel) beam region, where the angle of each ray corresponds to the position of its origin in the field of view. The light is then refocused onto the detector, resulting in interference fringes superimposed on the sample image. Crucially, the fringe density depends on the wavelength of the emitted light, enabling spectral encoding of spatial information. For broadband fluorescent emission, the intensity at each point on the detector is thus a convolution of the sample's emission spectrum and the sinusoidal angular-frequency response of the interferometer. Thus, by stepping and sampling the image multiple times across the field of view we can assemble the Fourier transform of the emission spectrum for each point on

the sample. Applying Fast Fourier Transform (FFT) to the data we thus reconstruct the emission spectrum [7], which is finally analyzed using a library of the known emission spectra of the fluorophores used in the staining, to produce the relative amount of staining of each fluorophore at each point. Collecting the points we can thus assemble an independent image for every fluorophore represented in the library, including autofluorescence. To further enhance multiplexing capability, we incorporated multi-wavelength excitation using multiple LEDs (currently 405 nm and 490 nm). The LEDs are fired sequentially at each scanning step, the images for every LED are analyzed separately until the extraction of the emission spectra, but the final spectral analysis finding the contributions of each fluorophore are done with the combined set of spectra for optimal elimination of cross talk.

A key advancement in our system is the replacement of the standard free-space interferometer with a monolithic Sagnac interferometer [8], custom-fabricated for this application. Although it lacks the tunability of mirror-based setups, it delivers superior mechanical stability and was shown to maintain alignment across months of operation without recalibration—an essential feature for clinical translation.

To enable optimal system performance, several calibration procedures were implemented:

- (a) Non-uniformity calibration was performed by illuminating an empty field to correct for illumination and detection inconsistencies.
- (b) Image distortion calibration was carried out using high-precision optical targets to correct geometric aberrations.
- (c) Stage motion calibration was also conducted using the same optical targets to ensure accurate positioning during scanning.
- (d) Spectral calibration was performed using narrow-band interference filters to determine the system's spectral response.

To accurately perform spectral unmixing, reference spectra for all fluorophores in the panel were acquired from single-dye stained tissue sections. Tissue autofluorescence was measured and modeled using multiple components extracted via principal component analysis (PCA) applied to unstained slides. These components were found to be tissue type specific and thus have to be separately optimized for each application.

Additional standard signal processing techniques were employed, including noise averaging, image sharpening, and compensation for varying exposure conditions.

The system was developed to a fully functional prototype level including an auxiliary color vision channel, automatic focusing, preliminary low resolution

scanning to enable tissue detection and scan area optimization and a full user interface. The current version of the scanner is designed as an add-on to a standard microscope, as can be seen in Figure 1b.

Preliminary analysis was additionally undertaken to segment the image into individual cells and classify them according to their unique biomarker expression profiles. This allowed us to compute the percentage of positive cells for every marker, a metric that is often used in cancer diagnosis guidelines, such as in lymphoma, thus saving the pathologists time to estimate expression levels and eliminating the common inter-observer variability.

Additional algorithm development done by the consortium included, in brief:

- (a) Development of AI-based classification algorithm enabling the detection of individual cancer cells in a tissue, proving that using the spectral information better detection is obtained compared to a standard RGB image,
- (b) Compressed sensing algorithm was developed to optimize the number of samples taken across the field of view, proposing that sub-Nyquist sampling could be used, leading to a speed up of the system.

These algorithms will be considered for implementation in the system as part of the next generation.

3 Technology Applications

3.1 Technology Applications tested during the ATTRACT Project

To demonstrate the capability of the system in addressing specific diagnostic needs, we have conducted during the ATTRACT project two retrospective clinical studies, one focusing on lymphoma and the other focusing on Non-Small-Cell Lung Cancer (NSCLC).

Lymphoma Study

Lymphoma was selected as this is the most difficult cancer to accurately diagnose, having over 80 sub-types. IHC is the main tool for sub-typing hence this case is especially interesting as ~15 markers are typically used for each

patient. For this study we have developed a staining panel focused on sub-typing of Diffuse Large B-Cell Lymphoma (DLBCL), which is the most prevalent group of lymphoma cases, including the following markers: CD3, CD20, CD79a, CD10, Ki-67, MUM1, BCL6 and a nuclear marker. An image of a healthy control tissue, including both a combined image and a separate image for each marker, is shown in Figure 2. As part of this study, we have retrospectively examined 20 cases of DLBCL of different sub-types. The multiplexing images of each case were blindly examined by two pathologists and the sub-typing they performed with these images was in full agreement with the reference obtained using the standard of care (multiple IHC slides). A typical image of a lymphoma case is shown in Figure 3, where the diffusive nature of the cancer, washing out the clear macro features of the healthy tissue, is very clear.

Non-Small-Cell Lung Cancer Study

Lung cancer was chosen as it is the most prevalent cancer type in which tissue scarcity is a persistent challenge. In fact, studies show that in approximately 15% of advanced-stage lung cancer cases, tissue scarcity is the primary reason for partial diagnosis [10,11]. As a result, in those instances, patients may be treated with a sub-optimal generic therapy rather than an advance targeted therapy that could have saved their lives due to the lack of an accurate diagnosis.

The panel focused on Non-Small-Cell Lung Cancer, the most prevalent family of lung cancer types, and included the following biomarkers: TTF1, P40, PanCK, CD45, ALK, PD-L1, and a nuclear stain. These biomarkers addressed multiple diagnostic needs: (a) Initial diagnosis of NSCLC and differentiation between the two major subtypes—adenocarcinoma and squamous cell carcinoma, (b) Biomarkers enabling therapy selection: PD-L1 and ALK, (c) Supporting biomarkers, such as CD45, assisting in visualizing the immune compartment within the tumor microenvironment and helping to exclude immune cells that may express PD-L1, thereby improving the accuracy of tumor-specific PD-L1 quantification. Table 1 summarizes key details for each target measured by the panel, including the fluorophores and detection methods used.

To assess the validity of our system as well as the staining procedures we initially used large excision samples. Figure 4 shows a comparison of PD-L1 staining across a large area using both IHC and our mIF system. Figures 5a and 5b further compare the same case for multiple markers on a smaller scale. As the slides shown are not successive slides the images do not seem to be identical, however the main features are similar in nature. Furthermore, the

images show that in some cases our mIF images are clearer and thus easier to interpret than standard IHC.

Finally, to further validate that our platform produces accurate clinical data, we conducted a retrospective clinical study using pathologist-curated tissue microarray (TMA) slides (Figure 6). A sub-cohort of 20 cases taken from two TMA slides, mostly pre-diagnosed as NSCLC cases, was used for the study, and Figure 7 shows a few typical examples. The mIF images of the 20 cases were blindly analyzed by a pathologist and found in full agreement with the reference diagnosis previously done using standard IHC staining.

Collectively, over the two studied cancer types, our results demonstrate complete agreement between diagnoses done based on our multiplex imaging data and the reference diagnoses previously made for the same cases using standard IHC assays, thus validating the clinical utility of our system.

3.2 Technology Applications envisioned after the ATTRACT Project

Following the ATTRACT project, several applications are envisioned, each having its own potential benefits and challenges:

- (a) Lung Cancer – additional work is needed in order to bring our lung panel to a product level, including: (1) enhancing the panel to include a few additional markers would be beneficial in some cases; (2) optimizing the staining process with a focus on simplification, reduction of the number of steps, and (3) adapting and testing the process on an automatic stainer. These activities would support bringing this application, which is attractive due to the large number of patients and tissue scarcity, to market.
- (b) Kidney biopsy applications - kidney biopsies are taken in different cases of kidney disease (e.g. lupus nephritis) or in cases of kidney transplants, in order to assess the state of the kidneys. This is a niche market relative to some of the more abundant cancer types, but with ~60,000 cases per year in the US, this is still a relevant market to address and not smaller than some other cancer types. The current standard of care in kidney pathology is to run a panel of 10 markers, and these are currently done using fluorescent staining, rather than bright-field IHC staining which is the standard in cancer. Hence, there

is an opportunity here to improve the diagnosis by adding co-localization of markers, and save workload by running all stains on a single slide.

- (c) Additional applications that we have briefly considered include prostate cancer and liver pathology (both cancer and metabolic diseases). Each of these (and other) opportunities is a different market in terms of the expected benefits to the pathologist and the pathology lab, but they can all benefit for the same set of basic capabilities we are bringing. It should be finally noted that in the cancer diagnosis field focus is needed in order to properly answer market needs in a single application, hence additional applications should only be considered at a later stage.

4 Commercialization

During the ATTRACT project we have transferred the knowledge from the academy to a newly set startup company (PentaOmix), developed the technology and have demonstrated a compelling PoC. Furthermore, we have designed and build a fully functional working prototype that can already be considered a lab tool for low quantity applications. We additionally have developed an initial go to market strategy, studied the regulation and reimbursement status and developed a business model.

As part of the next steps we are in process of raising seed funding which we plan to use for following main purposes: (a) bring the system to a higher TRL that will enable us to install it in a clinical lab, with a focus on improving acquisition speed and automation, as well as develop a standalone version that will not rely on a commercial microscope, (b) finalize the staining panel for the first installation, in collaboration with the intended first installation site, and (c) running a beta site in the first installation site in order to test the system in real world conditions towards wider market deployment and collecting validation data to support regulatory approvals.

5 Conclusions

During this project we have dramatically progressed the TRL of the system. Starting from a very initial concept we have reached a fully functional prototype that can be operated as a lab tool, providing high quality images and demonstrating up to 8 different markers on the same slide, thus providing a compelling POC of the technology. Furthermore, in two separate clinical studies, focusing on two different cancer cases, we have demonstrated that our system enables accurate diagnosis using a single slide, where currently

multiple slides are needed using the standard techniques, saving precious tissue and reducing workload.

As in any medical system, the path forward required in order to bring our system to full commercialization is still long. We next have to demonstrate the system installed in the relevant environment, being the hospital lab, which is highly demanding, demonstrate to regulatory authorities that our results are at least comparable to standard of care over a large enough set of cases, and receive the buy-in of both the medical community and the payers. The support we received through the ATTRACT project has been absolutely essential as a start to achieve these challenging goals.

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Tables and Figures

Figure 1a: Schematic description of the optical system

Figure 1b: Image of the scanner prototype.

Figure 2: Healthy tonsil tissue imaged using our multiplex imaging system, showing a composite image of 8 markers (center) and the image of each marker separately (around, corresponding to the white frame in the center image).

Figure 3: Diffuse Large B-Cell Lymphoma (DLBCL) case imaged by our multiplex imaging system, demonstrating the diffusive nature of this cancer, after washing out the natural macro order of the tissue.

Table 1: The markers used in the NSCLC panel

Target	Target's Sub-Cellular Localization	Antibody Clone used (Origin)	Fluorophore used for target detection	Detection Method
TTF1	Nucleus	8G7G3/1 (Mouse)	PE-eFluor610	Unconjugated Primary Antibody/ Biotin-Fab/ Streptavidin-conjugate
P40	Nucleus	BC28 (Mouse)	PE-iFluor 710	Conjugated-Primary Antibody
PanCK	Membrane+ Cytoplasm	AE1/AE3 (Mouse)	PE-Cy5	Conjugated-Primary Antibody
PD-L1	Membrane	22C3 (Mouse)	CF405S	Unconjugated Primary Antibody/ HRP-Conjugated-a-Mouse Antibody/ CF405S-Tyramide; (Tyramide-Signal-Amplification)
ALK	Cytoplasm	D5F3 (Rabbit)	CF405L	Unconjugated Primary Antibody/ HRP-Conjugated-a-Rabbit Antibody/ CF405L-Tyramide; (Tyramide-Signal-Amplification)
CD45	Membrane	2B11+ PD7/26 (Mouse)	mFluor Violet 610	Conjugated-Primary Antibody
Nuclear DNA	Nucleus	na	NucSpot-500/515	Conjugated-Staining reagent

Figure 4: Comparing PD-L1 staining between (A) IHC, (B) our mIF

Figure 5a: Comparing staining on a small scale (bar is 200 microns) – standard HC: (A) H&E (B) PanCK (C) TTF1 (D) p40 (E) PD-L1 (F) ALK

Figure 5b: Comparing staining on a small scale – mIF on our system: (H) Autofluorescence (I) PanCK (J) TTF1 (K) p40 (L) PD-L1 (M) ALK

Figure 6: Tissue Micro-Array (TMA) full slide scan

Figure 7: Typical case, showing: (A) Adenocarcinoma, (B) Squamous Cell carcinoma, (C) PD-L1 positive squamous cell carcinoma, (D) ALK positive case.

Highly efficient IR detection based on black germanium technology

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Abstract

Near-infrared (NIR) photodetectors are essential in applications such as telecommunications, medical imaging, and spectroscopy, where high sensitivity and low noise are critical. Germanium (Ge) is a promising material due to its suitable bandgap for NIR absorption and compatibility with complementary metal-oxide-semiconductor (CMOS) processes. However, conventional Ge photodiodes often suffer from high reflectance, limited quantum efficiency, and elevated dark current, limiting their performance. Here we present a novel Ge NIR photodiode featuring a nanostructured active area fabricated via inductively coupled plasma reactive ion etching (ICP-RIE). A strong charge-separating electric field is induced into the active area by the high negative fixed charge in an atomic layer deposited (ALD) aluminium oxide (Al_2O_3). Due to this electric field, also a laterally conductive channel is also formed. The nanostructure further enhances this effect by increasing the field depth, enabling performance beyond conventional ion-implanted junctions. To suppress surface recombination and to electrically isolate the active area, a silicon dioxide (SiO_2)/ Al_2O_3 passivation stack with positive fixed charge is developed using plasma-enhanced ALD. This stack provides excellent passivation for planar surfaces and acts as a channel stopper to further reduce the dark current. The resulting photodiode demonstrates over 90% external quantum efficiency (EQE) across the 1.2–1.6 μm range at zero bias and room temperature and exceeds 100% EQE below 300 nm due to carrier multiplication. It also exhibits ultra-low dark current and high specific detectivity, for example, 9.95×10^{10} Jones at 25 °C and 8×10^{13} Jones at -180 °C at the wavelength of 1550 nm. The photodiodes developed here are currently on the market and the first components are already sold to customers.

Keywords: near-infrared detection; germanium; photodiode; surface nanostructure; atomic layer deposition

1 Technology Description and Benchmark

Here we describe the technology development for efficient surface passivation scheme for black Ge based on atomic layer deposited (ALD) Al_2O_3 . More specifically, we investigate and address the three aspects that are concerned when integrating black Ge into optoelectronic devices: (1) surface area enhancement, (2) crystallographic damage caused by ion-bombardment and (3) chemical residuals remaining on nanotextured surfaces.

Figure 1 shows the surface morphology for the two sets of nanotexture used in this study, fabricated by using ICP-RIE with an ICP power of 1000 W. First, a 700 nm deep nanotexture (Fig. 1a) was formed by using capacitively-coupled plasma (CCP) power of 4 W, which results in black Ge with a broadband surface reflectance of less than 1 % [1]. The inset shows an optical image of the full 4-inch wafer to demonstrate the black appearance by naked eye. Second, a shallow nanotexture of ~ 200 nm height (Fig. 1b) was formed by using CCP power of 2 W, which results in completely different morphology i.e. only moderately increases the surface area compared to a planar surface. These two morphologies allow us to study the impact of the increased surface area on the passivation.

FIG. 1. Cross-sectional SEM images: (a) A deep nanotexture fabricated by using 4 W capacitively-coupled plasma power (inset showing an optical image of the corresponding 4 inch Ge wafer) and (b) a shallow nanotexture fabricated by using 2 W capacitively-coupled plasma power.

To determine the starting level of surface passivation of the Ge nanostructures, for the first experiment we chose the passivation scheme that has provided the best performance on planar Ge [2]. After subjecting to a HCl cleaning for 5 min, we deposited a 20 nm thick Al_2O_3 conformally on the nanotexture and activated the surface passivation by performing a 400°C post-deposition anneal. As expected, for a planar germanium reference sample, ALD Al_2O_3

provided excellent surface passivation resulting in a lifetime above 1 ms, as shown in Figure 2 [3,4]. For the deep nanostructures, the same passivation scheme leads to substantially lower lifetime around 200 μs (blue markers). Surprisingly, for shallow nanostructures (green markers) there is no significant improvement despite the drastic difference between the surface morphology shown by the SEM images. Therefore, it is clear that surface area enhancement, due to the formation of nanostructures, is not the primary factor limiting the lifetime for the nanotextured samples.

FIG. 2. Injection-dependent effective minority carrier lifetime of HCl-cleaned ALD Al_2O_3 passivated Ge samples with a planar surface (pink rhombus), a deep nanotexture (blue circle) and a shallow nanotexture (green triangle).

There has been a pervasive concern on surface damage induced by RIE [5,6], hence, to elucidate the role of ion-bombardment on the poor effective lifetime measured on nanotextured samples, the crystallinity of the nanotextured Ge was examined in detail at the Al_2O_3 -Ge interface by using TEM. As shown in Figure 3, Ge lattice at the proximity of the Al_2O_3 -Ge interface remains crystalline as no amorphous-like structure is observed, akin to what has been demonstrated on black silicon fabricated by the same method [7]. Consequently, the poor effective lifetime shown above is not caused by ion-bombardment during the etching process. Since no crystallographic damage was observed for the deep nanotexture, the same conclusion can be drawn from the shallow structures, as the degree of ion-bombardment correlates to the magnitude of CCP power, which was reduced from 4W to 2W. In summary, this result clearly demonstrates that it is possible to fabricate Ge nanotexture by ICP-RIE that is free of crystallographic damage.

FIG. 3. (a) A dark field transmission electron microscope image of a deep nanotexture coated with a 20 nm Al_2O_3 layer at 500,000 times magnification. Sub-labels (1), (2) and (3) indicate a region of sputtered platinum, Al_2O_3 layer and Ge, respectively. Green dashed-box highlights the area where the image with the higher magnification was taken. (b) A bright field transmission electron microscope image at 5 million times magnification. Sub-labels (2) and (3) indicate a region of Al_2O_3 layer and Ge, respectively.

Since neither the enhanced surface area nor the crystal damage explains the poor lifetime of the black Ge, next we studied whether some chemical residuals formed during dry etching could be the root cause. Figure 4 a and b shows the XPS spectra of the S 2p and F 1s bonding states measured at the surface of the nanotexture directly after the ICP-RIE process. A significant amount of sulfur and fluoride elements were detected on both deep and shallow nanotextures. (Note that there is a much higher amount of residuals detected on the shallow nanotexture, which could be due to the use of higher process gas flows and a lower CCP power during the ICP-RIE etching process.) As shown in Fig. 4c, after 5 min of HCl cleaning, the sulfur elements with a higher binding energy were removed, while the ones with a lower binding energy remain on the surface. On the other hand, all the fluoride elements were removed for both sets of nanotexture (Fig. 4d). The removed elements are likely associated with oxide compounds, as HCl has shown to be efficient in removing oxide from germanium surface [8]. To conclude, HCl is not able to remove all the chemical residues and most likely the remaining sulfur-related residuals cause the poor surface passivation. We speculate the following mechanisms for this: i) They could act as recombination-sites at the Al_2O_3 -Ge interface, which increases the interface defect density, ii) They could also hinder the subsequent activation of the Al_2O_3 layer during the post-deposition annealing, which reduces the fixed charge density at the interface. Nevertheless, the exact mechanism is difficult to identify, due to the ambiguous analysis of C-V measurements on nanotextured surface.

FIG. 4. X-ray photoelectron spectroscopy measurement of a deep nanotexture (cyan) and a shallow nanotexture (green): (a) S 2p level prior to a HCl cleaning, (b) F 1s level prior to a HCl cleaning, (c) S 2p level after 5 mins of HCl cleaning and (d) F 1s level after 5 mins of HCl cleaning.

Figure 5 shows what is the minority carrier lifetime after successful chemical residue removal. The addition of a 10-second cleaning in H_2O_2 solution increases the effective minority carrier lifetime of the deep nanotexture by 2-folds, reaching over $400 \mu\text{s}$ in the low-injection region. As the combination of oxidation and dissolution of Ge atoms during the H_2O_2 dip likely also modulates the nanotexture morphology, the impact of this cleaning treatment on the surface reflectance and morphology needs to be investigated. The surface reflectance of the deep nanotexture after 10 seconds H_2O_2 cleaning remains sub- 1% (Fig. 5b), as the features are largely intact, with only some rounding observed at the tip of the nanotexture. As another significant observation, it was found that the deep nanotexture with an addition of 10 seconds H_2O_2 treatment (orange star) resulted in a noticeably higher lifetime ($400 \mu\text{s}$ vs $240 \mu\text{s}$) when compared to the shallow nanotexture treated with HCl alone (green triangle) despite having a substantially higher surface area and a lower surface reflectance. Since the attribute of crystal damage has been excluded by the TEM image shown above, it is likely that the difference in surface contamination prior to ALD deposition, due to the addition of H_2O_2 cleaning, contributes to the difference in lifetime measured for both sets of nanotextures. Removing all the chemical residuals is, therefore, demonstrated to be a crucial factor in achieving good surface passivation for Ge nanotexture created by ICP-RIE process.

FIG. 5. (a) Injection-dependent effective minority carrier lifetime and (b) wavelength-dependent front surface reflectance of Ge samples with a deep nanotexture (cyan circle and dashed-line), a shallow nanotexture (green triangle and dashed-line), a deep nanotexture with 10 seconds H_2O_2 cleaning (orange star and dashed-line), a shallow nanotexture with 10 seconds H_2O_2 cleaning (purple square and dashed-line) and a planar surface (black dashed-line). Embedded SEM images: a deep nanotexture (left) and a shallow nanotexture (right) after 10 seconds of H_2O_2 cleaning.

In the case of shallow nanostructures, the addition of H_2O_2 cleaning was found to affect significantly the morphology by removing most of the features resulting in a planar-like surface. Consequently, the lifetime was improved from sub-300 μs to over 900 μs . The obtained value is clearly higher than in the deep nanostructure counterpart. This difference is likely due to the difference in the surface area. Consequently, it is suggested that the lifetime of the deep nanotexture after 10 seconds of H_2O_2 cleaning is limited by the significantly larger surface area when compared to the planar-like surface.

In order to analyze the tradeoff between electrical and optical properties after different H_2O_2 cleaning durations, Figure 6 summarizes both the surface recombination velocity (SRV) and the front surface reflectance at 1550 nm for all the samples. The deep nanotexture reduces the surface reflectance compared to the planar surface from over 35 % to sub- 1%. The surface reflectance of the deep nanotexture does not meaningfully increase by the H_2O_2 treatment until 30 seconds is reached, beyond which it increases significantly to over 20 % after 120 seconds. This significant increase in surface reflectance is expected, as the surface morphology is drastically modified after 120 seconds of H_2O_2 treatment. On the other hand, the formation of the deep nanotexture substantially increases the SRV as compared to the planar surface from 6 cm/s to over 100 cm/s. After 10 seconds H_2O_2 treatment, the SRV reduces by half, reaching 40 cm/s. Further increase in duration leads to further reduction in SRV, with 30 cm/s and 10 cm/s

measured after 30 seconds and 120 seconds, respectively. Consequently, the best combination of both optical and electrical quality is reached with 30 seconds H₂O₂ cleaning resulting in ~1% reflectance and SRV of ~30 cm/s.

FIG. 6. Front surface reflectance at 1550 nm (orange) and surface recombination velocity at injection level of $2 \times 10^{14} \text{ cm}^{-3}$ (blue) for the deep nanotexture after various H₂O₂ cleaning times (circles). Corresponding values for the planar surface (squares) are given as a reference.

The experiments have demonstrated, for the first time, efficient surface passivation of nanostructured Ge surfaces fabricated by ICP-RIE. First, we defined the limiting factors preventing effective surface passivation by conventional ALD Al₂O₃. While TEM analysis ruled out the presence of crystallographic damage, XPS confirmed that the root cause lies in sulfur-related chemical residues that were remaining on the surface after HCl cleaning. By adding a short H₂O₂ dip, we were able to remove all the chemical residuals on the nanostructured surfaces, resulting in a 2-fold increase in effective lifetime. After chemical residue removal, the next factor limiting the lifetime was found to be the increased surface area. To find a balance between electrical and optical properties, the surface area was reduced by extending the duration of the H₂O₂ dip. Consequently, the surface recombination velocity of nanostructured Ge further reduced from ~100 cm/s to ~30 cm/s without impact on the front surface reflectance.

2 Technology Applications

2.1. Technology Applications tested during the ATTRACT Project

The main application where we integrate our black Ge technology is a NIR photodetector, namely a PIN photodiode. The device is designed to minimize

both optical losses (reflectance) and electrical losses (carrier recombination, leakage current). A schematic cross section of the b-Ge photodiode structure is shown in Figure 7.

FIG. 7. Cross-sectional schematic of the black Germanium photodiode fabricated in the project.

The nanostructures are conformally passivated with atomic layer deposited (ALD) aluminium oxide (Al_2O_3) [9]. This dielectric contains a high negative fixed charge density (Q_{tot} , $\sim 2.3 \times 10^{12} \text{ cm}^{-2}$) [10], which repels majority electrons from the Ge surface, leaving behind ionized donor atoms. This results in upward band bending and generates a built-in electric field near the surface. The field suppresses surface recombination through field-effect passivation, achieving the SRV of $\sim 30 \text{ cm/s}$. Additionally, the field enables efficient carrier separation without introducing crystal defects typically associated with ion implantation. The resulting electric field intensity reaches up to 10^5 V/cm [11], with vertical orientation dominant near the surface facilitating effective separation of photogenerated electron-hole pairs and their subsequent drift to the front-side anode and rear-side cathode for photocurrent collection. As for the surface outside of the nanostructure, an advanced plasma-enhanced ALD silicon oxide (SiO_2)/ Al_2O_3 passivation stack is deposited. The Q_{tot} of the stack is positive with a density $\sim 8.5 \times 10^{11} \text{ cm}^{-2}$, resulting in a SRV as low as 1.3 cm/s [12]. In comparison to the active area with mere negatively charged Al_2O_3 and the resulting inversion, this stack provides the other type of field-effect with the positive charge to passivate the n-type Ge surface by (electron) accumulation. Furthermore, this stack shows great potential as a channel-stopping material, which blocks the current interconnection between anode and guard ring, and effectively isolates the active area from the leakage current originating outside it. By addressing both optical and electrical losses, the fabricated proof-of-concept b-Ge photodiode enables enhanced performance in near-infrared photodetection.

The optical properties of the fabricated device are shown in Figure 8a. A very low reflectance ($< 1\%$) has been achieved at b-Ge photodiode over a long spectral range from 300 to 1600 nm as expected. The inset shows the spatial

reflectance map of the photodiode, the laser source is 656 nm and the raster size is 50 μm . The reflectance map confirms the ultra-low reflectance through the whole nanostructure area and shows an optically homogeneous surface, which is very important in image sensors and in single-pixel photodiode [13,14].

FIG. 8. (a) Reflectance, transmittance and absorbance of the b-Ge photodiode active area. The inset shows a reflectance map measured at a wavelength of 656 nm. (b) EQE of b-Ge photodiode as a function of wavelength. The state-of-the-art NIR commercial photodiodes are shown as reference.

External quantum efficiency (EQE) reflects a photodiode's capability to convert photon energy into electrical current across different wavelengths. Fig. 8b presents the EQE of the b-Ge photodiode, which exhibits outstanding performance across an exceptionally wide spectral range, from ultraviolet (UV, 0.2 μm) to NIR (1.7 μm), detecting nearly 100% of the incoming photons. The observation of EQE exceeding 100% in the UV region is scientifically intriguing. To our knowledge, such behaviour has not been previously reported in Ge photodiodes, as UV photons are typically absorbed within a surface "dead layer" and lost to recombination. The ALD Al_2O_3 passivated nanostructured Ge appears to effectively eliminate this dead layer, enabling unusually high carrier collection efficiency even at short wavelengths.

For comparison, Fig. 8b also includes EQE data from a leading InGaAs photodiode [15] optimized for 1550 nm and a high-performance commercial Ge photodiode [16]. Our b-Ge device outperforms both references not only in absolute EQE but also in spectral range. While InGaAs can be engineered to extend detection to $\sim 2.5 \mu\text{m}$, this typically degrades performance at shorter wavelengths. In contrast, the b-Ge photodiode maintains high EQE from the UV to NIR without sacrificing performance.

Table 1 presents quantitative EQEs, responsivities and detectivities at three key wavelengths (1.3 μm , 1.55 μm and 1.75 μm) for b-Ge photodiode and the reference photodiodes at room temperature. It clearly shows that b-Ge photodiode consistently exhibits higher responsivity at all three wavelengths compared to the InGaAs references. As expected, the commercial Ge photodiode underperforms in comparison. For instance, the EQE and the peak responsivity at 1.55 μm are 68% and 0.85 A/W, respectively. The fact that the b-Ge photodiode surpasses even the best-performing InGaAs photodiodes highlights the strength of this novel design in boosting responsivity. However, at room temperature, the specific detectivity of the b-Ge device remains lower than that of InGaAs due to higher leakage current. This is primarily attributed to thermal generation in the Ge bulk. Consequently, high-sensitivity commercial Ge photodetectors are typically operated at cryogenic temperatures (down to $-200\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$) to suppress this effect.

TABLE 1: Comparison of EQE, corresponding responsivity (R) and detectivity (D^*) at three selected wavelengths at room temperature between this work and the best-performing commercial InGaAs and Ge photodiodes reported so far.

Photodiode	EQE [%] / R [A/W] / D^* [$\text{cm}\cdot\text{Hz}^{1/2}\cdot\text{W}^{-1}$]		
	$\lambda_1 = 1300\text{ nm}$	$\lambda_2 = 1550\text{ nm}$	$\lambda_3 = 1750\text{ nm}$
This work (Ge)	98.9% / 1.04 / 8.32×10^{10}	99.19% / 1.24 / 9.95×10^{10}	88.01% / 1.24 / 9.97×10^{10}
Commercial (InGaAs) Hamamatsu G8370-85	86.8% / 0.91 / 3.47×10^{12}	88.0% / 1.10 / 4.19×10^{12}	- / - / -
Commercial (Ge) Thorlabs FDG50	67.7% / 0.71 / 6.51×10^{10}	68.0% / 0.85 / 7.79×10^{10}	17.0% / 0.24 / 2.20×10^{10}

To assess the dark current behavior, Figure 9 presents the temperature-dependent leakage current of the b-Ge photodiode, measured from $25\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ to $-180\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$. At room temperature and -10 V reverse bias, the leakage current density is approximately $100\text{ }\mu\text{A}/\text{cm}^2$, which is comparable to the best values reported for bulk Ge photodiodes ($60\text{--}1000\text{ }\mu\text{A}/\text{cm}^2$) [16,17]. When cooled to $-180\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$, the dark current drops drastically to just $1.4\text{ nA}/\text{cm}^2$. This significant reduction enables a detectivity of up to $\sim 8\times 10^{13}\text{ cm}\cdot\text{Hz}^{1/2}\cdot\text{W}^{-1}$ surpassing that of InGaAs photodiodes and highlighting the performance potential of b-Ge under low-temperature operation.

FIG. 9. Dark current under different temperatures (from 25 °C to -180 °C).

In addition to the above photodiode testing, we have also integrated the black Ge technology to Baltic Scientific Instruments (BSI)'s existing commercial infrared detector. Their HPGe infrared detectors are intended for NIR fluorescence or Raman spectroscopy and similar applications in spectral region from 850 nm to 1.7 μm , where the b-Ge photodiode obtains extremely high EQE. The main difference to the above reported photodiode is that BSI's application is based on different type of substrate that has very low doping density as they need full depletion at used bias voltages to enhance the speed and spectral responsivity, and to reduce the capacitance. The typical operating condition is under reverse bias voltage ~ 50 V to fully deplete the HPGe photodiode. One key challenge during the project was the high leakage current under high reverse bias observed in early batches, which prevented full integration of the bGe photodiode into BSI's Ge modules with the planned time schedule. We confirmed that the high leakage current was not resulting from the nanostructures but from the HPGe device design. During the project this issue was resolved, and in the latest batch of diodes, by applying a $\text{SiO}_2/\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3$ passivation stack to the inactive areas, effectively isolating the active region and suppressing dark current originating from the edges and surrounding inactive regions, the leakage current is finally acceptable for integration into HPGe modules. However, there is still room for further improvement regarding the active area isolation. The distance between anode and guard ring could be further extended, which helps in mitigating the lateral expansion of depletion region under high reverse bias bypassing the channel stopping region, resulting in a lower leakage current under high reverse bias. The module is now in preparation phase using the sensors from the latest batch.

2.2. Technology Applications envisioned after the ATTRACT Project

While in this project we only focused on single-pixel detectors, the developed concept of nanostructured germanium (Ge) has a clear potential to be implemented also for imaging applications, namely for CMOS-based applications such as NIR camera systems, which operate beyond the visible spectrum, typically spanning from 700 to 1700 nm. NIR cameras have a wide range of applications. In medical diagnostics, NIR imaging is already being explored for non-invasive tissue analysis, cancer detection, and real-time surgical guidance. The broad spectral sensitivity and potentially low-noise operation of our Ge photodiodes at cryogenic temperatures can enable detection of smaller and earlier-stage tumors, enhancing diagnostic accuracy and improving patient outcomes. Security and surveillance are critical fields where NIR cameras play a pivotal role, especially under low-light or nighttime conditions, with targeting wavelength range in 900–1600 nm. Enhanced sensitivity and low noise, particularly at cryogenic temperatures, allow for better object detection, facial recognition, and motion tracking in poorly lit environments. This can lead to safer urban spaces and more effective monitoring systems. In agriculture, NIR imaging provides valuable insights into plant health, moisture content, and crop ripeness. Our b-Ge photodiodes' broad EQE from 300–1600 nm enables simultaneous monitoring of visible and NIR spectral features, facilitating multi-parameter analysis such as water stress detection, chlorophyll content estimation, and sugar level monitoring in fruits and vegetables. Similarly, in food quality control, NIR cameras equipped with our sensors could be used to monitor moisture levels in baked goods or identify contaminants during processing. In recycling, they can help sort plastics based on their distinct spectral fingerprints.

In summary, while InGaAs devices currently dominate the NIR photodetector market due to their high detectivity at room temperature, our nanostructured Ge NIR photodiodes offer an appealing alternative — especially when considering cryogenic operation, CMOS integration potential, and wide spectral coverage. As such, they represent a promising path forward for high-performance NIR imaging in medical diagnostics, surveillance, agriculture, and beyond.

3 Commercialization

In the ATTRACT project “Highly efficient IR detection based on black germanium technology (HYGER)” we selected two different utilization paths for the developed nanostructured Ge NIR sensor concept. In the first path the target was to develop highly cost-efficient plain detector chips targeting mainly low or medium profit but very high volume consumer markets. There it is important that the sensor fabrication is fully compatible to CMOS manufacturing lines, which makes it then relatively straightforward to scale up the chip technology even for large semiconductor foundries. Another significant issue is starting wafer cost and material. In the project, the concept was proven functional for bulk Ge wafers and all the tools used for fabrication are common in typical semiconductor factories. Thus, both of the critical requirements were fulfilled. In the second path the target was to develop as high performing detector chips as possible and then integrate them into higher profit low volume expert applications. Here we selected advanced high purity Ge detectors that are needed for spectroscopic applications. High-purity Ge detectors suffer from similar optical and electrical losses (dead layers) as Ge chips, therefore, we believe our developed technologies are key assets for this industry as well.

One of the main key targets was reached in the summer of 2025, when the first photodiodes developed under the project framework reached the market. These devices, based on the novel black germanium technology, are being manufactured and distributed by ElFys Inc., a spin-out company from Aalto University. In other words, ElFys has begun commercial-scale production of the photodiodes, and the first units have already been sold to early-adopting customers. This rapid transition to market exemplifies the industrial viability and readiness of the developed technology.

To our knowledge ElFys Inc. has established a dedicated production line for the black germanium photodiodes, which are being positioned for use in high-performance light detection applications. The commercialization process has been supported by ongoing customer engagement, early validation with prototype users, and focused marketing efforts in photonics and instrumentation sectors. The company is currently scaling up operations to meet anticipated demand, with a particular focus on OEM partnerships in spectroscopy, medical diagnostics, and precision measurement markets.

In parallel with this direct commercialization pathway, integration of the black germanium photodiodes into more complex instruments is also progressing. In collaboration with Baltic Scientific Instruments Ltd., significant advances have been made in incorporating the technology into advanced spectroscopy systems. This integration effort is now in its final phase, with system-level

testing and calibration underway. Full deployment into commercial-grade instruments is expected shortly after the project's completion, marking a major step toward application in scientific instruments.

Looking beyond the ATTRACT timeline, the next commercialization steps are also defined. Licensing agreements and co-development opportunities with larger photonics companies are under active discussion. Further refinement of the technology for CMOS-compatible manufacturing is also being explored. For instance, we have been actively planning joint experiments with the team at Open University (UK) since the kick-off meeting of Phase 1. Open University has vast experience in the design of detector circuits, CCD and CMOS image sensors and their front-end, such as readout electronics, which would perfectly complement our expertise on chip-level technologies. We have also been in direct contact with a CMOS image sensor manufacturer, who has expressed interest in extending their current technology that is based on silicon technology to infrared wavelengths. We have applied funding together from European Space Agency to demonstrate the technology in their industrial CMOS manufacturing lines and study the mass production capabilities. We have also started collaboration with a French partner that has long experience in manufacturing of Ge/SiGe/GeSn thin film devices that are especially interesting in photonic integrated circuits. Their contribution has helped us to extend the application range of black germanium beyond the traditional bulk photodiode technologies. The state of the art photonic integrated circuits indeed already now utilize germanium photodiodes but their sensitivity is still rather limited. In photonic integrated circuits the future market potential is seen to be even bigger than in traditional optoelectronics as it is anticipated that photonic microchips will eventually replace the microelectronic microchips used in integrated circuits. Finally, we are looking into possibilities to integrate the black germanium technology into consumer electronics and portable sensing platforms.

During the project we have successfully progressed from research and development to concrete commercialization. The ATTRACT project has thus laid a robust foundation not only for immediate market entry but also for sustained innovation and business growth in the European photonic semiconductor industry.

4 Conclusions

We have successfully demonstrated a novel nanostructured (black) germanium NIR photodiode that addresses key limitations of traditional Ge photodetectors, namely high surface reflectance, limited quantum efficiency,

and elevated dark current. By integrating conformally passivated black Ge nanostructures and exploiting field-effect passivation schemes, the device achieves near-unity external quantum efficiency across an exceptionally broad spectral range of 300–1600 nm.

Compared to state-of-the-art commercial InGaAs and Ge photodiodes, the b-Ge photodiode demonstrates superior responsivity at the whole spectrum. While room-temperature detectivity remains below that of InGaAs due to higher thermal generation in Ge, temperature-dependent leakage current measurements reveal that this limitation can be mitigated effectively through cooling, resulting in as low leakage current densities as 1.4 nA/cm² and detectivities exceeding 10¹³ Jones.

Beyond the ATTRACT project, the developed photodiodes show strong potential for integration into CMOS-compatible NIR camera systems. Applications in medical diagnostics, such as early-stage tumor detection and real-time imaging, are examples which could benefit from the black germanium photodiode's broadband sensitivity and low noise performance. In security and surveillance, our photodiodes enable high-sensitivity night vision and facial recognition in low-light conditions. In agriculture and food industries, they provide multi-wavelength imaging for assessing crop health, moisture content, and material sorting.

In conclusion, this work establishes a promising new direction for Ge-based NIR photodetectors that leverages nanostructure engineering and advanced surface passivation schemes to overcome conventional performance bottlenecks. The technology's compatibility with existing CMOS processes, scalability, and excellent optoelectronic properties support its use in next-generation photonic systems across medical, scientific, and industrial domains.

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IALL -Integrated Adaptive Liquid crystal Lenses

Maturing liquid crystal technology, from research pilots towards industrial exploitation

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Abstract

The IALL project is all about bringing a ground-breaking adaptive lens technology to a level of maturity, that would make it attractive to the optical or electro-optical industry. Thus, the main objective of the project was to mature the technology sufficiently to generate attractive demonstrators, that could spawn interest and collaboration with the relevant stakeholders. During the project the consortium has presented the technology to 2 of the 5 big tech, has proposed a business plan to a venture capital fund, and been in discussion with one of the major manufacturers of doorbell cameras. The technology has been presented at various scientific and technological conferences and congresses. Most noteworthy were the presentations at SPIE Photonics West and at the World Mobile Congress 2024. Both event have led to the above-mentioned industrial contacts.

Keywords: Adaptive optics; Liquid crystal; Tunable lenses.

1 Technology Description and Benchmark

The IALL project has been extremely successful, reaching practically all the objectives, benchmarks and milestones defined in the proposal, minus the last, *i.e.* the generation of a viable startup.

In the extended 3 years lifetime of the project, all the technical results were met or supplanted by more relevant goals. The consortium has generated a long list of both **high resolution** and **fast switching** lenses that subsequently have been **integrated with cameras**, in **microscopes**, and in **zoom lenses**. This has been presented in invited talks at 5 different international conferences (SPIE x3, OLC, ECLC)

The objective “the integration with machine vision unit” was supplanted by a lens design compatible with wafer level optics (WLO). In WLO an array of lenses (*e.g.* 20 x 20 for a 4” wafer) would be assembled in one process and then be glued onto wafer with a matching array of CMOS chips. Then the combined camera with adaptive focus would be diced in a single process and connected electrically. It was deemed necessary

demonstrator that was presented at three SPIE events, and at the World Mobile Congress 2024 (Fig. 2). Both of these demonstrators were likewise presented at the Attract final conference.

The final demonstrator was the insert compatible with most polarising microscopes and/or telescopes. This lens allows for z-scanning with no moving parts (Fig. 3)

to test the potential for WLO, and thus 0.5-, 1- and 5-mm lenses with only 4 electrodes were designed, manufactured and tested. The lenses have a minimum tunability range of 20 dioptres (Fig. 1).

The consortium fully updated the existing driver developed during the preceding ALL project and made a portable

The three demonstrators have been central in the presentation of the technology to relevant stakeholders. The IALL demonstrators have been shown to venture capital investors, to big tech. companies, and to various smaller and startup companies, aiming at the transfer of the technology.

The IALL lenses have great educational potential and have as such been used in numerous divulgation events, where they have been shown to high school students and general public at 3 open door events at the UPM.

While the IALL technology hasn't, yet, been transferred to an industrial partner, then the IALL project has led to UPM acting as consultant for two EU based startup companies using similar LC technology. Both companies are building production lines that with no, or limited, adaptation could be used for a high throughput IALL lens production.

The drivers developed by ADT are already a commercial product independent of the IALL lenses.

The UPM has been in discussions one potential licensor of the patent with one potential joint venture partner and one venture capital investor, in the ongoing efforts to generate the final transfer of technology.

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Fig. 3: Microscope demonstrator using a 14mm lens

2 Technology Applications

Liquid crystal lenses, like the ones developed within IALL, and the preceding ALL, project have a tremendous potential, being highly adaptable to a wide range of applications requiring low weight, fast tuning range, large area, long lifetime, low power consumption, low voltage. On top of this all at an extremely low unit cost price, well below 10€, in the context of high-volume (>100.000 units per annum) manufacturing.

An analysis of strengths of weaknesses was done early in the project (Table 1).

The major challenge was to identify a mass market, that could bear the relatively high initial investment that a production line in EU would have required. It has been the policy of the IALL inventors, not to embark on establishing a spin-off prior to a client commitment. The ideal case would be the creation of a spin-off as a joint-venture with such a client. Alternatively, a licensing scheme and consultancy agreement could be discussed.

TABLE 1: SWOT analysis of the IALL technology as presented to investors

	PROS	CONS
Internal	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -The best diffractive LC lens technology -Extremely low high-volume cost -Protected technology -Infinite device lifetime -Low voltage, small footprint, radiation hard, low weight 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Predefined tuning range -Residual hazing in high power lenses -No current EU manufacturer of volume LC products -No experience in high throughput fab design in the team -High capital investment
External	<p>VR/AR/XR applications Specific markets where alternatives don't exist:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Full field adaptive eyewear • Portal cameras • Surveillance • Medicare • Aerospace/military • Car lighting 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Overrated VR/AR/XR market - Existing liquid lens solutions already on the market - Similar, more mature, yet inferior LC solutions are available - Adaptive eyewear is being developed

2.1. Technology Applications tested during the ATTRACT Project

A number of demonstrators were developed during the project. Already during the phase 1, a set of lenses were manufactured for the use in ophthalmologic eyewear (spectacles in which the strength of the glasses could be adjusted to the current need of the user). During the second phase, these lenses were vastly improved, and additional demonstrators (microscope, WLO and CCTV) were developed, as commented above.

2.2. Technology Applications envisioned after the ATTRACT Project

The future demonstrators, and applications will very much depend on the industrial contacts that will be established. The consortium is open to all suggestions, and is actively contacting companies related to optics, and imaging. The challenge is to find the mass market, that may justify manufacturing facilities.

3 Commercialization

3.1 Lens commercialization.

The main applications for the IALL lenses are still to be defined. The consortium has developed lenses for web/doorbell cameras, lenses for CCTV cameras, for microscopes and telescopes, for eyewear, and yet the final application is yet to be identified. The consortium will continue looking for a market for the lenses. Even if the lenses have not become a commercial product, then the drivers developed therefore have and the ADT has started a smaller production of them.

The future commercialization route of the IALL lenses will depend on the identification of the mass market, and potential client. Three possible outcomes are considered:

1. Joint venture with a client with mass market presence
2. Licencing of technology to a UPM collaborator (most likely Eye4Sky or Pixieray)
3. Creation of an independent startup
4. Licencing to third party

The consortium is still working towards the first option, while keeping the remaining options in mind.

The consortium will continue to promote the technology in both scientific and commercial contexts. It is the intention to present the new improved demonstrators at both SPIE and MWC events again, as well as in at least one event organized by Optica (Previously known as OSA), to ensure that the relevant stakeholders are kept informed about the project progress.

At the same time the consortium still has pending meetings with major European manufacturers of optical equipment. These meetings will hopefully take place over the next 12 months.

The consortium will also seek to participate in scientific/technological partnerships, aiming at developing industrially relevant lenses for specific, yet undefined, uses. The UPM is already involved in one project in direct continuation of the IALL project, with an industrial partner.

The lenses have been used extensively in the promotion of the UPM in the divulgation contexts, since the underlying principles and technological potential and applications are easily understood by lay persons.

To generate further interest in the lenses specifically and in STEM education in general, the UPM has officially proposed the lenses to be presented in a popular science TV-show (“El Hormiguero”).

To what extent this divulgation effort will lead to a commercial success, is still not given.

The consortium will likewise maintain the major technological companies informed about the lens progress. The consortium has not given up upon the potential of the technology in the context of XR/VR/AR applications, although this market still seems to be very immature.

3.2 LC related consultancy

The lack of European facilities for mass production of LC devices has meant that the UPM is currently consulting actively two EU based SMEs. One of these (Pixieray OY (FI)) employs a technology that is very similar to the IALL technology, to make eyewear. Rather than treating this as a competitor, the UPM is providing consultancy and facilitating the establishment of a Pixieray production line.

Pixieray participated as partner in a Pathfinder Open proposal coordinated by UPM, centered on eyewear based on the IALL lenses manufactured on a flexible substrate.

The UPM is likewise consulting the Spanish startup Eye4Sky in their efforts in setting up a production line of LC devices.

Both of these companies, may become future license holders of the IALL technology if the opportunity arises, and a mass market is identified. It is estimated that both companies future production lines would be able to manufacture the IALL lenses at with a minor additional capital investment (<2M€).

4 Conclusions

The IALL project was the logical progression of the original adaptive liquid crystal lens (ALL) project from the Attract phase 1. It has brought the technology to a readiness level of 7 in most of its proposed implementations. The developed demonstrators ranges from large area lenses with potential applications in telescopes, CCTVs and eyewear to small diameter lenses to be incorporated in microscopes and medicare devices, and hyper powered millimeter sized wafer level optics lenses to combined directly with web camera sensor chips for low cost cameras with active focus. The consortium has presented the technology to big tech, to venture capital and to potential collaborators/licensees in the context of project, collaborations and conference congresses and fairs.

MicroQuaD Attract-Material Science Microscopy with Quantum Detectors

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Abstract

We present the outcomes of *MicroQuaD*, a collaborative project between Single Quantum and PicoQuant, aimed at advancing quantum detection technologies and their integration into microscopy platforms. The project focused on the development of novel single-photon detectors and scalable multichannel time-correlated electronics.

Key outcomes include the successful validation of a Broadband (BB) detection system for material science applications, the design and testing of an UltraBroadband (UBB) SNSPD detector, and the development of the PicoHarp 330 TCSPC system, which demonstrated high performance and scalability. A multielement detector was also engineered and validated.

A highlight of the project was the integration of the MicroTime 100 confocal fluorescence lifetime microscope with the Single Quantum's EOS SNSPD system, demonstrating high sensitivity, excellent signal-to-noise ratio, and exceptional temporal and spatial resolution in the near-infrared (NIR) range as detailed in a peer-reviewed publication.

Parallel commercialization efforts in the project led to the successful launch of new products, accelerating the commercialization of these advanced technologies for both companies.

Keywords: single photon detectors; time correlated electronics; microscopy.

1 Technology Description and Benchmark

There are currently two competing technologies to detect single photons at optical wavelengths in the visible and near-infrared which are based on two different material classes; semiconductors and superconductors. The semiconductor detectors are typically avalanche photodiodes (APD/SPAD), whereas superconductor detectors are based on a meandering nanowire. Superconductor nanowire single photon detectors (SNSPDs) greatly surpass the performances of APDs in detection efficiency, jitter, dark-counts, rise time, dead time, detection rate, and after pulsing, but do require cryogenic cooling ($< 4\text{K}$). The current state of the art for SNSPDs reach detection efficiencies of $>99\%$ with a time resolution better than 20 ps and saturation count rates in the order of 100 MHz. Such state-of-the-art detectors are based on a superconducting nanowire ($\sim 50\text{-}100\text{nm}$) that meander over a length of $\sim 1\text{ mm}$ to match the mode field of a standard optical fiber ($\sim 10\text{ }\mu\text{m}$ in diameter). Producing such long and thin meanders results, however, in a challenging fabrication process and limited fabrication yield.

A third class of single-photon detectors still in use is photomultiplier tubes (PMTs). Though largely superseded by semiconductor and superconducting technologies in several areas like Quantum communications, PMTs remain relevant in certain research environments—particularly those involving microscopy setups and multimode optical fibers, where their large active area and high gain can be advantageous. As part of the MicroQuaD project, one of our key objectives was to integrate SNSPDs into a commercial microscope platform to produce comparative performance data. This benchmarking effort was designed to help engaging research communities still relying on PMTs and to demonstrate the potential benefits of transitioning to superconducting detection technologies. The results, published in a peer-reviewed study, offer quantitative insights and provide a foundation for informed adoption especially for Material science.

The microscope system integration within the MicroQuaD project demonstrated significant improvements in sensitivity and timing precision, as well as a breakthrough in signal-to-noise-ratio (SNR) for the intended application: 2 orders of magnitude improvement when compared to a standard detection technology (PMTs) in that community at near-infrared (NIR) range.

The SNSPDs introduced through this project represent a novel product not previously available on the market. Their unique specifications enable access to new application areas, particularly in NIR microscopy, where they demonstrated clear advantages over existing time-resolved detection systems such as InGaAs-SPADs and photomultiplier tubes.

Additionally, a multi-element detector was successfully developed, offering enhanced response speed and enabling photon number resolution. The TCSPC electronics were realized as an optimized and scalable extension of PicoQuant’s existing platform. By increasing the number of channels and improving timing resolution, the system was able to fully leverage the potential of the interleaved coupled SNSPDs.

These electronics were seamlessly integrated into PicoQuant’s established software suite, supporting both fundamental and advanced analytical workflows. Collectively, these developments played a crucial role in fulfilling MicroQuaD’s overarching goal of advancing quantum-enhanced microscopy technologies.

TABLE 1: Technology benchmark

Technology	Highlight	TRL level
Ultrabroadband detectors	1000nm spectral bandwidth	TRL5
Multielement detectors	8pixels with 14.5ps Jitter and 3dB point of 400MCPS	TRL4
TCSPC electronics	4ch, 8ch and 16ch, scalable	TRL 5-6
Integrated confocal microscopy system+ SNSPD+TCSPC	2 orders of magnitude in SNR w.r.t. PMT standard solution	TRL 7

2 Technology Applications

Here we present some technology applications tested during Attract2.

2.1. Technology Applications tested during the Project

2.1.1. Ultrabroadband SNSPDs

The ultrabroadband SNSPDs developed within this project exhibit a combination of performance characteristics that make them well-suited for advanced photon-counting applications. These include a dark count rate below 200 photons per second, count rates exceeding 50 million counts per second, and timing jitter under 30 picoseconds.

FIG. 1. Characterization results for an ultrabroadband (UBB) SNSPD detector. Left: efficiency vs wavelength, Right: timing Jitter.

The detectors also offer a broad spectral response, covering wavelengths from 800 to 1800 nm, with a spectral bandwidth of 1000 nm, these detectors offer exceptional sensitivity and timing precision across the near-infrared range.

This combination of low noise, high-speed response, and ultrabroad spectral sensitivity makes these detectors uniquely suited for demanding applications where precision, sensitivity, and speed are critical as in quantum optics, time-resolved spectroscopy, and bioimaging. Characterization data, including timing performance and spectral sensitivity, are presented in Figure 1.

FIG. 2. Back scattered imaging of a gold coated design on silicon substrate with: (A)640nm, (B) 1064nm, (C)1855nm, (D) 2001nm laser source. All images were recorded using the same SNSPD.

An example of imaging with the developed ultrabroadband SNSPDs is shown in Figure 2, where a microscopic sample of a gold-coated design on a silicon substrate was imaged using a confocal microscope across multiple wavelengths (640 nm, 1064 nm, 1855 nm, and 2001 nm). The imaging was conducted with a single detector, demonstrating the system's ability to capture high-resolution, wavelength-dependent information across a broad spectral range. This ultrabroadband capability highlights the detector's versatility and exceptional performance in imaging applications, where precise, high-sensitivity detection is required for materials characterization and surface analysis.

2.1.2. Multielement SNSPDs

Multielement interleaved superconducting nanowire single-photon detectors (SNSPDs) introduce advanced functionalities and significantly enhanced performance metrics. By segmenting the detector's active area into multiple individually addressable pixels, these devices achieve superior photon number resolution. This spatial multiplexing architecture also enables substantially higher count rates, effectively mitigating limitations imposed by the dead time of conventional single-element meandered detectors.

These capabilities have already attracted interest across several domains. In quantum key distribution (QKD) and long-distance laser communication, the high count rate is particularly advantageous. Meanwhile, applications in photonic quantum computing and quantum source characterization benefit from the improved photon number resolution.

FIG. 3. Test results for a 8 pixels interleaved SNSPD: (a) Single element timing jitter. (b) Photon number resolution capabilities. (c) Overall system detection efficiency as a function of the total count rate.

To validate these advantages, 8-pixel interleaved SNSPDs were fabricated and experimentally tested. The results demonstrate clear performance gains over standard single-pixel detectors. In addition to maintaining high detection efficiency and precise timing resolution, the devices achieved a 3 dB efficiency point at 400 MHz and maintained a fidelity above 0.5 for photon number states up to six.

2.1.1. TCSPC and SNSPD integration in Microscopy

The combination of the MicroTime 100 upright confocal fluorescence lifetime microscope with a Single Quantum EOS Superconducting Nanowire Single-Photon Detector (SNSPD) system was demonstrated [1] as a powerful tool for photophysical research and applications, especially in material science, yielding spatial and temporal information on a wide range of samples. High sensitivity, excellent signal-to-noise ratio as well as high temporal resolution combined with confocal spatial resolution in the near-infrared range (NIR) spectral range were demonstrated. The performance of different SNSPD designs for time-resolved photoluminescence measurements and imaging on different Cu(InGa)Se₂ (CIGS) devices was compared with that of a standard NIR-photomultiplier tube (NIR-PMT).

FIG. 4. TRPL images of weakly emitting CIGS. Intensity and time resolved images(a,b) and PL decays acquired at two different ROIs of the sample (c,d) measured with the NIR-PMT (a,c) and multimode fiber coupled SNSPD (b,d). Image taken from [1]

2.2. Technology Applications envisioned after the ATTRACT Project

Building on the successes of the MicroQuaD project, both Single Quantum (SQ) and PicoQuant (PQ) are committed to advancing their respective technologies and the implementation of quantum detectors in microscopy to meet emerging scientific and industrial demands.

SQ will continue the development of multielement superconducting nanowire single-photon detectors (SNSPDs), with a focus on (i) increasing their dynamic range (count rates) to ensure compatibility with a wider range of analytes and imaging targets, and (ii) improving their photon number resolution enabling new PNR-based microscopy techniques.

PQ will further scale its multichannel time-correlated electronics, expanding the capabilities of TCSPC systems to support increasingly high-throughput experiments. This will facilitate sophisticated data acquisition strategies across a range of disciplines.

Together, these advancements will drive more precise quantum-enhanced measurements in complex systems and dynamic imaging environments. The continued innovation from both partners is expected to uncover previously unattainable insights in applications including:

- **Material Science:** Enabling better understanding of photophysical properties and ultrafast dynamics of advanced materials.
- **Bioimaging:** Supporting high-resolution techniques such as fluorescence lifetime imaging microscopy (FLIM) and Förster resonance energy transfer (FRET) for a better grasp of cellular and molecular dynamics.
- **Quantum-enhanced microscopy techniques:** The implementation of quantum detectors with PNR capabilities allows for faster adoption of emerging imaging techniques based on quantum phenomena such as quantum correlation and PNR. [2]

Beyond microscopy, the developed SNSPDs and TCSPCs are expected to impact other fields including:

- **Quantum Computing:** Providing the detection precision and timing accuracy required for scalable quantum information processing.
- **Quantum Sensing:** Enhancing sensitivity and resolution in next-generation sensors for fundamental research and applied technologies.
- **Secure Optical and Quantum communication:** Allowing for high-rate secure data transmission with reduced error rates and through increased distances.

These developments will not only extend the reach of quantum-enhanced microscopy but also position SQ and PQ at the forefront of innovation in photon-based measurement science.

3 Commercialization

The transfer of prototypes to marketable products is a standard but complex process that both SQ and PQ have successfully demonstrated multiple times in the past. The products developed in ATTRACT fit seamlessly with the existing portfolios and business interests of both SMEs. Therefore, marketing of the new developments is done mostly through existing channels (website, conferences, direct marketing to existing customer base, etc.), which is much smoother and efficient than entering completely new market segments.

Concrete steps have been taken to bring MicroQuaD innovations to market. Both Single Quantum and PicoQuant have actively promoted the collaboration through dedicated website¹ features and targeted outreach, raising visibility and interest across their customer bases.

Single Quantum successfully sold three UltraBroadband SNSPD detection systems, with one sale setting a new benchmark (just four months from development to sale), demonstrating rapid product readiness and market demand. Furthermore, SQ has received multiple inquiries (>5) for multielement detectors.

¹ <https://www.singlequantum.com/solutions/imaging-line/>
<https://www.picoquant.com/scientific/product-studies/microtime-100-snspsds-coupling>.

PicoQuant advanced its commercialization strategy for time-correlated single-photon counting (TCSPC) systems by launching the scalable 4-channel PicoHarp 330. Building on this, the HydraHarp 500 platform will soon support 8- and 16-channel configurations, with a modular design that allows stacking multiple 16-channel units—enabling systems with great scalability potential. This flexible architecture, combined with competitive pricing, significantly enhances market viability in a sector that demands both performance and scalability.

Future steps:

Single Quantum (SQ) and PicoQuant will continue commercializing their respective new products while actively exploring joint opportunities to strengthen market outreach. Complete microscope systems and upgrade modules will be targeted primarily at academic researchers in the life and materials sciences, with anticipated interest extending into adjacent domains such as medical research and industrial R&D. These offerings can be distributed globally through PicoQuant’s established international network of distributors [<https://www.picoquant.com/contact/distributors>], ensuring broad accessibility across research institutions.

The newly developed superconducting nanowire single-photon detectors (SNSPDs) will also be commercialized worldwide. Single Quantum has already achieved significant market penetration, with more than 300 high performance detection systems installed across Europe, North America, Asia, and Australia. This global footprint is supported by a combination of in-house sales engineers and specialized resellers operating in key regions such as Asia and North America, enabling rapid deployment of new products. By leveraging the strong reputations of both SMEs within their respective markets, the collaboration aims to expand customer reach and identify new opportunities through complementary sales expertise.

4 Conclusions

The MicroQuaD project successfully advanced the integration of quantum detection technologies into microscopy platforms, achieving multiple technical and commercial milestones. A Broadband detection system was assembled and validated at both Single Quantum and PicoQuant, reaching Technology Readiness Level 5 (TRL 5). This system was further validated through material science applications, culminating in a peer-reviewed

publication that demonstrated its effectiveness in time-resolved photoluminescence mapping.

The UltraBroadband (UBB) SNSPD detector was designed, tested, and validated, also achieving TRL 5. Its performance in the near-infrared range marked a significant step forward in single-photon detection capabilities. In parallel, the PicoHarp 330 multichannel TCSPC system was validated at TRL 5–6, confirming its scalability and suitability for high-throughput photon timing applications.

A multielement SNSPD detector was designed, fabricated, and validated at TRL 4, laying the groundwork for future innovations in photon-number resolution and interpixel correlation. These developments collectively enhance the precision and versatility of quantum-enabled microscopy.

From a commercialization standpoint, the project demonstrated remarkable agility, with the UBB detector reaching its first sale within just four months of development—setting a new benchmark for time-to-market in this domain. These outcomes not only validate the technical feasibility of the MicroQuaD innovations but also underscore their readiness for deployment in research and industry.

5 Acknowledgements

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In-situ monitoring of natural gas mixtures

PiPe4.0 ATTRACT Phase-2 Project

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Abstract

The PiPe4.0 project, funded by the ATTRACT Consortium, addresses the escalating need for new measurement paradigms in the evolving gas sector by developing innovative laser-based and distributed sensors for on-line natural gas monitoring within pipeline networks. This initiative is driven by trends in decarbonization and the integration of alternative gas types, including biomethane and hydrogen. The system comprises two interconnected units: the Gas Monitoring Unit (GMU) and the Distributed Sensing Unit (DSU).

The GMU functions as the primary analytical instrument, employing optical Raman spectroscopy to comprehensively measure gas parameters, such as composition and thermodynamics properties, at critical points like injection and gas distribution cabins. It is designed for reliable, fast, cost-effective, and consumable-free operation across a wide range of environmental conditions. The DSU is a self-powered system that generates energy from pipeline thermal gradients to measure selected parameters, such as temperature and CO₂ concentration, enabling a distributed sensing approach.

Both units have undergone industrial validation in two pilot plants: a natural gas pressure reduction cabin and a biogas generation facility. The GMU consistently meets the OIML R 140 Class A standard for Heating Value accuracy (within $\pm 0.5\%$) and repeatability (0.2%) across a -20°C to 50°C

¹ Request of project information to luca.poletto@cnr.it

temperature range. The DSU, with ATEX certification, has successfully demonstrated autonomous sensing and wireless data transmission capabilities in operational field environments. This integrated architecture aims to establish a new measurement approach for enhanced fuel gas distribution and sensing.

Keywords: Natural gas; composition measurements; thermodynamics properties; Raman spectroscopy; distributed sensing; biogas, hydrogen; energy harvesting; on-line measurements; remote monitoring.

1 Technology Description and Benchmark

The PiPe4.0 project, funded in the framework of the ATTRACT Consortium [1], is focused on developing innovative laser-based sensors and distributed sensors for on-line measurements on Natural Gas (NG) within pipeline networks. The project responds to the growing demand for innovative measurement paradigms in the evolving gas sector, prompted by decarbonization efforts and the increasing integration of alternative gases such as biogas, biomethane, and hydrogen. The project responds to the growing demand for innovative measurement paradigms in the evolving gas sector, prompted by decarbonization efforts and the increasing integration of alternative gases such as biogas, biomethane, and hydrogen.

The Pipe4.0 system is designed to assess two principal challenges associated with in situ monitoring in NG distribution networks through a system consisting of two interconnected units:

- Gas Monitoring Unit (GMU), functions as the primary analytical instrument. Its role is to conduct a comprehensive measurement of gas parameters, such as composition and thermodynamics properties, at specific points like injection cabins or gas distribution cabins, through optical Raman spectroscopy. It is designed to be reliable, fast, and cost-effective, capable of operating across a wide range of environmental conditions characteristic of gas pipelines, without necessitating consumable supplies. The GMU's purpose is to furnish detailed gas analysis at key monitoring points.
- Distributed Sensing Unit (DSU): a system capable of generating energy from the thermal gradient between NG pipelines and the surrounding environment. Once sufficient energy has been harvested, the system can measure selected NG parameters (e.g. temperature, CO₂ concentration) and transmit the data to a server. This enables a distributed, self-powered sensing approach for monitoring key parameters across the entire network.

The PiPe4.0 final implementation is designed to be demonstrated and validated under real operating conditions through on-site deployment in two distinct pilot plants, showcasing the industrial applicability of both the GMU and DSU:

- An injection cabin for hydrogen-enriched NG in the distribution network.
- A biogas generation plant for electric energy production.

The proposed architecture is intended to establish a new measurement paradigm within the field of fuel gas distribution and sensing by integrating detailed analysis at crucial points with distributed monitoring across the network.

1.1 GMU description and benchmark

Historically, the NG network has been considered as a structure relying solely on gas supplied from extraction points. Nowadays, the variability of the mixtures flowing through the networks is continuously increasing. This is the consequence of processes such as the direct injection of biomethane, re-gasified LNG and the forecasted injection of hydrogen to form Hydrogen-enriched Natural Gas (HNG). The variations are generally localized around the areas of the injection points, thus leading to different mixtures qualities across the entire network; the quality control analysis is focused on measuring the mixtures compositions to calculate the thermodynamics properties. The mixtures are primarily composed by methane (80% - 100%), ethane (1% – 10%), propane (0.1% - 5%), butanes (0% - 2%), pentanes or heavier hydrocarbons (0% - 1%), non-flammable gases such as nitrogen and carbon dioxide are also present (0% - 3%). Traces of inert gases (Helium and Argon) can be found in its composition and, as introduced above, hydrogen (0% - 20%) is starting to be injected depending on the national regulations.

Since the thermodynamics properties of the NG directly affects its economic value, the NG sector increasingly requires distributed sampling of the quality of the mixtures that are transported, distributed and delivered to the final customers. The final cost accounted to the users is directly dependent on both the quality and the quantity of the NG consumed. The primary thermodynamic parameter used in the quality classification of a combustion mixture is the Heating Value (HV). Referring to a particular combustion mixture, this parameter expresses the amount of energy in form of heat released by the combustion of a specified volume or specific mass of the mixture. It is possible to determine the HV by direct measurements or by mathematical calculation starting from the knowledge of the mixture composition. The standard ISO 6976:2016 [2] provides all the computational steps useful to the HV (and other

important physical and thermodynamic parameters) calculation starting from the sample chemical composition.

The NG sector has also established specific standards to define the performance requirements (accuracy, repeatability, etc.) and legally compliance of quality analyzers that can be used for fiscal metering and custody transfer. Among the most important references, the OIML R 140 [3] outlines the metrological and technical requirements for instrumentations used in the measurement of gaseous fuels. In particular, it defines accuracy classes, performance requirements and testing procedures for gas analyzers used in trade and custody transfer of gaseous fuels. The NG sector demands for OIML class A instrumentation; in terms of HV calculation, this is mainly reflected in the compliance of the following equations:

$$(|HV_{\text{meas}} - HV_{\text{real}}|) / HV_{\text{real}} < 0.50 \%, \text{ accuracy} \quad (1)$$

$$(HV_{\text{max}} - HV_{\text{min}}) / HV_{\text{mean}} < 0.20 \%, \text{ repeatability} \quad (2)$$

Where HV_{meas} is the measured HV, HV_{real} is the certified HV. HV_{max} , HV_{min} and HV_{mean} are the maximum, minimum and average HV measured by an instrument under the same experimental conditions (operative temperature and analyzed sample).

Others relevant standards are: (i) ISO 10723, which provides the methodology for evaluating the performance of on-line systems used to monitor the composition of NG. (ii) MID 2014/32/EU, provides the EU's legal framework for approving and certifying measuring instruments, compliance is required for CE marking and market access within the EU. (iii) ATEX 2014/34/EU ensures that measuring instrumentation used in NG pipelines is designed and certified to prevent ignition in potentially explosive atmospheres.

Nowadays, Gas Chromatography (GC) analysis represent the reference technique for determining NG composition and thermodynamic properties (HV) in applications where high accuracy, traceability and compliance with standards are required. The commercial GC analyzers comply with the OIML R 140 class A requirements. The GCs separate the mixture components through the interaction with their heated columns and then measuring each component one by one via non-specific detectors such as TCDs. They are the benchmark technology for NG quality measurement in fiscal applications, particularly in cases where real-time, on-line analyses are required over the gas trade chain [4-6]. On-line GC systems are employed directly in-the-field; they automatically extract a gas sample, which is subsequently conditioned (depressurized, thermalized and diluted with a gas carrier), injected into the instrument at regular intervals and then vented to atmosphere. In on-line applications, they are calibrated to measure hydrocarbons, up to pentanes,

carbon dioxide and nitrogen. These instruments are also capable to measure hydrogen in HNG applications by the addition of a supplementary column. The thermodynamics properties (HV) are calculated based on the measured composition. Even though their performance is very high and they serve as reference instruments by providing self-standing operations; these systems can be relatively complex, requiring rather high initial costs, constant gas carrier supply and periodic maintenance. Given their sensibility, they also require for periodical recalibrations with certified reference gases. Usually, the sample is dispersed in environment after the measurement.

Several other approaches are employed in NG quality analysis, for example: (i) inferential techniques measure some physical parameters, such as sound propagation speed in the mixture, to estimate a simplified composition. (ii) transducers sensors, such as electrochemical sensors, change their physical characteristic when they directly interact with the sample. These approaches suffer cross-talk and hysteresis problems and are not taken into consideration for precision in-the-field analyses.

IR spectroscopy is characterized by a high level of accuracy in hydrocarbons content determination. However, measurements on diatomic molecules is very difficult [7]. It is employed in NG leakage detection, process control or carbon dioxide measurements.

Raman Spectroscopy (RS) represents a suitable choice for NG and HNG analysis. This technique measures the molecular composition based on vibrational, and rotational in the case of gases, energy shifts when molecules scatter the light emitted from a laser. RS is a well-established and widely accepted technique in the analysis of liquids and solids, several instruments are commercially available, ready to the use or adaptable to specific user requirements. However, when applied to the analysis of gaseous samples, the technique faces significant challenges due to the inherently weak Raman signals. As a result, several technical adaptations and optimizations are necessary to enable its effective use in this domain. Despite these limitations, recent advances in signal processing, optical design and components, and detector sensitivity have significantly improved the feasibility of applying RS to gaseous sample analysis. These developments have opened new possibilities for its deployment in real-time and in-field applications. In the case of NG analysis, RS intrinsically is multiple gas sensitive, it is capable of measuring simultaneously hydrocarbons from methane to butanes, carbon dioxide, oxygen and hydrogen by using a single laser source and one detection system. Moreover, it performs fast measurements without the need for sample preparation or consumables. Its applicability has already been demonstrated in scientific laboratories with high accurate results [8-10]. It has already been employed in real-time and in-situ measurements analysis in LNG plants with high level of accuracy [11]. Its applicability to on-line NG and HNG

measurements had remained a key breakthrough yet to be achieved with this technology. Before the ATTRACT Pipe4.0 project, no commercially available OIML R 140 class A instrumentation for NG mixtures based on RS existed on the market. In particular, this applies when considering operating temperatures ranging from -20°C to 50°C. Previous Raman-based NG instrumentation was designed to be used within temperature-controlled laboratory environments and did not ensure operability under class A conditions.

Compared to other analysis devices, the developed technology allows the reinjection of the analyzed gas without any greenhouse gas emission into atmosphere. This makes the instrument already compatible with the European regulation 2024/1787.

This device is protected by the following patents:

Patented Italy 102019000006954 and EP 3 748 339 B1

Pending Italy 102024000002328 and EP 25152840.2

1.2 DSU description and benchmark

Monitoring gas pipelines poses two main challenges: powering remote sensors without wired supply and ensuring equipment is safe in explosive environments. Thus, self-powered IoT devices, able to safely harvest ambient energy to avoid battery changes, are being a key approach for novel intelligent gas distribution networks. Present energy harvesting solutions being developed include thermoelectric (using pipe temperature differences), solar photovoltaics and mechanical energy (vibration or flow).

The Distributed Sensing Unit (DSU) developed within the PiPe4.0 project is a self-powered system designed to wirelessly monitor NG pipelines. It primarily consists of a Thermoelectric Energy Harvesting (EH) unit, a Low Power Management and Communication Board and an interface for low-power sensors. A Resistive Temperature Detector (RTD) was chosen for the final implementation for environmental measurements. The EH unit uses an array of thermoelectric generator (TEG) modules to convert the temperature difference (ΔT) between the warmer NG inside the pipeline and the cooler ambient environment into electrical energy. This harvested energy is then conditioned by the power management board to supply the sensor and enable wireless data transmission. Key components of the DSU, specifically the EH unit and the power management board, have undergone successful conformity of ATEX equipment for category 3G-(zone-2).

Within the broad domain of thermoelectric harvesting, the PiPe4.0 DSU technology employs a passive approach, relying on the existing thermal gradient. This contrasts with active thermal harvesting, such as Parker Hannifin's TEC-8 Thermo-Electric Charger, which burns a small flow of NG to generate 6.5 to 7.3 W, and is rated for Class I Div 2 hazardous locations

[12]. On the other hand, passive systems typically yield lower power but can operate continuously if a ΔT is present. For instance, Fraunhofer's BlueTEG achieves 200 μW from a 2 K temperature difference [13]. The PiPe4.0 DSU's EH unit, with 96 TEG modules, demonstrated capability to generate open circuit voltages of 3.26V and short circuit currents of 15.4mA, with a temperature of $\sim 8.8^\circ\text{C}$ in field conditions, although consistent power delivery was heavily influenced by environmental factors like airflow.

More mature alternatives like solar photovoltaics are available, with vendors such as JCE Energy providing ATEX-certified panels and complete systems including batteries for Zone 1/2 sites, with powers ranging from 120 to 960 W [14]. Vibration or flow energy harvesting represents another potential solution, although it remains less developed and less commonly used in gas infrastructure. This is largely due to the typically low levels of mechanical perturbation associated with gas flow, which limits the available kinetic energy to drive such systems effectively. Academic prototypes using piezoelectric strips attached to gas pipes have generated up to 2.18mW [15]. While promising for ultra-low-power sensors, commercial, ATEX-certified solutions for pipelines are less prevalent compared to thermal or solar.

The PiPe4.0 DSU is thus benchmarked as a passive thermoelectric harvesting system, specifically developed and tested for retrofitting onto existing NG pipelines. Its ATEX certification for the EH unit and power management board is a critical feature for its target application.

2 Technology Applications

2.1 Technology Applications tested during the ATTRACT Project

Given the natural division of the Pipe4.0 project into the developing of two systems, the technical descriptions reported in this chapter are accordingly divided into two sections, referring to either the GMU or the DSU.

2.1.1 Gas Monitoring Unit Technology Applications tested during the ATTRACT Project

The GMU was designed to meet the key requirements of the industrial sector while preserving the performance of a scientific instrument. This resulted in a scientific and engineering challenge involving several stages of hardware upgrades and the implementation of analytical software aimed at compensating for any performance losses.

An explanatory scheme of the GMU is reported in figure 1. The radiation from laser source (a) is focused into a gas cell (c) using a focusing lens (b). The beam exits the gas cell and it is then terminated on a beam dump (d). The gas

cell adopts technological arrangements required to safely operate up to a pressure of 17 absolute bar (bara). The radiation scattered by the sample within the gas cell is collected with a 90° geometry. The collecting optics consist of two achromatic lenses (e, g) that recreate a rescaled (x0.5) image of the laser beam inside the cell onto the focal plane of a diffraction grating spectrometer (h). The Rayleigh scattering, being at the same wavelength of the exciting laser, is rejected through an interference filter (f) placed in the region between the two collecting lenses, where the light is collimated.

FIG. 1. Schematic view of the Raman-based sensing unit

This design was progressively optimized throughout the stages of the project [16-19], culminating in the current version which employs a laser diode emitting in the blue region (455 nm) operated at fixed temperature by the use of a thermoelectric cooler. Unlike other more commonly used sources (DPSS Nd:YAG 532 nm), laser diodes allow operation within the temperature range required by the NG sector (-20°C to 50°C). These sources are characterized by a relatively broad spectral emission (FWHM \approx 2 nm), which results in broader spectral features. Extensive work has been carried out to compensate for the spectral broadening and maintain accuracy levels compliant with OIML class A standards. A picture of the latest GMU version is reported in figure 2.

The calibration of the GMU constitutes an indispensable initial phase. Its fundamental purpose is to establish a comprehensive library of reference Raman spectra corresponding to the individual target gas species. These calibrated spectra are subsequently employed in fitting routines to accurately

determine the molecular composition of complex gas mixtures. Knowledge of the precise composition then allows the calculation of key parameters such as the HV.

The calibration process involves acquiring Raman emission spectra from certified gas bottles containing the pure components or specific binary mixtures of the relevant gases, including methane, ethane, propane, butanes, nitrogen, carbon dioxide, and hydrogen. To acquire calibration spectra, the molecules are pressurized to known pressures inside the gas cell, and their Raman spectra are recorded. The acquired data undergoes post-processing, including background noise subtraction and normalization for gas pressure, molecular concentration, laser optical power, and camera integration time. Calibration is conducted at room temperature. Representative calibration spectra are shown in Figure 3.

FIG. 2. GMU latest version.

FIG. 3. GMU calibration spectra

Before field tests and certification phases, the GMU underwent a crucial laboratory validation process within a climatic chamber. The primary motivation for this phase was to characterize the instrument's metrological performance under the operative temperature range. The goal was to demonstrate the GMU's capability to provide accurate and repeatable measurements using a single calibration set. The validation methodology involved positioning GMU prototypes inside a climatic chamber capable of reaching temperatures from -20°C to 50°C . Various certified gas mixtures, representative of typical NG and HNG compositions, were tested. A custom software algorithm was implemented to compensate for any instrumental drift in temperature. The results successfully confirmed that the GMU consistently meets the requirements of the OIML R 140 Class A standard for both HV accuracy and repeatability. HV percentage errors remained within the $\pm 0.5\%$ limit across the full -20°C to 50°C temperature range and for all tested mixtures.

The results on three NG and two HNG mixtures are reported in Table 1. Some experimental spectra are shown in Figure 4. The results, in terms of HV calculation accuracy, are shown in Figure 5.

FIG. 4. Experimental spectra acquired during thermal characterization.

FIG. 5. HV accuracy percentage errors.

TABLE 1: Tested mixtures compositions

	NG1	NG2	NG3	HNG1	HNG2
CH₄	85.100	93.116	99.481	91.808	74.155
C₂H₆	9.000	4.108	0.039	4.122	3.321
C₃H₈	1.519	0.708	0.009	0.814	0.659
nC₄H₁₀	0.209	0.121	0.001	0.137	0.110

iC₄H₁₀	0.142	0.184	0.003	0.117	0.095
N₂	2.472	1.016	0.402	1.279	1.031
CO₂	1.426	0.629	0.055	0.645	0.523
H₂	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.996	20.040
BAL	0.132	0.118	0.010	0.082	0.066
HV[kJ/m³]	40202.8	39137.1	37636.0	38746.7	33594.6

Field installations of GMU prototypes were conducted in real operational environments, including NG pressure reduction station, a biogas production plant, and the first Italian HNG injection pilot plant. The latter is of particular interest as it represents the first feasibility test in Italy to use HNG in residential installations. The tests involved the use of HNG with hydrogen concentration of 2% and 5% [20]. Installed in ATEX certified boxes and connected directly to existing gas flow lines these deployments represented typical in-the-field scenarios without additional climate control or constant human supervision. Results over time at NG station demonstrated HV measurements aligning well with periodic reference GC analysis, consistently meeting OIML R 140 Class A accuracy and repeatability requirements over several months of continuous operation. Biogas testing validated the GMU's capability to measure key components like methane, carbon dioxide, and nitrogen, showing alignment with plant sensors. Data from the H2NG injection site also demonstrate the applicability of the GMU in real scenarios. These tests also served as long-term stability checks, as they extended over a period of up to 11 months of continuous operations. A picture of the GMU installed in a NG pressure reduction facility and the daily average HVs measurements carried out using the GMU, together with the reference measurements provided by the plant operator, are shown in Figure 6.

a)

b)

FIG. 6. a) GMU installation in NG pressure reduction facility. b) GMU HV results vs reference measurements.

2.1.2 DSU Technology Applications tested during the ATTRACT Project

The DSU developed within the PiPe4.0 project was subjected to field testing under real operational conditions to validate its design robustness and functional performance in powering sensor systems deployed on NG pipelines. Two primary field deployments were conducted, one at INRETE (Forlimpopoli, Italy) and another at the Greenway biogas facility (Bertiolo, Italy). However, since at the INRETE installation had relatively small temperature gradient ($\Delta T \sim 3.5^\circ\text{C}$; Fig. 7), one decided to focus on the deployment site at the Greenway biogas energy production station. In this case, the DSU was installed on a vertical DN200 pipe near a gas-powered engine. This site presented a more promising average ΔT of around 8.8°C , yielding an open-circuit voltage of approximately 3.26 V. Despite the higher available voltage, the initial deployment with a NDIR CO_2 sensor failed to establish reliable communication over several months. This was attributed to the sensor's high-power demand and unnecessary power use of the microcontroller. Recognizing these challenges, in July 2024, the sensor was replaced with a low-power ATEX certified PT1000 RTD temperature sensor, significantly reducing the energy budget required for sensing. Accordingly, a smaller capacitor was used in the power management board, which made it easier to reach the threshold for discharge. Independent data loggers were used to monitor ambient and gas temperatures, and an analog-to-digital converter was installed to continuously track the EH unit's output voltage, providing crucial diagnostic information. The EH unit was also optimized to improve

airflow over the heat sinks, aiming to enhance heat dissipation and maintain a more effective ΔT across the TEGs.

FIG. 7. DSU installation at INRETE (Forlimpopoli, Italy)

In March 2025, the microcontroller setup underwent significant revisions. These included disabling the microcontroller's debugger to reduce quiescent current, optimizing power delivery to the sensor, refining ADC configurations for better accuracy, and minimizing data transmission packet size and active time.

FIG. 8. DSU installation at Greenway (Bertiolo, Italy), after the optimizations and changes.

Following these optimizations, the DSU at the Greenway facility successfully established wireless communication. Data transmitted after the July 2024 changes showed the system's capability to measure ambient temperature using

the RTD and transmit data when sufficient energy was harvested. Long-term analysis revealed that successful measurement instances were strongly correlated with wind/airflow, which aids heat dissipation from the TEG cold side. The final optimized setup demonstrated a significant boost in performance and reliability, with the average number of measurements per 15-minute interval increasing from 32 to 82, and a mean absolute error of 1.47°C. The overall success rate (at least one measurement per 15 min) increased from 0.4% to 3.1%. These tests validated the DSU's capability for autonomous operation under favorable conditions and highlighted critical design considerations for thermal energy harvesting systems in dynamic environments, namely the necessity for sufficient airflow, along with low power design and sensor selection.

FIG. 9. Data dashboard showing some acquired DSU data from the Greenway installation.

2.2 Technology Applications envisioned after the ATTRACT Project

The GMU is an instrument capable of measuring the composition of gaseous molecules that are pressurized within its gas cell. Its analysis algorithm has been specifically developed to efficiently characterize NG. In addition to measuring NG directly on transmission and distribution lines, the GMU can also be employed as a process control tool during blending operations, providing real-time data on the mixture and enabling feedback-based correction of the input streams.

Within the scope of fuel gas applications, the system can be readily adapted to various scenarios such as shale gas extraction analysis, mud logging, and more generally, other phases of petrochemical processing. Future adaptations of the instrument may include applications such as flue gas analysis from metallurgical industries or combustion products, as well as the characterization of gaseous products from biomass or industrial waste pyrolysis. Following its commercialization in the NG sector and subsequent market deployment, potential demands will be evaluated in order to address new application requirements.

3 Commercialization

The results obtained from the on-field tests have provided evidence of two different levels of maturity for the two systems. On one side, GMU has achieved the performance required to be proposed as a metering instrument for combustible gases, in terms of accuracy, repeatability, working temperature range, working pressure range. The unit is fully certified for ATEX operation, OIML metrology, EM compatibility, therefore ready for commercialization, with a TRL level of 8/9. On the other side, the DSU has reached a TRL of 6/7. Its core energy harvesting system and associated power management board are ATEX Zone 2 certified. The integrated DSU, including these certified components and an RTD sensor, successfully demonstrated autonomous sensing and wireless data transmission in an operational field environment. While functional, consistent performance is influenced by environmental factors impacting power generation and thus sensor selection. Further design enhancements to improve reliability and overall performance are identified but would necessitate a new ATEX certification.

Given the different TRL levels reached by the two units, the commercialization efforts have been mainly concentrated on the GMU.

The partner mainly involved in the pathway to market is Pietro Fiorentini S.p.A., a leading Italian industrial group with a longstanding presence in the global energy sector. Founded in 1940, at present the group has ≈2.800 employees and 40 international offices. It is specialized in the development of technologies for the transportation, treatment, measurement, and distribution of NG. Headquartered in Arcugnano (Vicenza, Italy), Pietro Fiorentini operates across numerous international markets, with a broad portfolio of solutions that span the entire NG supply chain.

Today Pietro Fiorentini S.p.A. (<https://www.fiorentini.com/it/>) is one of the main industrial companies in the North East of Italy reaching over 100

countries around the world. In 2024, the Group's consolidated turnover reached around 500 million euros.

The Group is organized into three main Strategic Business Units (SBUs):

- **Oil & Gas Solutions:** deals with engineered solutions for the design, construction, installation and maintenance of plants in the energy sector, both onshore and offshore, for the extraction, treatment, storage and transport of natural gas and oil.
- **Gas & Water Network Solutions:** provides solutions for the regulation and custody transfer measurement of gas and water, also developing solutions compatible with biomethane and hydrogen.
- **Renewables Solutions:** focuses on the engineering and supply of plants for the production of biomethane, hydrogen and power-to-X. The Group supplies biogas upgrading plants, biomethane injection stations, reverse flow plants, liquid biomethane metrology, mixing stations, power-to-gas and biomethanation systems. In addition, thanks to the acquisition of Hyter S.r.l., the Group is now able to offer solutions for the generation of hydrogen through electrolysis.

The Group boasts 21 production plants (10 in Italy, 11 abroad). Each plant specializes in the production of specific product lines. In the early 2000s, Pietro Fiorentini adopted the logic of lean production in order to optimize production spaces, reduce waste and simplify production processes as much as possible. The lean revolution has also led to a rethinking of production and the abandonment of production for large batches. Thanks to this new approach, it has been possible on the one hand to significantly reduce stocks and warehousing and on the other hand to offer greater production flexibility to customers. Today, the Group is constantly looking for methodologies to achieve new goals by monitoring internal processes with a view to continuous improvement of each phase of work.

The company's technological offering includes advanced systems for pressure regulation, filtration, and metering, as well as a growing focus on digital infrastructure, including smart metering, remote monitoring, and automation platforms. In recent years, Pietro Fiorentini has significantly expanded its commitment to innovation, particularly in areas aligned with the energy transition, such as hydrogen integration, green gas monitoring, and the digitalization of gas networks.

From a technological perspective, the company actively integrates embedded systems, cloud-based platforms, and IoT-enabled devices, all designed to support real-time control, predictive maintenance, and compliance with

metrological standards (e.g., MID – Measuring Instruments Directive). Special emphasis is placed on cybersecurity, data traceability, and scalability, which are essential requirements for modern utility-grade instrumentation.

Within this context, the GMU represents a strategic technological evolution for Pietro Fiorentini. Originally conceived as a research-oriented prototype, the GMU has undergone a robust engineering process that has transformed it into a fully industrialized platform. It is designed for the continuous, in-line monitoring of gas composition and quality, using advanced optical sensing techniques, such as RS.

Several key characteristics make the GMU highly compatible with the company's existing infrastructure:

- It is a compact, modular unit capable of operating in field conditions, including those typical of industrial gas installations.
- The GMU is network-enabled, facilitating seamless integration into existing telemetry and SCADA systems, and enabling real-time data acquisition and remote diagnostics.
- Its software architecture incorporates best practices in industrial software engineering, including requirement traceability, version control, automated testing, and compliance with cybersecurity standards relevant to legal metrology in internet-connected environments.

The GMU fits naturally into Pietro Fiorentini's broader technological framework, serving as a valuable addition to its portfolio of intelligent field devices. Its ability to provide high-resolution, continuous measurements of gas quality parameters not only enhances operational transparency, but also supports compliance with evolving regulatory and fiscal metrology requirements.

Moreover, the implementation of robust, user-friendly interfaces—both for internal technical staff and for end-users—ensures that the system is easy to operate, maintain, and configure in various deployment scenarios. These characteristics make the GMU a scalable and adaptable solution, ideally suited for integration across the company's widespread network of installations.

As real numbers showing the market potentials, we comment here on the Italian status. The resolution of 23 November 2021, 512/2021/R/gas, requires an on-site gas analysis (including hydrogen concentration) in pressure reduction and metering stations (PRMS) with flow capacity greater than 4000 Sm³/h by the end of 2025 without incurring penalties, except for postponements. PRMS with flow capacity greater than 30000 Sm³/h require compulsorily gas chromatographs. However, there are more than 7600 PRMS where the PiPe4.0 GMU could be proposed only for the Italian market. It is

clear that even entering a smaller portion of the market (10-20%) could give important numbers. Obviously, the extension to the EU market makes commercial considerations even more attractive, without considering any other fields of use such as combustion control in electricity generation, for example.

In summary, the GMU introduces a novel and high-impact dimension to Pietro Fiorentini's technological landscape. By combining optical sensing innovations with industrial-grade integration capabilities, it enables a new class of intelligent instrumentation aligned with the demands of digitalized, sustainable, and secure gas infrastructure. This development reinforces the company's role as a forward-looking player in the global energy transition, while also unlocking new opportunities for data-driven process optimization and advanced gas quality assurance.

4 Conclusions

The PiPe4.0 project successfully developed and validated the GMU and DSU for advanced on-line NG monitoring. The GMU, now demonstrating a TRL of 8/9, consistently meets the stringent OIML R 140 Class A standards for HV accuracy (within $\pm 0.5\%$) and repeatability (0.2%) across a wide operating temperature range of -20°C to 50°C . This performance has been rigorously validated both in laboratory climatic chambers and through long-term field installations in NG pressure reduction stations, biogas plants, and pioneering HNG injection sites in Italy. The GMU's capability to provide comprehensive, real-time gas composition and thermodynamic property measurements without requiring consumables or external gas carriers marks a significant advancement over traditional methods like gas chromatography, streamlining quality control and billing processes. Furthermore, its design allows for the re-injection of analyzed gas, aligning with contemporary environmental regulations.

The DSU, having achieved a TRL of 6/7, is a self-powered system specifically engineered for distributed sensing within gas pipelines. Its core thermoelectric energy harvesting unit and power management board are ATEX certified for operation in hazardous environments (Zone 2). Through continuous optimization, the DSU has demonstrated significantly improved reliability and performance in real-world operational environments. By leveraging thermal gradients from pipelines to autonomously measure and wirelessly transmit selected parameters, the DSU offers a viable solution for remote and continuous network monitoring, eliminating the need for external power supplies or frequent battery replacements.

The GMU is poised for broader commercialization within the NG sector, offering process control capabilities for blending operations, shale gas analysis, and petrochemical processing, with potential expansion into flue gas analysis. The DSU's validated self-powered capabilities lay the groundwork for widespread distributed sensing networks, which are crucial for comprehensive network status monitoring, thereby enhancing safety and optimizing energy distribution in evolving gas infrastructures. These integrated innovations collectively establish a new approach for efficient, sustainable, and secure fuel gas management in the context of global decarbonization efforts.

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Abstract

Unpredictability is usually perceived with a sense of uneasiness and discomfort. However, when it comes to secure our data, information, posts, pictures and whatever flows to (or from) the internet about us, protection relies on unpredictability. The impossibility for an eavesdropper or a hacker to break the walls protecting our digital life depends on secret keys, protocols and cyphering algorithms, namely the art & science of cryptography. Keys, essential to lock&unlock the doors, must be randomly generated. And true randomness implies unpredictability.

Random Power harnesses the quantum properties of semiconductors to generate a virtually endless stream of random bits feeding cyber-security systems. The principle is embodied in a Silicon device and benefits from micro-electronics advances; the source of randomness is endogenous and this is a genuine paradigm shift with respect to existing devices, providing simplification and robustness of the system; quantum properties of matter make unpredictability irreducibly unbreakable.

The principle at the base of RaP! was embodied in a platform of devices, including a custom Application Specific Integrated Circuit. The quality of the randomness resulting by the devices was proven relying on the highest ranked procedures and independent tests. The architectures were designed and implemented according to the prescription by the U.S. National Institute of Standard and Technology and the first step towards certification completed.

The Intellectual Property is protected by a patent already granted in Europe, U.S., China and Japan. A spin-off company was established for the exploitation of the project results and a binding agreement for a seed investment by private venture capital firms was signed.

Keywords: True Random Number Generationn (TRNG); quantum tunneling; avalanche breakdown; cryptography

1 Technology Description and Benchmark

Random Power targets the development of a platform of random bit streamers, starting from time series of self-amplified pulses seeded by quantum tunneling phenomena.

In the macroscopic world as we perceive it, particles are seen as tennis or ping-pong balls, bouncing back when they hit a wall; however, in the microscopic world governed by quantum mechanics, sub-atomic particles may also behave as waves and not hard-core nuts. Waves are associated to the surface of lakes, seas and oceans but light is also a wave, an electromagnetic wave. Light across a dark glass can be attenuated, its intensity reduced but, unless the glass is truly black, a bit of it can go through an escape beyond the “barrier”. This is what happens when a sub-atomic particle hits a wall, a barrier of energy. Unless the barrier is infinitely high (the equivalent of a truly “black glass”), the sub-atomic particle can occasionally go through like a ghost, and escape. The probability for this to occur (again, the equivalent of the attenuation of light through an opaque glass) depends on the energy of the particle and the height of the barrier but the key points are that it does occur and we do not know when it does and the phenomenon of escaping is unpredictable. This is **Quantum Tunneling**. Random Power exploits it, embodied in dedicated structures in Silicon dies; when electrons escape the barrier, they enter a region of high electric field, trigger an avalanche multiplication by impact ionization, producing random current pulses. Pulses are detected, time stamped and the sequence of the time labels processed in real-time. Lags between pair of pulses are compared and, at last, this is determining the state of streams of bits, set to 0 or 1 in an unpredictable way.

Random Power can be identified as a True Random Number Generator (TRNG), where bits and then numbers are resulting by the analysis of unpredictable natural phenomena. Coin tossing is possibly the easiest TRNG example, where 0’s and 1’s can be associated to the appearance of a head or tail. Millions of coins can be flipped and this will teach us whether the coin is fair and the underlying probability distribution function; however, our knowledge will never be able to tell whether the next launch will give us head or tail with more than 50% probability. In a similar way, Random Power can be seen as a platform of quantum-based coin flippers, embodied in custom boards and an ASIC (Application Specific Integrated Circuit), a microchip.

Assessing real randomness is not trivial and the qualification of the random bit streams was a significant step. Random Power relies on test suites [RUKIN] offered by the U.S. National Institute of Standard and Technology (NIST), complemented by a customized TESTU01 library [ECUYER] developed by one

of the leading experts in the field. Moreover, the hypothesis of the stream to be made of Independent and Identically Distributed (random) variables (IID property) was assessed, a pre-requisite towards certification. At last, the raw bit stream Shannon's entropy, a measurement of unpredictability, was measured.

1.1 The Random Power platform of bit streamers

During the ATTRACT Phase 1 and Phase 2 project, the consortium developed three embodiments of the quantum-tunneling based random bit streamers:

- **The Single Generator Board (SGB)** is the Minimum Viable Product showing the Random Power principle. Smaller than a credit card, interfaced and powered through a USB port, it can provide up to 100 kHz of quantum entropy. It features on-board proprietary firmware based on-line sanity-checks and a SHA-256 real-time entropy conditioning function, namely a post-processing step which can be activated by the user relying on an algorithm vetted by NIST. Time stamping of the random pulses is performed by an FPGA based proprietary Time-to-Digital Converter (TDC) with 32 ps granularity and a self-calibration procedure. The device is compatible with Windows, Linux and MacOS and comes with a testing GUI and a Python SDK. A description of the SGB and the architecture of the TDC can be found in [CACCIA].

Thanks to the plain-Python code provided in bundle, the board is capable of performing entropy injection into the `/dev/random` entropy pool in Linux and can provide entropy to the backend of the widespread NumPy Python library. The SGB is a plug&play, low cost device aimed for preliminary assessments and practice by the end users; moreover it provides a platform for a series of table-top experiments in applied statistics aimed to the educational market.

Beside specific end-user oriented applications, the development of the SGB is completed. The layout and the actual board are shown in *Figure 1*.

Figure 1. Layout and actual realization of the single generator board.

- The Multi-Generator Board (64xMGB)** is based on an array of 64 independent generators, with analog pulses processed by the LIROC front-end chip, produced by Weeroc, a consortium partner company. The LIROC identifies the occurrence of each pulse and produces the digital signals feeding the firmware integrated 64 independent TDC's. The board is controlled by a System-On-Module (SOM) integrating an UltraScale FPGA and a powerful quad-core ARM processor, making the 64xMGB a computer-on-a-board with 4 GB RAM and 16 GB eMMC. It runs on a Linux OS and secures the critical operations in the Trusted Execution Environment. The board can operate in both stand-alone mode, connected to an ethernet network, or as a PCIe card inside a server. The raw bit stream rate is up to 30 Mbps and a firmware implemented Deterministic Random Bit Generation (DRBG) scheme, as of the NIST SP 800-90A/B/C, [NIST-SP800-90A, NIST-SP800-90B, NIST-SP800-90C] makes it [FIPS-140-3](#) compliant, as outlined in the following section. Taking into account the execution

time of the DRBG and tuning the refresh rate of the seed with quantum entropy, the FIPS compliant rate can achieve values in the Gbps range.

The board is the ideal platform for the deployment of custom applications exploiting the quantum entropy for data encryption, privacy and computing applications. The system can be customized just as any other ARM-based single board computer, but the product is bundled with a general purpose, flexible architecture designed fit designed to make the system a randomness-as-a-service platform, with the possibility to encrypt the output bit stream.

A prototype board was produced and qualified in September 2023; **product grade boards were delivered in September 2024 and fully qualified**, with no obvious flaws and limitations. **By the time of writing, the focus is on the development of an end-user oriented flexible and secure software architecture**, aimed for serving a plurality of users and customizable for specific applications. The alpha version was released in July 2025 and the beta is targeted for the end of 2025. The layout and the actual board are shown in Figure 2.

Figure 2. Layout and actual realization of the multi-generator board.

- **The RaP! Application Specific Integrated Circuit (ASIC)** is the flagship element of the RandomPower technology. It is based on a commercial mixed-signal 180 nm CMOS process and it can be integrated inside any product with the same easiness of any QFN100 integrated circuit.

The chip needs a simple single-rail power supply and offers two separate SPI (Serial Peripheral Interface, clocked at 24 MHz) interfaces, being compatible with almost any SoC (System On Chip), CPU (Central Processing Unit), FPGA (Field Programmable Gate Array) or MCU (Micro Controller Unit) on the market. The first SPI channel is used for the configuration of the ASIC and optimal parameter setting and it can be permanently disabled to avoid any misuse. The second SPI allows end-users to control, re-calibrate the chip and generate entropy. The chip embodies the NIST SP-800 A/B/C

DRBG protocol for FIPS-140-3 compliancy up to prediction resistance (see next section for details). The optimal operational parameters are stored in OTPs (One Time Programmable memories) for maximizing safety and optimal operation. The design maximum bit rate is 32 Mbps in FIPS compliant mode and about 3 Mbps in raw mode. Moreover, the bit stream can be AES-256 encrypted and signed. Keys are generated through an on-chip Key Derivation Function, starting from a root key embedded in Silicon and customer and chip identifiers. The key never leaves the chip and a copy is provided to the end user, as generated by a dedicated engine. The layout of the chip and the actual realization are shown in Figure 3.

Figure 3. Top view of the chip layout and its realization.

Because of the embedded features, the RaP! chip goes beyond a pure bit streamer and it can be considered the cornerstone of high resiliency Root-of-Trust architectures for industrial IoT and critical infrastructures. Moreover, it can be the engine for Quantum Key Distribution (QKD) networks, Hardware Security Modules (HSM) and Public Key Infrastructures (PKI).

Throughout the project, 12 wafers resulting from an engineering run were produced, with four different flavors in terms of implant dose optimization. Six more wafers for the optimal dose profile are being processed by the time of writing. **The sixteen essential functionality**

blocks were fully qualified and proven to work; as a consequence, an initial batch of 500 chips were sent for being packaged (QFN100).

1.2 Qualification and entropy measurement

As outlined above, quality of the bit stream was assessed relying on the NIST test suite and on a customized version of the TESTU01 library, together with a proof for the series of bits to be IID, namely to be made of Independent and Identically Distributed Symbols. Moreover, a series of on-line tests were implemented; as far as the NIST DRBG procedures tests, they were embedded also in the ASIC and firmware implemented in the 64x MGB. Complementary tests based on the MONOBIT and RUNS tests, respectively measuring asymmetries in the number of 0's and 1's and the statistics of the bit flips in a sample, were firmware coded in the control of the 64x MGB. Details are reported in [BPA], which got the Best Paper Award at the 2024 IEEE Cyber Security and Resilience Conference.

Beside details on the qualification, it is worth mentioning the measurement of the Shannon and min-entropy [HCOL] of the raw bis streams, at last the ultimate qualifier. The Shannon entropy is defined as:

$$H(X) = -\sum_{x \in \mathcal{A}} P_X(x) \log_2 P_X(x).$$

Where X is a discrete random variable with possible outcomes in \mathcal{A} and $P_X(x)$ is the probability to have the specific x value. In the Random Power platform, streams are generated in strings of 4 bits, namely an alphabet of 16 possible symbols (2^4 configurations). In case of perfect randomness, all configurations are equally probable and $P_X(x) = 1/2^4$ for every outcome, leading to a value $H=4$. Worth noting that 2^H can be seen as the average number of trials required to guess the value of an outcome. In case of non-uniform $P_X(x)$ or values resulting by a measurement of the probability of every outcome, the same concept can be associate to the so-called min-H (minimum entropy), defined as:

$$H_{\infty} = -\log_2[\max_{x \in \mathcal{A}} P_X(x)]$$

providing the boundary on the number of trials required to guess the most likely value of the random variable.

Values of min-H were measured in bit streams from a set of SGB's and exemplary results are reported in Figure 4, confirming the extremely high degree of raw randomness produced by the mechanism at the base of Random Power and its embodiment. More advanced measurements based on the failure frequency of the NIST on-line tests are reported in [BPA], confirming the quality of the "raw" randomness to be at world class level.

Figure 4. Measurement of the min-Entropy in the bit stream of an exemplary SGB. The horizontal axis identifies the symbol coded in the 4 bits resulting by every iteration of the randomness extraction algorithm used by Random Power. The vertical axis corresponds the probability of every symbol to occur.. The dashed red line is the expected value presuming perfect, uniform probability. The measured min-H value and its uncertainty are reported.

2 Technology Applications

Random numbers generated by sequences of bits are essential for our digital world, providing secret keys to encrypt and decrypt our data, building up protocols to guarantee privacy and authenticating access. Beside cybersecurity, randomness is the core of numerical simulations of complex systems, notably for Science, the financial markets, engineering and weather forecasting and for image rendering addressed to medical and recreational applications. As outlined below, the technology platform developed by Random Power was designed with cryptography applications in mind, with exemplary applications on the way.

2.1. Technology Applications tested during the ATTRACT Project

The major application of the RaP! platform is the enforcement of the security layer of digital communications and data storage/transfer over the internet. As a consequence, both the multi-generator board designed for data centers and the chip targeted to Internet-of-Things (IoT) and critical infrastructure security systems were designed to be compliant to the NIST standards, a pre-requisite for the FIPS-140-3 certification, the relevant protocol by NIST. This implies to design and implement architectures going beyond pure random bit streamers and notably requiring:

- Implementing NIST specified on-line quality tests
- Implementing a hybrid mechanism, where raw bit streams are used to seed the so-called Deterministic Random Bit Generator (DRBG), namely an algorithm mathematically proven to provide random bits as long as seeded by random bits of “sufficient” quality.

Beside these irreducible requirements:

- The ASIC was designed to provide authentication and encryption of the bit stream, using AES-256 protocols
- The ASIC includes a Key Derivation Function (KDF) where, starting from a root key encoded in Silicon and providing public material (customer ID and chip ID), a unique key is generated. The key never leaves the ASIC and a factory owned secure engine is set-up to generate keys that are then distributed to the end-user in a secure way (e.g. by delivery of hardware encrypted supports or post-quantum key encapsulation systems, by now not implemented yet).

This architecture was also embodied in the multi-generator board, in firmware; moreover, being the multi-generator board controlled by a System-On-Module integrating an ARM quad-core processor, a flexible and customizable software architecture for serving in a secure way a multiplicity of users was designed, incapsulating in the Trusted Execution Environment of the ARM processor all the critical operations related to the board control and, whether required, key generation, storage, encryption/decryption of data blocks.

FIPS-140-3 certification, as far as this class of devices is concerned, proceeds through three steps:

1. The [Cryptographic Algorithm Validation Program](#), essentially certifying the DRBG mechanism. This initial assessment was completed and the NIST certificate issued before the tape-out of the chip. **The certificate, submitted by NAGRA-Kudelski, a project partner, can be traced at this NIST repository [link](#) and it applies as well to the firmware implementation in the multi-generator board, based on the same procedure at Register Transfer Language (RTL) level;**
2. [Validation of the entropy source](#) through a sub-set of the tests embedded in the NIST suite and the proof of the stream to be made of Independent and Identically Distributed (IID) random variables. Within the consortium, the NIST recipe for the IID property assessment was coded, together with complementary statistical indicators and run over bit streams produced by the platform elements. **By the time of writing, the assessment of the streams by a set of ASICs and by the product-grade board started and it is planned to enter the Entropy Source Validation (ESV) in Fall 2025; data from the single generator board are IID compliant.**
3. Validation of the hardware module/chip through the so called [Cryptographic Module Validation Program \(CMVP\)](#). This is the final step required to obtain the FIPS-140-3 certification which would be an asset in the exploitation path. According to consultants by SERMA, an European based NIST qualified partner, the designed features of the ASIC and the multi-generator board make the products eligible up to level 2 out of 3. Entering the program is considered in the exploitation plan, following the outcome of the ESV and planned for 2026.

2.2. Technology Applications envisioned after the ATTRACT Project

The development of exemplary applications in the cyber-security field is considered highly strategic and it actually started already during the final phase of the ATTRACT project, thanks to two short-term Italian grants at national phase:

- Supported by the [CYBER4.0](#) Competence Centre, Random Power, meant as the company spun-off the project, is targeting the

development of a Root-of-Trust based on the entropy provided by the RaP! chip for IoT networks. In details:

- a. A RaP! chip carrier board in the form an ARDUINO compliant shield was designed and commissioned
- b. The carrier has been interfaced to a development board by NORDIC semiconductor, hosting the [nRF9161 System-In-Package](#), possibly one of the most advanced communication platforms for IoT
- c. An analysis of the different communication protocols for IoT identified in the [DECTnr+](#) the most promising standard designed for industrial and professional applications, both because it relies on the non-cellular 5G protocol and because it leaves open essential features like mechanisms for key encapsulation and distribution, offering the possibility to develop procedures that, once validated, could be widely adopted.

By the time of writing (August 2025) a preliminary architecture has been designed and it is being implemented, with the major goal of an exemplary deployment by December 2025.

- Supported by [NQSTI](#), the Italian National Quantum Science and Quantum Technology Institute, Random Power is qualifying a platform for Differential Privacy (DP), notably one of the highly considered paradigms to guarantee the impossibility to identify by cross-analysis individuals contributing to a database. The principle, developed by Cynthia Dwork and co-workers [DP], is essentially based on adding random variables distributed either according to a Laplacian or gaussian distribution to the quantity of interest, trading off information with privacy preservation. In a seminal paper [[USCensusBureau](#)] by researchers at the U.S. Census Bureau, it was shown that in order to guarantee the planned privacy preservation, true random numbers rather than pseudo-random numbers should be used, triggering the development of a dedicated in-house randomness farm based on Quantum-Random Number generators (Q-RNG). In the on-going project, the three major open source libraries for DP were compared, a metric for assessing the impact of the use of the RaP! QRNG was developed and, by the time of writing, the final assessment based in

robustness against DP specific attacks is being completed with the target to deploy a toy platform.

Beside exemplary applications, Random Power targets the development of a series of RaP! chip carriers, from a low-cost plug&play USB stick to an advanced PCI-EXPRESS “entropy booster” controlled by an FPGA, collecting the raw entropy by a plurality of chips, implementing in firmware the DRBG and serving high-rate entropy consumers like Hardware Security Modules (HSM) or Quantum-Key Distribution (QKD) systems.

3 Commercialization

Exploitation of the ATTRACT project results will be pursued through the company identified by the project short name, established in Italy by the time of ATTRACT phase 1 (June 2021) as a spin-off company of Università dell’Insubria and AGH-University of Krakow. Company establishment followed the participation to the so-called [2020 Start-Cup Lombardia](#), Italy, where Random Power got the first prize in the ICT sector, and the two prizes assigned by venture capital firms during the national phase called [Premio Nazionale per l’Innovazione](#). One of them, named [LifTT](#), a venture capital firm located in Torino (Italy), proceeded with a so called [Proof-Of-Concept investment](#), a limited amount which was essential to get started, be qualified by third parties and start in the proper way the learning procedure towards entrepreneurship. Beside events which brought to the establishment of the company, it is worth mentioning that Random Power was one of the 25 winners of a worldwide competition launched by the [Falling Walls Foundation](#) in 2022 and it had the opportunity to be [on stage](#) during the FW Science Symposium in Berlin in November 2022.

In 2024 and 2025, as the technology platform advanced towards maturity, the team probed the interest by the market participating to a number of trade fairs, thanks also to the support by the [Italian Trade Agency](#):

- [Embedded world](#) 2024 (Nuremberg, Germany) possibly the most important fair in IoT and embedded systems, hosted at the booth of SECO, a consortium partner;
- [IoT solutions world congress](#) 2024 and 2025 (Barcelona, Spain), hosted by IMASENIC, a consortium partner, and supported by the Catalan government
- [RSA Conference](#) 2025 (San Francisco, U.S.A.), possibly the most relevant event in cybersecurity

- [VivaTech](#) 2025 (Paris, France), one of the major events addressed to start-ups

The feedback was extremely positive and gained confidence in the value of what it is being proposed, establishing a series of contacts (undisclosed for the sake of confidentiality) aimed to both sales and partnerships for co-development of advanced products based on RaP! platform.

In terms of **Intellectual Property**, it is worth mentioning that the patent [RaPatent] protecting the principle at the base of Random Power has been granted in Europe, U.S., Japan and China, waiting for the feedback by the examiners in South Korea. Moreover, the know-how and IP co-developed during the ATTRACT project has been licensed to the spin-off company and guarantees the full freedom to operate with returns to the involved public research organizations and companies on a royalty based scheme and with guarantee of Research exemption.

Thanks to the advancement throughout the ATTRACT project, Random Power could raise interest in international Venture Capital firms and by the time of writing a seed investment binding agreement has been signed with four new investors, including a U.S. based firm (details still undisclosed until closing, subject to the feedback by the Italian Authorities under the “Golden Power” right). The investment was anticipated by a SAFE contract (Simple Agreement for Future Equities) by current and new shareholders which, together with a bank loan and the two Italian grants outlined above, could guarantee the full company functionality until the closing of the investment.

The current investment round, expected to cover the needs for three years, is focused on the exploitation of the existing platform and, as a mid-term milestone, the identification of the features of the second generation products and the engineering of the public-private procedure to acquire the required resources to start it. In short, through the one-year long negotiations with investors:

- An update business plan over three years was completed;
- Relevant markets and main actors within were identified, drafting a go-to market strategy accordingly, supposed to start in Q4-2025;
- A thorough comparative analysis with respect to competitors was performed, confirming the value of both the complementary security features embedded in the chip and the value of having a multi-generator board controlled by a system-on-module with an ARM processor;
- Plans for completing the FIPS-140-3 certification were drafted;

- Plans for performing comparative robustness tests under side-channel attacks and preliminary contacts with a certified laboratory has been established
- Workplans for providing a series of chip carriers have been finalized
- Activities for exemplary applications showcasing the value of the Random Power platform were already started (see above)
- A thorough legal due diligence was completed, essential to assess the viability of the investment.

In summary, the Technology Readiness Level achieved during the ATTRACT project made the project of interest for investors, built a network of committed research and industrial partners and triggered an industrial action based on synergy and co-development of a plurality of actors with complementary skills and competences at European level and beyond.

4 Conclusions

Thanks to the support by ATTRACT, the original concept of generating random bit sequences based on quantum tunneling and the analysis of self-amplified time series of pulses was developed up to a maturity stage raising interest in venture capital firms, supporting with a seed investment the completion of a platform of embodiments, including a custom Application Specific Integrated Circuit, a micro-electronics chip, the implementation of the envisaged go-to-market strategy, the growth of the spin-off company resulting by the project activities and the analysis of the market needs in view of the engineering of the second generation products.

Random Power, grown at European level and including companies, universities and research laboratories, is proving the value of collaborative efforts steered by a common objective, made possible by a balanced investment by the public and private sector.

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The gold standard in biosensing, *reinvented*

Expanding the reach to microscale analytes

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Abstract

This project extends the capabilities of Surface Plasmon Resonance (SPR), a widely used technique in biosensing, to enable the detection and analysis of larger, more complex biological analytes such as bacteria, viruses, extracellular vesicles, and even whole cells. By introducing active transport mechanisms and gradient-based surface functionalization, the platform now supports both advanced research applications and clinical diagnostic use cases. These enhancements allow for more efficient detection, improved signal quality, and the quantification of multivalent interactions (avidity), opening up new possibilities in fields ranging from infectious disease diagnostics to immunology and pharmaceutical development.

Keywords: biosensing; in-vitro diagnostics; avidity; surface plasmon resonance; electrochemistry; microfluidics; research tool; medical technology

1 Technology Description and Benchmark

We took Surface Plasmon Resonance (SPR) imaging—a staple in biosensing—and expanded its reach to analytes it was never designed to detect. Traditionally limited to small molecules and proteins up to molecular weight of 1 MD, SPR has now been re-engineered to handle whole cells, viruses, and bacteria, enabling applications that range from fundamental research to point-of-care diagnostics.

This transformation was achieved by introducing two synergistic innovations within the same platform:

1. A method to actively transport nano- to microscale analytes toward the sensor surface, overcoming the fundamental limitations of diffusion, using an electric field (**ESPR**)
2. A gradient-based approach to quantify avidity—the collective binding strength of multivalent interactions—especially for large analytes like cells (**Tipping Point SPR**)

Together, these developments turn SPR from a molecular-scale analytical tool into a versatile biosensing platform capable of measuring functional interactions across a wide range of size scales and biological contexts.

1.1 SPR, Reinvented

Surface Plasmon Resonance has long been the gold standard for label-free detection of molecular interactions. It measures changes in refractive index near a gold-coated surface, enabling real-time kinetic measurements without fluorescent tags or amplification steps. It does so by observing the shift of the angle at which there is the highest energy transfer from incident light in plasmons generated in the thin gold film, simply with a brightfield camera.¹

But despite its strengths, traditional SPR is confined to analytes that diffuse rapidly. Molecules in the 1–10 nm range are ideal; anything much larger—such as bacteria (~1 μm), vesicles (~50–300 nm), or cells (5–20 μm)—either diffuses too slowly or produces unpredictable signals. Moreover, conventional SPR focuses on affinity: the strength of one molecular interaction, not the avidity of many weak ones working together, which is more relevant in immunology, cell adhesion, and many drug mechanisms. Our platform addresses both of these limitations in a unified way.

1.2 Extending the Reach: From Molecules to Cells

The first core innovation is the integration of electric field enhanced mass transport into the SPR platform. By applying a mild voltage across the gold sensing surface, a field is generated that gently drives suspended analytes—such as bacteria or extracellular vesicles—toward the sensor. This drastically reduces the time needed for analyte binding and ensures that even rare or slow-moving particles make contact.²⁻⁴

This “field-enhanced” mode of operation transforms SPR into a viable tool for clinical diagnostics, where analytes are often large, rare, or suspended in complex media. It allows simultaneous detection of pathogens (e.g. *Borrelia* in the case of Lyme disease diagnostics) and host response markers (e.g.

antibodies or cytokines) in a single assay. Proof-of-principle studies have already been completed using synthetic particles, and a clinical feasibility study is now being initiated in collaboration with a diagnostic partner, focusing on Lyme disease. The platform is ready for clinical proof-of-concept evaluation and sample collection has started.

The second innovation, gradient-based surface functionalization, further extends the platform's analytical power. By patterning the sensor surface with a gradient of ligand density, we can measure not just whether something binds, but how many interactions are needed before it binds stably. This reveals the avidity tipping point: the threshold at which a cell, vesicle, or protein complex becomes "functionally sticky." This approach yields an avidity fingerprint of each analyte, providing actionable insight in contexts such as immune cell activation, cancer immunotherapy, antibody-drug conjugate screening and cell adhesion studies.

This gradient-based methodology has already been tested in multiple industrial settings and is nearing market readiness. The technology readiness level (TRL) for this mode is 7: several working demonstrators have been tested at major biopharma and biotech companies, and purchase commitments for scaled deployment are now pending.

FIG. 1. SPR instrument (left) and EPR module (right)

1.3 Benchmarking Against the State of the Art

<i>Capability</i>	<i>Traditional SPR</i>	<i>Re-engineered SPR Platform</i>
Compatible analyte size	1–10 nm	1 nm – 20 μm
Mass transport	Passive diffusion	Active field-driven (for small particles)
Sensitivity to large particles	Poor	High (via enhanced delivery and signal)
Avidity measurement	No	Yes (via ligand density gradient)
Typical sample matrix	Buffer	Complex biological fluids (plasma, serum)
Use cases	Protein–protein interactions, drug discovery	Pathogen detection, immune monitoring, cell–ligand avidity profiling
TRL	8–9 (mature)	7 (gradient), 4–5 (diagnostic mode)

1.4 A Platform for Both Research and Diagnostics

The unified SPR platform developed here bridges a gap between research instrumentation and clinical diagnostic potential:

- In biotech and pharma, it enables quantitative avidity profiling at the cellular or vesicular level—offering a new layer of insight that goes beyond affinity-based screening.
- In clinical diagnostics, it allows high-resolution detection of pathogens and immune markers in native samples, with minimal preparation time and label-free detection.

With its modular architecture, the platform can support both use cases: a research version optimized for multiplex avidity screening, and a diagnostic version geared for clinical throughput.

In short: SPR has evolved. What began as a tool for measuring molecular affinity now becomes a window into the functional interactions of complex biological entities—cells, pathogens, vesicles—with real-world relevance in both health and disease.

2 Technology Applications

Surface Plasmon Resonance (SPR) has long been one of the workhorses of biosensing, widely used to study molecular binding kinetics in pharmaceutical and academic settings. Traditionally, it excels at detecting small molecules and proteins, but fails when analytes become larger, sparser, or structurally complex. By redesigning SPR and implementing the SPR imaging approach from the ground up—both physically and chemically—we created a platform that applies the same trusted principles to whole cells, bacteria, viruses, and vesicles, and can measure not only *affinity*, but *avidity*: the functional strength of multivalent interactions.

During the ATTRACT project, we explored both **research** and **diagnostic** applications of this re-engineered imaging platform. The work culminated in two complementary capabilities:

- (1) *gradient-based avidity quantification (Tipping Point SPR)* and
- (2) *field-enhanced transport for single-particle diagnostics (ESPR)*

Below we describe both the validated use cases and the applications now in development.

2.1. Technology Applications tested during the ATTRACT Project

A central objective of the project was to assess the platform’s utility in real-world scenarios. To that end, **seven demonstration studies were performed on-site at potential users’ facilities**, ranging from public health laboratories to academic research groups to multinational biotech companies. These studies tested both the technical capabilities and the relevance of the new SPR modes in applied contexts.

One high-impact use case involved the **functional avidity mapping of anti-CCR8 T cells** using a chemokine-mimetic peptide (AP8ii).¹ In this setup, immune cells were flowed over a sensor surface coated with a gradient of ligand density. By measuring where each cell type began to bind stably, we extracted an “avidity threshold” that quantitatively distinguishes activation states and receptor expression profiles.

Blocking the CCR8 receptor with antibodies resulted in a clear, dose-dependent shift in binding patterns. This study, conducted with our CellVysion system, demonstrated that **avidity can be quantified in a single, label-free measurement**, a feature not offered by flow cytometry or conventional SPR.

Feedback from users highlighted the platform's ability to:

- Deliver **functional readouts** that reflect multivalent binding, not just binary on/off interactions.
- Replace labor-intensive assays with **single-step, high-content** measurements.
- Detect weak or transient interactions that often escape other methods.

These results validated the gradient technology at **TRL 7**, with multiple partners expressing interest in purchasing units for internal R&D workflows. The insights from these studies shaped refinements in optical stability, ligand immobilization protocols, and fluidic control—ensuring the system meets the reliability expectations of industrial users.

FIG. 2 Top) ESPR sensorgram showing cyclic attraction and repulsion of analyte along with switching the mass transport potential. Middle) Ligand density schematic indicating where the ligand density crosses a threshold after which multivalent immobilization stabilizes the analyte. Bottom) Results of experiment where the effect of opsonization is quantified.

2.2. Technology Applications envisioned after the ATTRACT Project

The next development phase focuses on deploying this technology in **clinical diagnostics**, where its unique capabilities can address long-standing unmet needs.

Conventional diagnostic tools like ELISA or PCR often target either the pathogen *or* the immune response—not both. They also tend to struggle with trade-offs between speed, sensitivity, and information content. Our new SPR platform, redesigned to work in complex matrices and to detect particles and molecules simultaneously, offers a way forward.

The diagnostic system now under development builds upon three components:

1. **Field-enhanced particle delivery:** A mild electric field gently drives analytes such as bacteria or extracellular vesicles toward the sensor surface, dramatically accelerating the assay. This enables **minute-scale detection**, even in plasma or urine.
2. **Multiplexed readout:** SPR imaging captures interactions across thousands of distinct surface spots simultaneously. This allows **parallel detection** of a pathogen and associated immune biomarkers, such as IgM/IgG antibodies or cytokines, from a single sample.
3. **Plug-and-play coating chemistry:** The sensor surface is pre-functionalized with a universal reactive layer that enables rapid conjugation of specific recognition elements—antibodies, antigens, aptamers—tailored to each disease context.

The system is intended for **clinical proof-of-concept studies**, beginning with infectious disease diagnostics. The initial focus is on conditions where traditional tests often fail to distinguish between *past exposure* and *active infection*. In such cases, **simultaneous detection of pathogen and immune response** is critical for correct interpretation and treatment planning.

A first clinical study will center on blood samples from patients suspected of Lyme disease. The goal is to assess:

- Sensitivity of bacterial detection in early-phase infections
- Concordance between antibody profile and bacterial presence
- Throughput and stability under routine lab conditions

Sample collection has already begun. When successful, this will mark one of the first demonstrations of **direct, label-free detection of pathogens and antibodies in the same test**, with time-to-result under 10 minutes.

Future diagnostic applications may include:

- **Urinary tract infections**, where current tests are slow or insensitive
- **Sepsis panels**, combining pathogen load with cytokine release markers
- **Pandemic preparedness**, allowing rapid reprogramming of assay surfaces

The diagnostic branch of the platform is currently at **TRL 4–5**, with a clear roadmap toward regulatory validation through clinical partnerships and modular assay development.

Envisioned Research Applications: CAR-T Engineering and Beyond

The avidity profiling mode—based on SPR imaging over ligand density gradients—is also opening new doors in **cell therapy research**, notably in the development of **CAR-T and CAR-NK** treatments.

In these therapies, the strength of interaction between a modified immune cell and its target is a key determinant of both efficacy and safety. Too strong, and healthy tissues expressing low levels of the target antigen may be attacked. Too weak, and tumor cells escape recognition.

Tipping Point SPR imaging enables researchers to measure, for the first time:

- **The ligand density at which engineered immune cells begin to bind stably under a fixed shear flow condition.**
- **The kinetics of cell engagement and detachment across a gradient**
- **The effect of receptor design (e.g. hinge domain or co-stimulatory motif) on avidity**

This approach provides a **functional fingerprint** of a CAR construct, supporting rational design choices and potency assays. It complements—but does not replace—methods like cytotoxicity assays or cytokine release profiling. Instead, it serves as an **early-stage screening tool**, allowing developers to identify candidates with a favorable avidity profile before moving to expensive in vivo studies.

Moreover, the label-free nature and single-use cartridge format make the platform attractive for **GMP-compatible QC testing** of cell therapy batches.

In sum, the re-engineered SPR platform serves both translational research and clinical diagnostics. Whether helping a biotech company fine-tune the next generation of CAR-T cells, or empowering physicians to diagnose infection in real time, it offers a unified, high-resolution window into the functional biology of complex analytes.

3 Commercialization

The ESPRIT platform is more than a research outcome; it is a commercially viable, modular system designed to support both cutting-edge bioscience and real-world diagnostic workflows. The foundational innovations—field-enhanced analyte transport and ligand-density-driven avidity quantification—have been translated into robust hardware and consumable products, jointly brought to market by two industrial partners: **Vysens**, responsible for instrument design, assembly, and sales; and **ECsens**, the exclusive supplier of the ESPRIT module and SPR imaging chips.

This collaboration ensures that the complete system, when delivered with field-enhanced functionality, is commercialized under the name **EVysion**. In its standard SPR configuration (without the ESPR module), the platform is sold under the name **CellVysion**. All systems support SPR imaging and multiplexed analysis, but EVysion uniquely enables rapid, label-free detection of submicron analytes in complex fluids—a key capability for future diagnostics.

By clearly dividing responsibilities and protecting intellectual property through binding agreements, the platform is built to scale and support downstream assay development by third parties, while maintaining tight control over quality, compatibility, and support.

FIG. 3. Commercialization plan

3.1 Current commercial activity and traction

Vysens has already begun commercial deployment of the **CellVysion** instrument to a growing network of early adopters in **academia, pharma, and biotech**. These are high-content research users who value the platform’s imaging-based SPR approach, ease of functionalization, and label-free kinetics.

Applications currently in use include:

- Avidity screening of therapeutic immune cells against engineered ligand gradients
- Real-time binding analysis of extracellular vesicles and viruses

- Custom assays for antibody-based drug candidates with multivalent binding profiles

These research users typically acquire both instruments and consumable chips on a per-project basis. ECsens supplies the chips and field-enhancement modules through an exclusive OEM model, ensuring end-users receive a unified and fully supported experience. These interactions also serve as **pre-commercial pilots** for future diagnostic modules, helping validate both technical performance and user expectations.

To further accelerate traction, demo units have been deployed for extended trials at key opinion leaders in immuno-oncology and cellular therapy development. These engagements have already resulted in interest for broader adoption and co-development of custom avidity assays.

3.2 Commercialization strategy: two-stage deployment

The commercialization roadmap is explicitly **bifurcated** to separate the dynamics of research and diagnostics:

1. Research Use Only (RUO) Track

Instruments and chips are immediately available to assay developers and life science researchers. In this model, the system is not subject to regulatory constraints, and users are free to develop their own coatings, assays, and fluidic protocols. The platform is sold as **RUO hardware**, supported with functionalization kits and open-access surface chemistry.

These users form the backbone of early revenue. They are typically familiar with label-free biosensing but frustrated with the size limitations and low throughput of conventional SPR systems. EVysion offers them an upgrade path: better sensitivity, larger analyte range, and support for complex assays in native biological media.

2. CE-IVD Clinical Track

In parallel, ECsens and Vysens support external assay

developers in building CE-marked diagnostics based on the EVysion platform. Once an assay developer has completed technical and clinical validation, they can apply for CE-IVD status as the **legal manufacturer**. Upon certification, they gain a license to procure validated EVysion hardware and ESPR consumables for use in clinical labs.

This model enables a **distributed innovation model**, where assay developers retain control over the biology and regulatory path, while ECsens and Vysens ensure consistent and CE-ready hardware components. The business model allows flexible licensing and procurement schemes adapted to the size and scope of each diagnostic partner.

Early adopters of this pathway are focused on infectious disease diagnostics (e.g., Lyme disease, urinary tract infections), where simultaneous detection of pathogen and immune response provides clear clinical value.

3.3 Risk mitigation and scalability

To minimize barriers to market entry, the entire system has been designed for **scalable production** and **modular use**:

- **Chips and reagents** are batch-manufactured with standardized surface chemistry, ensuring reproducibility across users and time points.
- **Instruments** are built around off-the-shelf components where possible (optics, imaging, control), while the ESPR module is compact, low-voltage, and robust to temperature and humidity.
- **Coating protocols** have been optimized for shelf-stability and shipping, allowing for plug-and-play installation even in field conditions.

Manufacturing risk is limited by the fact that the hardware is already in production for RUO customers, and chip production has already been scaled to support multiple industrial users during the ATTRACT project. Consumable costs are projected to remain competitive, with

ample margin for assay developers to build business models around clinical deployment.

To further de-risk market entry, the consortium deliberately chose Lyme disease as a target for initial validation. This indication combines:

- A clear unmet need (current diagnostics are poor at distinguishing early vs. late infection)
- A known biomarker set (Borrelia antigens, IgM/IgG)
- An accessible clinical network for sample access and evaluation

A first proof-of-concept clinical study will begin in the next project phase, with assay development supported by the same coating and fluidic protocols used in the RUO platform. The study is designed not only to validate clinical performance, but also to fine-tune usability, assay design, and cost per test.

3.4 Market outlook and long-term vision

The EVysion platform is designed to support **multiple diagnostic verticals**, each developed by partners or licensees in their respective domain. Beyond Lyme disease, clear opportunities exist in:

- **Immuno-oncology**: detecting cell–ligand avidity shifts in response to therapy
- **Cell therapy QC**: verifying CAR-T or NK cell functionality via gradient binding profiles
- **Urinary tract infection**: detecting pathogens and host markers in a single test
- **Pandemic response**: rapidly reprogrammable detection surfaces for emerging pathogens

The modular architecture supports both **standalone benchtop use** and **integrated clinical deployment**, making it attractive for use in both core labs and decentralized care settings.

As more assays are developed, the platform becomes increasingly valuable. The growing installed base of EVysion instruments lowers the barrier to assay adoption, creating a network effect where each new application strengthens the platform's utility. This dynamic mirrors other successful diagnostic platforms where hardware is subsidized or bundled to enable recurring consumable revenue.

Ultimately, EVysion offers a pathway to **multi-analyte, high-content diagnostics** that go beyond simple yes/no answers. It delivers layered, functional insight—on how strongly things bind, how fast they react, and what that means for health and disease.

4 Conclusions

This project reinvented Surface Plasmon Resonance (SPR) by extending its capabilities far beyond molecular interactions. By introducing active analyte transport and gradient-based avidity analysis, the platform now enables the study of complex, multivalent biological interactions—at the scale of bacteria, vesicles, and even whole cells.

Two key technical advances form the backbone of this transformation. First, a mild electric field can now be used to accelerate the delivery of analytes to the sensing surface, making label-free detection of pathogens and immune markers feasible even in complex clinical samples. Second, a ligand density gradient applied to the sensor surface allows for the quantification of avidity—providing a functional fingerprint that reflects how strongly and under what conditions analytes engage.

These features unlock unique applications in both research and diagnostics. In research, tipping point SPR provides new tools for CAR-T and antibody screening, avidity quantification, and immunological profiling. In diagnostics, the platform supports the simultaneous detection of pathogens and host biomarkers in a single drop of blood, enabling faster and more informative testing.

Over the course of the project, the system was demonstrated at seven external sites, including industrial and clinical partners. The avidity gradient technology reached TRL 7, with several large companies now preparing to adopt the platform. The diagnostic mode, now branded

EVyision, is ready for proof-of-concept studies in Lyme disease diagnostics, with sample collection underway.

Commercialization has already begun. The CellVysion instrument is being sold for research use, while EVyision will support future CE-IVD assays through a partner-driven model. ECsens and Vysens continue to scale up production of the chips and instruments, ensuring a reliable supply chain and clear IP boundaries.

This project has laid the foundation for a new generation of biosensing tools that bridge the gap between molecular insight and clinical utility—making SPR not only faster, but fundamentally more capable.

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